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D6.1. Environmental engineering master study plans report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The D6.1 Environmental Engineering Master Study Plans report summarizes research that compares Environmental Engineering master's curricula across the European Union, aiming to help Uzbekistan update its programs to meet European Union standards and best practices.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full form
EE	Environmental Engineering
EU	European Union
STEM	Science-Technology-Engineering-Math
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
WP	Work Package
MS	Master of Science
ASTI	Andijan State Technical Institute
KIUT	Kimyo International University in Tashkent
IPVC	Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo
UAVEIRO	Universidade de Aveiro
UVIGO	Universidad de Vigo
JizPI	Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute
EEMCD	Environmental Engineering Master Course Databases

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1 Introduction

Uzbekistan is actively transforming its higher education system, with a focus on Environmental Engineering (EE), to better meet the nation's growing environmental challenges. The redesign aims to offer educational programs that are both internationally respected and professionally relevant. Traditional curricula have often failed to bridge the gap between education and employment, especially in fast-changing scientific and technical sectors. Responding to national priorities and aligning with the European Union's Green Deal objectives, this project is developing modern EE Master's degree programs that adhere to European standards while remaining sensitive to local needs.

The D6.1 EE Master Study Plans report is a key initial output, presenting an in-depth comparative analysis of European EE study plans, teaching practices, and curriculum structures. These insights guide the creation and execution of new, sustainable EE Master's courses in Uzbekistan, preparing graduates with advanced Science-Technology-Engineering-Math (STEM) skills, research abilities, and practical know-how needed for sustainable development at both the national and regional levels.

1.1 General description of typical EE MSc programs in Europe

Master of Science programs in EE in Europe are typically structured as intensive, two-year curricula that prioritize scientific precision, interdisciplinary scope, and practical applicability within the labour market and industry. These programmes consistently utilize the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), enabling enhanced student mobility and facilitating comparability of qualifications among academic institutions.

European EE Master programs offer a balanced curriculum integrating core engineering, environmental policy, sustainability, and technology. The curriculum typically includes:

- Foundation modules in environmental science, engineering mathematics, and core environmental engineering concepts.
- Specialized courses covering sustainable development, climate change mitigation, water and wastewater treatment, air quality management, resource recovery, and environmental impact assessment.
- Interdisciplinary learning elements, including courses on policy, environmental economics, legislation, and management, often in collaboration with industry.
- Extensive laboratory work and field-based training to build hands-on skills.
- Opportunities for research projects, internships, and industry placements, culminating in a thesis focused on contemporary environmental challenges.

Admission usually requires a relevant engineering or scientific bachelor's degree, though some programs accept broader STEM backgrounds. Curricula now include digital skills, innovation, and green transition modules to meet EU priorities. Graduates gain advanced STEM, research, and environmental problem-solving skills, preparing them for professional and leadership roles in the field.

2 Methodology

Work Package 6 (WP6) began in January 2025, launching the research phase on EU EE Master Study Plans. The team created a unified template to standardize the collection and analysis of MSc curricula from top EU universities.

The methodology involves organizing the data collection process into four clearly defined phases:

- Part A: General information (degree title, university, ECTS, duration, etc.)
- Part B: Course-specific learning aims, outcomes, and competencies by semester
- Part C: Distribution of course subjects as a percentage breakdown by application area
- Part D: Compilation of good practice examples including laboratories and teaching innovations

The WP6 leader team: Andijan state technical institute (ASTI) used this method and template to set up a thorough way of comparing and summarizing EU practices. This provided solid evidence for updating the curriculum and ensuring that new EE Master’s programs in Uzbekistan match accepted European standards.

At the project kick-off meeting on February 18, 2025, at Kimyo International University in Tashkent (KUIT), the research tasks for compiling and benchmarking EU curricula in EE were officially distributed among the project partners. Each institution is tasked with studying MSc EE programs in designated European Union countries as outlined below:

Table 1 Distribution of tasks around the project partners

Partner	EU countries
Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo (IPVC)	Portugal, Poland, and England
Universidade de Aveiro (UAVEIRO)	Romania, Türkiye, and Republic of Cyprus
Universidad de Vigo (UVIGO)	Spain, Slovakia, and Slovenia
KIUT	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, and Croatia
ASTI	Sweden, Czech Republic, Denmark, and Estonia
Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute (JizPI)	Finland, France, Germany, and Greece
Fergana Politehnika Instituti (FerPI)	Hungary, Ireland, Italy, and Latvia

This distribution ensures a coordinated effort and supports the creation of a robust comparative repository of EU EE Master’s study plans by ASTI team.

3 Key findings

3.1 Overview of Data-Gathering and Representation

The results of the data-gathering efforts among project partners were formally presented during the Second Project Meeting, which took place at UVIGO, Spain, on July 14–15, 2015. This comprehensive review involved a detailed, country-by-country tally of EE Master’s programs that were examined across Europe. In total, the study encompassed 87 universities spanning 21 European countries. This extensive representation ensured that the comparative analysis was both robust and inclusive, providing a solid foundation for benchmarking and aligning new master’s programs in Uzbekistan with established European standards.

Figure 1 Number of Environmental Engineering Master's Programs by Country

The graph shows strong representation from Italy (12 universities), Spain (10), and Germany (6), along with coverage in France, Sweden, Denmark, and others. Each bar indicates how many universities' MSc Environmental Engineering curricula were included for benchmarking. This wide dataset enables effective comparative analysis to help align Uzbekistan's new master's programs with European standards.

3.1.1 Programme Curriculum Components (Part A)

At the 2nd Project Meeting (July 14–15, 2015, UVIGO, Spain), project partners discussed findings on EE Master's programs in Europe. This analysis shows that most programs are standard Environmental Engineering degrees, but many also incorporate management, technology, and sustainability, highlighting the field's interdisciplinary scope in Europe. Most programs (55%) are titled "Environmental Engineering," with other specializations including Environmental Science (14%), Environmental Management (8%), Environmental Technology (6%), Sustainable Environmental Engineering (6%), and Environmental and Resource Engineering (5%).

Figure 2 Distribution of master's Program Titles in Environmental Fields

The decision to establish a **2-year duration** for the new EE Master's program was driven by a comparative analysis of international standards. As illustrated in the data, the 2-year format is by far the most prevalent model, accounting for **69** of the analyzed programs. This significantly outweighs other formats, such as the 1.5-year duration (9 programs) and the 1-year duration (6 programs).

Figure 3 Duration of Environmental Engineering Master's Programs

The ECTS framework standardizes master's programs, with 120 ECTS being the norm for EE degrees—67 programs use it, versus 10 with 90 ECTS and 6 with 60. Adopting 120 ECTS enhances compatibility and recognition in Europe and internationally.

Figure 4 ECTS of Environmental Engineering Master's Programs

The Master thesis is a confirmed **mandatory requirement** for the new EE Master's program. This decision is strongly supported by the comparative analysis of EU programs, which showed that most reviewed curricula—specifically **83 programs**—require a thesis, indicating a clear international standard.

Figure 5 Master thesis of Environmental Engineering Master's Programs

Based on international benchmarking and consensus reached at the 2nd Project Meeting in Vigo, Spain, the EE Master's program was established as a 2-year course totaling 120 ECTS credits, structured to include a mandatory Master thesis.

Table 2 EE master program structure

Title of the master program	Environmental Engineering
Duration	2 years
ECTS	120 (30 ECTS per semester)
Language	Uzbek and English
Master thesis	Yes

Comprehensive information pertaining to PART A, including its objectives, structure, content, and any associated requirements or guidelines, can be found in Appendix 1. This appendix serves as a detailed reference for all aspects related to PART A and should be consulted for a thorough understanding of its scope and particulars.

3.1.2 Course-Specific Learning Aims, Outcomes, and Competencies (Part B)

The Course-specific learning aims/outcomes/competencies (Part B) define the academic focus of the new EE Master's program. The project's main goal is to create a curriculum that meets European standards and addresses environmental challenges locally and globally. Using the Environmental Engineering Master Course Databases (EEMCD), the team analyzed core EU courses to identify essential content, forming the basis for module design and targeted learning outcomes.

Figure 6 Most used courses of Environmental Engineering Master's Programs

The analysis shows that core modules in Sustainability and Environmental Engineering are heavily relied upon. The top nine modules, each with a "Repeatability" score of 18, are central to the program and considered essential. These include key areas like "Quantitative Sustainability," "Environmental Modelling," and "Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems." Importantly, "Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining" is also a top module, highlighting the importance of advanced data science and quantitative skills in environmental and engineering

work. On the other hand, more specialized topics such as "Environmental Chemistry" (Repeatability: 10) and "Air Pollution Control" (Repeatability: 7) appear less frequently, suggesting the program prioritises broad, interdisciplinary subjects with significant impact.

Appendix 2, labeled as EEMCD, provides all key information regarding PART B—such as module titles, semesters, ECTS credits, and outcomes. Please consult this appendix for a comprehensive understanding.

3.1.3 Distribution of the course subjects (Part C)

The result shows that, in European EE Master's programs, Engineering Sciences occupy the largest proportion of courses at 50.7%, followed by Natural and Earth Sciences with 23.8%. Physical and Mathematical Sciences represent 9.7% of the curriculum, while Social and Policy Sciences account for 7.0%. Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields contribute 8.2%, and Supervised Learning Experience makes up 10.3%, indicating a significant emphasis on practical training alongside core scientific and engineering subjects.

Table 3 Distribution of the course subjects

Scientific Area	Average in EU (%)
Engineering Sciences	50.7
Natural and Earth Sciences	23.8
Physical and Mathematical Sciences	9.7
Social and Policy Sciences	7.0
Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields	8.2
Supervised Learning Experience	10.3

Appendix 3 provides detailed information on this subject.

3.1.4 List of good practice examples (Part D)

European EE master's programs showcase exemplary practices by fostering global collaboration, integrating advanced research, and emphasizing practical skill development, which is evident in their comprehensive program structures.

In the sphere of **Double degree and Erasmus projects**, universities actively pursue international academic partnerships through established Joint and Double Degree offerings—such as the Sustainability Engineering Double Degree at the University of Antwerp, opportunities for dual diplomas at Cracow University of Technology, and involvement with Erasmus Mundus Joint Master consortia that enable students (for example, at ULB) to complete up to 30 ECTS credits abroad without hindering their studies.

On the **Research** front, these programs maintain robust connections to major initiatives, frequently obtaining substantial EU support—including several ERC grants awarded to institutions like TU Wien and Ghent University—and drawing both regional and European funding for student-centric projects. Students routinely contribute to hands-on, applied research tackling real-world environmental issues, working alongside external partners as part of internships (as seen at the University of Seville) or collaborative projects such as Nova University Lisbon's Environmental Engineering Project.

Excellence in **Education** is achieved through inventive teaching approaches, including "The Aalborg Model for Problem Based Learning (PBL)," as well as the facilitation of student-led undertakings—like DTU's Blue Dot projects and innovation initiatives at Università di Padova. Programs also feature multidisciplinary, project-oriented courses, with requirements such as public exhibitions defending master's theses at TU Wien.

State-of-the-art **Laboratory** resources form a critical asset, featuring specialized facilities like the Environmental Trace Analysis Laboratory (CeMESS) equipped with gas/liquid chromatography linked to triple quadrupole MS, the Environmental Mass Spectrometry (EMS) Facility, and the Hydrogeology & Contaminant Interface Laboratory employing XAS technology for pollutant mobility analysis. These are complemented by practical on-site experiences at infrastructure locations, including wastewater treatment plants.

Lastly, rigorous **Quality assurance** mechanisms are in place, supported by certified internal management systems audited by organizations like AQ Austria (an ENQA member listed in EQAR), ASIIN accreditation for core engineering tracks, and conformity to European Higher Education Area (EHEA) criteria. Select master's programs have also earned esteemed international distinctions, such as the EUR-ACE label.

4 Discussions

4.1 European Good Practice Models

These best practices of the EU universities are distinguished by a consistent focus on research excellence, internationalization, applied pedagogy, and stringent quality assurance.

1. European universities are prioritizing research in Green Digital Transition (GreenDT) and receiving substantial funding and infrastructure support:

- **Sustainable Water Management:** Developing low-energy wastewater treatment, managing micropollutants, and remediating groundwater contamination.
- **Circular Economy:** Advancing waste valorisation technologies and sustainable resource management.
- **Climate Adaptation & Energy:** Innovating renewable energy integration and climate adaptation for urban and water systems, e.g., National and Kapodistrian University of Athens's H2TRANS hydrogen station project.
- **Funding & Scale:** Universities demonstrate success with competitive grants—Ghent University has 120 ERC grants, University of Vienna reached €117.6 million in third-party funding in 2023, and TU Wien researchers have received various ERC grants.
- **Advanced Infrastructure:** Specialized labs support research, such as the Environmental Mass Spectrometry (EMS) Facility, Hydrogeology & Contaminant Interface Laboratory (XAS analysis), and DTU's E-MAT facility for new energy materials discovery.

2. Applied Pedagogy and Industry Collaboration for Workforce Development. This educational approach equips graduates to apply GreenDT solutions right after graduation:

- **Problem-Based Learning (PBL):** Universities like Aalborg use the "Aalborg Model for PBL." Others, including DTU and University of Pisa, have student-led projects on sustainability.
- **Mandatory Industry Integration:** Formal partnerships and practical experience are required. ULB collaborates with over 30 environmental consultants and NGOs, providing internships and projects worth up to 10 ECTS credits. Nova University Lisbon mandates external partner involvement in engineering projects.
- **High Employability and Innovation:** The applied curriculum leads to strong career prospects—over 90% of TU Wien graduates find jobs within six months. The i²c incubator at TU Wien fosters research spin-offs and startups. Graduates are ready for roles in clean-tech, consulting, R&D, and government agencies.

3. Internationalization is central to European universities, ensuring globally relevant environmental practices.

- Double Degrees & Erasmus Mundus: Structured mobility programs like the Master of Applied Ecohydrology (MAEH) allow students (e.g., through ULB’s Erasmus Mundus consortia) to study up to 30 ECTS abroad without academic delay.
- Global Accessibility: Many master’s courses—including Environmental Systems in Vienna—are offered fully in English, increasing international enrollment (ULB: 25–30%, UAntwerp: 18%).
- Interdisciplinary Collaboration: International structures promote cross-field work, such as ULB’s M-ENVIG track integrating Geography, Economics, Law, and Civil Engineering.

4. Quality assurance is maintained through rigorous processes and recognized certifications:

- External Certification: The University of Vienna’s QA system is externally audited and certified by AQ Austria, meeting national and European standards. AQ Austria is an ENQA member listed in EQAR.
- International Program Accreditation: Programs are internationally accredited, including EUR-ACE for the master’s at Universitat Rovira i Virgili and ASIIN for TU Wien’s engineering courses.
- EHEA Compliance: Institutions such as TalTech and ULB fully comply with EHEA standards, enabling qualification recognition across Europe and supporting professional mobility and research collaboration.

Figure 7 European Good Practice Models

In summary, sources describe European University Environmental Practices as an integrated system supported by leading research, strict quality control, innovative teaching, and international collaboration. This ensures universities play a central role in ecological and digital transitions.

4.2 Scheme for development of master study plan

The Figure 8 scheme illustrates a structured process for updating educational components based on the EU model. The figure shows a cyclical process where external EU standards are adopted via course selection, applied to curriculum and materials, reviewed by peers and committees, and then documented.

Figure 8 Scheme for development of master study plan

Here is a detailed breakdown of the components and flow within the scheme:

Inputs and Initial Stage. The process begins by drawing information from two primary sources: The EU database (Appendix 2) and European Good Practice Models.

Both sources feed directly into the Course selection stage.

Implementation Levels. The course selection results and overall goals are managed through a centralized system of implementation, which is structured into three distinct levels, all based on the EU model:

- **High level Implementation:** The focus here is to Update the standards based on the EU model.
- **Middle level Implementation:** This stage is responsible for Updating the master study plan (curriculum) based on the EU model.
- **Low level Implementation:** This level concentrates on Updates course syllabuses, new teaching materials, and methods based on the EU model.

These implementation levels are connected to the project's Work Packages (WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5).

Review and Feedback Loops. The implementation process involves important review and discussion stages:

- **Peer Review:** The implementation levels (specifically the Low level) are subject to Peer review. This review is conducted by the Tashkent State Technical University and the Ministry of Higher Education. The results of the Peer review feed back directly into the implementation levels, indicating a necessary adjustment or validation loop.
- **Steering Committee:** The implementation levels also feed into a Discussion: Steering Committee.

Output and Submissions. The final stages of the scheme involve submission and documentation:

- The discussion led by the Steering Committee leads to D6.2.
- The overall scheme includes a requirement for Submission to the FTOP system.

The figure summarizes a cyclical process in which external EU standards are integrated by selecting courses, updating curriculum and teaching materials, undergoing peer and committee reviews, and then documenting the results. This approach ensures ongoing feedback and alignment with EU models through structured review and submission steps.

Appendix 1

Part A. General Information

#	Country	University	Title	Duration	Semester	ECTS	Language	Master thesis
1	Portugal	University of Aveiro	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English, Portuguese	Yes
2	Portugal	University of Porto	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
3	Portugal	Nova University Lisbon	Environmental Management and Systems	2	4	120	English, Portuguese	Yes
4	Portugal	University of Lisbon	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English, Portuguese	Yes
5	Poland	Gdańsk University of Technology	Science in Environmental Engineering	1.5	3	90	English	Yes
6	Poland	Cracow University of Technology	Science in Environmental and Land Engineering	1.5	3	90	English	Yes
7	Poland	Warsaw University of Technology	Science in Environment Protection Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
8	Poland	Czestochowa University of Technology	Intelligent Energy for Environmental Protection	1.5	3	90	English	Yes
9	Romania	University Politehnica of Bucharest	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	Romanian	-
10	Romania	Politehnica University of Timișoara	Environmental Engineering and Management in Industry	2	4	120	-	Yes
11	Romania	Babeș-Bolyai University (Cluj-Napoca)	Sustainable Development and Environmental Management	2	4	120	Romanian, English	Yes
12	Romania	Dunărea de Jos University of Galați	Environmental quality and sustainable development	2	4	120	Romanian	-
13	Romania	Dunărea de Jos University of Galați	Sustainable development and security in industry	2	4	120	English	-
14	Türkiye	Middle East Technical University	Environmental Engineering	-	-	-	-	Yes
15	Türkiye	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	Environmental Sciences Engineering and Management	-	-	-	Turkish, English	Yes

#	Country	University	Title	Duration	Semester	ECTS	Language	Master thesis
16	Türkiye	Boğaziçi University	Science program in Environmental Sciences	2	4	126	-	Yes
17	Türkiye	Hacettepe University	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
18	Türkiye	Yıldız Technical University	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	-	Yes
19	Cyprus	University of Cyprus	Environmental Engineering	2	4	90	English	Yes
20	Cyprus	Cyprus International University	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
21	Cyprus	Open University of Cyprus	Sustainable Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
22	Spain	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	Environmental Engineering	1.5	3	90	Spanish	Yes
23	Spain	University of Santiago de Compostela	Environmental Engineering	1.5	3	90	Spanish	Yes
24	Spain	University of Seville	Environmental Engineering	1	2	60	Spanish	Yes
25	Spain	Polytechnic University of Cartagena (UPCT)	Environmental and Sustainable Process Engineering	1	2	60	Spanish	Yes
26	Spain	University of Huelva and International University of Andalucía	Environmental Technology	1	2	60	Spanish	Yes
27	Spain	University of A Coruña	Environmental Sciences, Technologies and Management	1	2	60	Spanish	Yes
28	Spain	Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)	Environmental Engineering and Energy Sustainability	1.5	3	90	Spanish	Yes
29	Spain	University of Cantabria	Environmental Engineering	1.5	3	90	Spanish	Yes
30	Spain	European University of the Atlantic	Environmental Engineering	1	2	60	Spanish	Yes
31	Spain	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	Spanish	Yes
32	Slovakia	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU)	Environmental Protection Technology	2	4	120	English	Yes
33	Slovakia	University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Trnava (UCM)	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	Slovak	Yes
34	Slovenia	University of Ljubljana	Water Science and Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	Slovenian	Yes

#	Country	University	Title	Duration	Semester	ECTS	Language	Master thesis
35	Austria	University of Vienna	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
36	Austria	Technical University of Wien	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	German	Yes
37	Belgium	Ghent university	Environmental Science and Technology	2	4	120	English	Yes
38	Belgium	University of Antwerp	Environmental Science	1	2	60	English	No
39	Belgium	Université libre de Bruxelles	Environmental Science and Management	2	4	120	English, French	Yes
40	Sweden	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	Environmental Engineering and Sustainable Infrastructure	2	4	120	English	Yes
41	Sweden	Lund University	Environmental Studies and Sustainability Science	2	4	120	English	Yes
42	Sweden	Chalmers University of technology	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
43	Denmark	Technical university of Denmark	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
44	Denmark	University of Copenhagen	Environmental Science	2	4	120	English	Yes
45	Denmark	Aarhus University	Agronomy and Environment	2	4	120	English	Yes
46	Denmark	Aalborg University	Water and Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
47	Denmark	University of Southern Denmark	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
48	Czechia	University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague	Sustainability and Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
49	Estonia	Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech)	Environmental Engineering and Management	2	4	120	English	Yes
50	Ireland	Trinity College Dublin	Environmental and Resource Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
51	Ireland	University College Cork	Environmental and Resource Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
52	Ireland	University College Dublin	Environmental and Resource Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
53	Ireland	University of Galway	Environmental Management	2	4	120	English	Yes
54	Italy	Politecnico di Milano	Natural Resources, Land Use, and Environmental Protection	2	4	120	English	Yes

#	Country	University	Title	Duration	Semester	ECTS	Language	Master thesis
55	Italy	Politecnico di Torino	Disaster and Risk Management	2	4	120	English	Yes
56	Italy	Polytechnic University of Milan	Animal Ecology	2	4	120	English	Yes
57	Italy	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies – Pisa	Agriculture and Conservation	2	4	120	English	Yes
58	Italy	Sapienza University of Rome	Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
59	Italy	University of Bologna	Landscape ecology	2	4	120	English	Yes
60	Italy	University of Milan	Environmental Impact Assessment	2	4	120	English	Yes
61	Italy	University of Naples Federico II	Climate Change Ecology	2	4	120	English	Yes
62	Italy	University of Padua	Environment, Waste Management, Sustainability Strategies	2	4	120	English	Yes
63	Italy	University of Pisa	Environmental Management	2	4	120	English	Yes
64	Italy	University of Turin	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
65	Italy	Università di Padova	Marine and Coastal Ecosystem Biology, Climate Change, Genetic and Molecular Methods, Marine Conservation and Ecosystem Monitoring	2	4	120	English	Yes
66	Latvia	University of Latvia	Management, Landscape and Animal Diversity and Ecosystem Monitoring	2	4	120	English	Yes
67	Finland	Aalto University	Water and Environmental Engineering – Master of Science (Technology)	2	4	120	English	Yes
68	Finland	University of Oulu	Water and Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
69	Finland	Tampere University	Water and Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
70	Finland	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology (LUT)	Environmental Technology	2	4	120	English	Yes

#	Country	University	Title	Duration	Semester	ECTS	Language	Master thesis
71	Finland	University of Eastern Finland	Environmental Health and Technology	2	4	120	English	Yes
72	France	École Polytechnique	Environmental Engineering and Sustainability Management	2	4	120	English	Yes
73	France	Centrale Méditerranée	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
74	France	Grenoble INP - Ense ³	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
75	France	Université de Poitiers - ENSIP	Environmental Engineering	3	6	180	French	Yes
76	France	INSA Toulouse	Water Engineering and Water Management	2	4	120	English	Yes
77	Germany	Leibniz University Hannover	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	German	Yes
78	Germany	Technical University of Munich	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
79	Germany	KIT, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
80	Germany	Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH)	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
81	Germany	Universität Stuttgart	Air Quality Control, Solid Waste and Waste Water Process Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
82	Germany	RWTH Aachen University	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
83	Greece	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	Greek	Yes
84	Greece	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTh)	Environmental Engineering	1.5	3	90	English	Yes
85	Greece	University of Crete	Environmental Engineering	1.5	3	90	English, Greek	Yes
86	Greece	University of Patras	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes
87	Greece	University of Ioannina	Environmental Engineering	2	4	120	English	Yes

Appendix 2

PART B – Course-specific learning aims/outcomes/competencies

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
1	Introduction to Environmental Science	1	15	Students know the fundamentals of ecological and biogeochemical approaches in environmental science and are able to carry out and communicate statistical analyses of study results.
2	Introduction to Environmental Chemistry	1	15	Graduates of this module have profound knowledge of environmental and geochemical processes and mechanisms that play a key role in environmental systems. They know methods of analytical environmental chemistry.
3	Environmental System Laboratories	2	30	Students have profound practical knowledge of subject areas in the field of environmental science.
4	Individual Research Projects	3	10	Students are able to plan and implement a small research project in the context of current research that prepares them for their master's thesis and includes all necessary steps. Students conduct literature analysis, formulate testable hypotheses, apply analytical and statistical methods to address new issues, structure the experimental approaches and laboratory work, present and interpret results and write a report in the form of a short publication.
5	Individual Specialisation	3	20	Students acquire profound knowledge of the subject area in which they write their master's thesis. They know the key concepts, theories and hypotheses in this area and are able to interpret and discuss the results of individual research in this broad context.
6	Master's Thesis	4	25	The master's thesis serves to demonstrate the student's ability to achieve adequate standards of content and methodology when independently addressing academic topics. The assignment for the master's thesis must be chosen in a way that the student can reasonably be expected to complete it within six months.
7	Vertiefende Grundlagen des Umweltingenieurwesens	1	20	Deepens interdisciplinary foundational knowledge in geodata acquisition & processing, energy technologies, risk & climate, engineering hydrology, and resource management, supplemented by environmental ethics — equipping students with a solid base for specialized studies
10	Ressourcenmanagement & Siedlungswasserwirtschaft	2	30	Develops advanced expertise in the chosen focus areas — Geodata Processing, Air Quality & Climate Risk, Water Risk, or Resource & Urban Water Management — including technical methods, data analysis, modeling and solution design in each domain
11	Wahlfächer zur Vertiefung und Ergänzung	3	31	Allows individualized curriculum design via electives in sustainability, evaluation, transport & noise, management, economics, and law—broadening the student's interdisciplinary perspective and enriching their environmental engineering profile

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
12	Freie Wahlfächer	3	9	Builds non-technical competencies—such as project management, communication, digital literacy, and language skills — ensuring graduates are well-rounded professionals ready for collaborative, cross-sectoral work
13	Module Environmental Sustainability and Policy	1, 2	13	Have advanced understanding of physical, chemical, and ecological processes in natural and disturbed ecosystems and apply this knowledge to problem solving and decision-making).
14	Module Environmental Diagnostics	1	15	Evaluate causes, consequences and solutions of environmental problems from multiple perspectives (scientifically, technologically, socially, legally, economically).
15	Module Environmental Technology	2	15	Identify and quantify environmental pollution at multiple temporal and spatial scales (from local to global).
16	Module Applied Ecology	1	9	Apply concepts of environmental sustainability, clean technology, the circular economy and resource recovery.
17	Module Research Skills	2	3	Collect, critically evaluate and quantitatively analyze environmental information and data to answer relevant research questions about and to recommend solutions for environmental problems Competence field 2: Technological Competency. Formulate scientifically and technologically up-to-date approaches to diagnose and solve environmental problems in a professional setting.
18	Major Environmental Assessment and Management of Chemicals	3, 4	21	Select the most appropriate measures or technologies to prevent, remediate, or control environmental problems
19	Major Resource Recovery Technology	3, 4	21	Consider uncertainty, ambiguity and risk when formulating solutions for environmental problems. Competence field 3: Interpersonal competency.
20	Major Urban Environmental Management	3	21	Communicate clearly, scientifically correctly, and with scientific integrity in scientific and non-scientific contexts about environmental problems and solutions.
22	Master's Thesis	3,4	30	Have cutting-edge scientific knowledge and technological skills in one of the following specialization domains of environmental science and technology (depending on the chosen major):
23	Hydrocarbons Analysis and Environment	1	5	Students will orient themselves in the issues of basic and advanced analysis of conventional and alternative fuels.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
24	Atmosphere Analytics		5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - analyse the samples of the ambient, indoor and workplace air - analyse the samples of waste gases - measure the flowrate of the waste gases throughout the ducts - express the gaseous mixtures composition and mass flow of the pollutants emitted into the ambient air
25	Water Analysis		4	Students will know the determination methodology of common components of drinking, surface and sewage water and they will know the principles of all determinations. Students will know the procedure of each hydroanalytic determination and they will be able to calculate the results from the measured values, including the correct interpretation of the obtained results.
26	Water Analysis - Laboratory		5	Students will be able to quantify basic components of drinking water, surface water and wastewater, and correctly interpret the results.
27	Environmental Microbiology		4	Student will understand the basics of microbial processes proceeding in the environment and their implications for maintaining equilibrium in the biosphere. In addition, students will acquire both theoretical and practical knowledge in the field of microbial diversity analyses.
28	Atmosphere Analytics: Laboratory	2	4	Students will be able to: sample gases, prepare samples for analysis, perform basic analysis of gaseous sample, put results of analysis in required form
29	Atmosphere Pollution Control		4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nature of air pollution, origins, relative types, characteristics. 2. Sources and relative effects of air pollutants and source control measures. 3. Integrated approaches to air pollution control. 4. Controlling principles and devices for aerosol particles. 5. Controlling principles and devices for gaseous pollutants. 6. Special topics: indoor air pollution, odour pollution and noise pollution control. 7. Meteorological aspects of air pollution and atmospheric self-purifying processes. 8. Atmospheric photochemistry and photochemical smog pollution control strategy. 9. Large-scale effects of air pollution: climate change, ozone layer depletion and acid rain. 10. Energy and air quality management, carbon capture and storage technology. 11. Ambient air and emission monitoring. 12. Air quality management and standards. 13. Stationary (point, area and line) and mobile sources inventory. 14. Fundamentals in air pollution modelling.
30	Power Engineering		6	Students will be able to: Understand the thermodynamic principles and operational parameters of conventional thermal and nuclear power plants, combined cycle, refrigeration cycle and heat pump, principles of corrosion processes and corrosion prevention in power cycles. Calculate mass and thermal balance of a steam generator and the optimal size of demineralization line.
31	Contaminated Soil Treatment		5	<p>On successful completion of the course students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand processes that affect the fate of contaminants in the subsurface 2. Understand many of the basic concepts of contamination and the effects of environmental contamination on human health and environment 3. Summarise remediation methods used at contaminated sites

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				4. Determine if the remediation methods are safe 5. Explain why the remediation methods should be used
32	Waste Treatment Technology		5	Students will be able to apply technical knowledge learned within the course to numerous professional activities, including mainly construction and operation of waste treatment facilities.
33	Fuel Processing and Utilization		5	Students will know: Fundamentals of petroleum processing and production of most important petroleum products. Utilization and basic properties of motor fuels and other petroleum products. Fundamentals of coal and natural gas processing. Utilization and basic properties of alternative liquid and gaseous fuels.
34	Water Treatment		3	Students will be able to: understand and utilized basic design methods for ground and surface water treatment.
35	Green Chemistry	3	3	Students will learn: General concepts of green chemistry Alternative reaction media and possibilities of the intensification of chemical processes Possibilities of biomass utilization for production of fine chemicals Current trends in biomass utilization as an alternative to petrochemical processes
36	Sludge Management		3	Students will be able: to estimate the amount of sludge at various treatment technologies and to evaluate their properties, to choose an optimal alternative of sludge stabilization and other technological stages of sludge treatment to assess the possibilities of material and energy reuse of sludge and to assess the mutual impact of sludge and sewage lines.
37	Product Ecology		5	Detailed knowledge of Life Cycle Assessment method, mechanisms of environmental impacts of industrial activities and environmental product declaration of products and services.
38	Environmental Engineering-Laboratory		3	Both theoretical and practical understanding of basic analytical methods used in environmental technology and engineering focused on wastewater treatment and waste and sludge management. Practical experience with working in a laboratory.
39	Water Management in Smart Cities		5	Students will be able to: - independently asses the advantages and disadvantages of DESAR systems under particular circumstances. - apply the principles of various DESAR solutions and design technological parameters in order to comply with legislation.
40	Biological Wastewater Treatment		6	Students will be able to: understand and work with basic legislative norms of the Czech Republic and of the European Union in the field od wastewater treatment, know biochemical and micorbiological principles of municipal wastewater treatment, describe, explain and calculate the principal technological units of municipal wastewater treatment plant, design different modifications of activated sludge process for nutrioent removal and design tertiary treatment necessary for wastewater reuse.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
41	Water Management in Industry		5	Students will be able to: describe and explain water management systems in industry - generally and in specific water-intensive industrial branches, analyse and evaluate water management of an industrial plant, propose an optimal solution for water management of an industrial plant.
42	Special Separation Methods in Water Treatment		5	Students will be able to: Characterize the individual procedures of desalination methods. Propose the technology of treatment of the given type of water (sea, brackish or surface) for the preparation of drinking water or demineralized water utilizing ion exchange, sorption and membrane technologies. Also, they will be able to use separation and desalination processes to treat the process water and selectively remove unwanted ions and organic substances from water.
43	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
44	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
45	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
46	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
47	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations.</p> <p>Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining.</p> <p>Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science.</p> <p>Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python.</p> <p>Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues.</p> <p>Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.</p>
48	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems • Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system • Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation • Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool • Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting • Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome • Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts • Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context • Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner • Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study • Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
49	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. • Describe methods for characterization of waste. • Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. • Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. • Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. • Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. • Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>system.</p> <p>Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies.</p> <p>Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems</p> <p>Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region</p>
50	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
51	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
52	Environmental Assessment and System Analysis	1	6	<p>Outcomes/competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the system of the main environmental assessment tools, their scope, and area of use. Comprehend the concept of sustainable development in the context of natural resource utilization and production. Analyze material and substance flows. Familiarity with life cycle analysis and environmental risk assessment methodologies.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Develop a systematic understanding of environmental indicators. Brief description: This course provides an overview of environmental assessment and system analysis, focusing on anthropogenic environmental impacts. It covers methods such as Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), and Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA). Students will engage in both theoretical and practical aspects, including case studies and individual projects.
53	Research Methodology		3	Outcomes/competencies: Develop skills in research design, data collection, and analysis specific to environmental engineering. Critically evaluate scientific literature and methodologies. Formulate research questions and hypotheses relevant to environmental studies. Apply appropriate research methods to environmental engineering problems. Brief description: This course introduces students to research methodologies applicable in environmental engineering. It covers qualitative and quantitative research methods, data analysis techniques, and the ethical considerations in conducting research. The course prepares students for their master's thesis work. Learning outcomes On completion of this course the student should have an: 1) understanding of the research process including ethics and good research practice principles; 2) ability to carry out focused and critical reviews of academic literature 3) ability to define a research aim, objective and set of research questions or hypotheses 4) ability to identify and develop the relevant research concept and methodology to meet a research objective; 5) ability to write research outputs at a Master thesis level.
54	Water and Wastewater Treatment Technologies		6	Understanding water management and treatment processes After completing the course, the student: 1) Comprehends the physical, chemical, and biological processes in water and wastewater treatment. 2) Can evaluate treatment technologies for different environmental contexts. 3) Applies knowledge to practical water management projects. Content: Technologies for water purification, wastewater treatment, and recycling; laboratory work and real-world case studies.
55	Environmental Management and Policy	2	5	Outcomes/competencies: Gain knowledge of international environmental policy frameworks and their implementation. Understand the role of environmental management in public and private sectors. Analyze the effectiveness of environmental policies and management strategies. Brief description: This course explores environmental management principles and policy development. Topics include sustainability indicators, environmental impact assessments, circular economy, and the roles of various stakeholders in environmental governance. Case studies and guest lectures provide practical insights.
56	Participation in Environmental Governance		3	Outcomes/competencies: Understand the principles of participatory democracy in environmental decision-making. Develop skills in stakeholder engagement and public participation processes. Critically assess participatory approaches in environmental governance. Brief description: The course examines participatory methods in environmental governance, including stakeholder analysis, public

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				consultations, and collaborative decision-making. Students will engage in simulations and projects to practice these approaches.
57	Environmental Impact Assessment and Auditing		6	Ability to assess and mitigate environmental impacts After completing the course, the student: 1) Understands Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) processes. 2) Can identify and evaluate environmental impacts of projects and plans. 3) Develops skills to propose mitigation measures and conduct public consultations. Content: EIA/SEA methodologies, environmental legislation, impact analysis, and public involvement strategies.
58	Hydrological Processes and Modeling	1	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Demonstrate a thorough understanding of the hydrological cycle, including precipitation, evapotranspiration, infiltration, surface runoff, and groundwater flow. · Analyze and model hydrological processes using physically based and empirical methods. · Apply hydrological modeling tools (e.g., SWAT, HEC-HMS) to simulate watershed behavior and evaluate the impacts of land use and climate change. · Interpret model outputs critically and calibrate models using observed environmental data. · Communicate hydrological assessments effectively for both scientific and policy-making audiences.
59	Environmental Data Analysis and Statistics	1	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Collect, process, and analyze environmental datasets using statistical and computational techniques. · Apply statistical methods such as regression analysis, hypothesis testing, multivariate analysis, and time series analysis to environmental data. · Use software tools such as R, Python, or MATLAB to conduct advanced environmental data analytics. · Assess uncertainty, variability, and error propagation in environmental measurements. · Visualize complex environmental data using modern graphical techniques to support evidence-based decision-making.
60	Water and Wastewater Treatment Technologies	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Understand the principles and design criteria of physical, chemical, and biological treatment processes for drinking water and wastewater. · Analyze water quality parameters and select appropriate treatment technologies based on pollutant types and concentrations. · Evaluate the efficiency and sustainability of treatment systems in varying operational and climatic conditions. · Design and simulate treatment plant operations using engineering software tools and standards. · Apply laboratory and field knowledge to troubleshoot and optimize real-world treatment systems.
61	Environmental Policy, Governance, and Law	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Demonstrate an understanding of national and international environmental policy frameworks, governance systems, and legal instruments. · Analyze institutional roles, stakeholder dynamics, and policy-making processes related to water and environmental management. · Evaluate the effectiveness of environmental regulations, including compliance mechanisms and enforcement strategies. · Engage in interdisciplinary discourse on ethics, equity, and justice in environmental governance. · Develop policy briefs or governance proposals that incorporate scientific, legal, and socio-political considerations.
62	GIS and Remote Sensing for Environmental Applications	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Operate Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for the analysis and management of spatial environmental data. · Utilize remote sensing techniques to monitor land cover, vegetation, hydrology, and pollution. · Process satellite imagery and spatial datasets using tools such as QGIS, ArcGIS, and ENVI. · Apply spatial analysis methods to support environmental impact assessments, watershed modeling, and conservation

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				planning. · Integrate spatial data with modeling outputs for decision support in resource management.
63	Sustainable Water Resources Management	3	10	· Understand the principles and practices of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM). · Analyze water allocation challenges in the context of competing demands, equity, and ecosystem sustainability. · Design strategies for water conservation, demand management, and reuse under various socio-economic and climatic scenarios. · Evaluate the role of participatory approaches, stakeholder engagement, and transboundary cooperation in water governance. · Apply interdisciplinary methods to assess and optimize sustainable water use at basin and national scales.
64	Climate Change and Water Systems	3	10	· Analyze the physical and socio-economic impacts of climate change on water availability, quality, and infrastructure. · Use climate models and hydrological simulations to predict future water-related risks such as droughts, floods, and sea-level rise. · Evaluate adaptation strategies for water systems at local, national, and global levels. · Integrate climate resilience into the planning and design of water management projects. · Communicate scientific findings and policy implications related to climate-water interactions.
65	Master's Thesis	4	30	· Formulate a clear research question and objectives relevant to water and environmental engineering. · Design and conduct independent, original scientific research using appropriate methodologies. · Collect and analyze empirical or simulation-based data rigorously. · Demonstrate project management skills including planning, time management, and resource allocation. · Produce a comprehensive written thesis and deliver an oral defense that meets academic and professional standards. · Apply ethical research practices and contribute to the advancement of environmental knowledge or policy.
66	Introduction to Environmental Engineering	1	6	- Understand key environmental engineering concepts and their relevance to global sustainability issues - Identify and evaluate environmental challenges through a systems approach.
67	Sustainability Concepts and Frameworks	1	6	- Grasp core theories and frameworks in sustainability science - Apply the triple bottom line (environmental, economic, social) in analyzing sustainability problems
68	Environmental Chemistry	1	6	- Analyze chemical processes affecting air, water, and soil - Understand pollutant behavior, transformation, and remediation pathways
69	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	1	6	- Learn methods for assessing potential environmental impacts of projects and plans - Gain knowledge of EIA procedures, tools, and regulatory frameworks
70	Fundamentals of Sustainability Management	1	6	- Understand sustainability principles in business and industry - Analyze sustainable strategies across supply chains, operations, and product development

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
71	Water Resources Management	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about integrated water resource management (IWRM) approaches - Design and assess water conservation and treatment strategies
72	Waste Management Technologies	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand sustainable waste processing methods including reuse, recycling, and energy recovery - Evaluate the environmental impacts of waste treatment technologies
73	Environmental Data Analysis	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply statistical tools and data science techniques to environmental datasets - Visualize and interpret data to support sustainability decision-making
74	Air Quality Management	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze sources and health/environmental impacts of air pollution - Study regulatory frameworks and control technologies for air quality improvement
75	Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand principles of energy-efficient technologies - Evaluate the role and integration of renewable energy sources in sustainable development
76	Water Resources Management	3	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about integrated water resource management (IWRM) approaches - Design and assess water conservation and treatment strategies
77	Corporate Sustainability Strategies	3	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze how companies embed sustainability into core operations - Develop corporate social responsibility (CSR) and ESG strategies
78	Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation	3	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand climate science and its implications for engineering and policy - Evaluate strategies for reducing emissions and adapting infrastructure and systems
79	Environmental Policy and Regulations	3	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study international and national environmental policy instruments - Assess the influence of policy on sustainable development implementation
80	Sustainability Reporting and Certification	3	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare sustainability reports aligned with GRI, SDGs, and other frameworks - Understand environmental certifications (e.g. ISO 14001, LEED)
81	Capstone Project in Environmental Engineering	4	24	Capstone Project in Environmental Engineering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct a complex real-world sustainability project - Integrate cross-disciplinary knowledge and methodologies - Communicate solutions effectively to stakeholders
82	Environmental Process Engineering	1	10	Understand and model physical, chemical, and biological processes relevant to environmental systems.
83	Hydrology	1	10	Analyze the movement and distribution of water in natural and urban environments.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
84	Environmental Chemistry	1	10	Understand chemical behavior and transformations of pollutants in air, water, and soil.
85	Water and Wastewater Engineering	2	10	Design and evaluate technologies for water supply and wastewater treatment systems.
86	Air Pollution Control	2	10	Understand emission sources, pollutant behavior in the atmosphere, and control technologies.
87	Environmental Analytics	2	10	Acquire skills in environmental sampling, monitoring, and analytical techniques.
88	Waste Management	3	8	Understand and design systems for solid waste collection, recycling, treatment, and disposal.
89	Renewable Energy Systems	3	6	Analyze and evaluate renewable energy sources and integration into environmental systems.
92	Master's Thesis	4	30	Conduct independent scientific research, analyze data, and develop innovative solutions to complex environmental problems. Present and defend results effectively.
93	Environmental Systems Engineering	1	12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand the structure and function of environmental systems - Analyze interactions between natural and engineered systems - Apply systems thinking to environmental challenges
94	Hydromechanics	1	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Master principles of fluid mechanics relevant to environmental engineering - Solve problems in hydraulics and flow behavior - Model water movement in natural and technical systems
95	Environmental Microbiology	1	8	Understand microbial processes in natural and engineered environments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze the role of microbes in pollution and treatment - Apply microbiological methods to environmental problems
96	Water Quality	2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of water - Understand water pollution sources and impacts - Design water treatment methods to improve quality
97	Air Pollution Control	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand sources and types of air pollutants - Design and evaluate air pollution control technologies - Apply regulatory frameworks for air quality management
98	Environmental Chemistry	2	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study chemical transformations and transport of contaminants - Use analytical chemistry techniques for environmental samples - Evaluate chemical risks to environment and health

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
99	Environmental Data Analysis	2	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study chemical transformations and transport of contaminants - Use analytical chemistry techniques for environmental samples - Evaluate chemical risks to environment and health
100	Environmental Data Analysis	2	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply statistical and computational methods to environmental data - Use software tools for data visualization and interpretation - Support decision-making with data-driven insights
101	Urban Water Systems	3	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design and manage urban water distribution and drainage systems - Analyze impacts of urbanization on hydrology - Incorporate sustainability in urban water management
102	Waste Management	3	8	Understand waste generation, collection, and disposal methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply principles of recycling, recovery, and treatment - Evaluate environmental and economic impacts of waste management
103	Renewable Energy	3	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze renewable energy sources (solar, wind, bioenergy) - Assess feasibility of renewable energy integration - Understand policy and environmental implications
105	Master's Thesis	4	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct independent research under supervision - Formulate research questions and hypotheses - Apply scientific methods and data analysis - Write and defend a thesis demonstrating technical expertise and innovation
106	Basics in Environmental Engineering	1	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand key concepts in environmental processes and systems - Learn fundamental environmental challenges and solutions
107	Fluid Mechanics	1	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grasp principles of fluid behavior relevant to natural and technical water systems - Solve basic flow and pressure problems
108	Environmental Physics	1	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze energy flows, thermodynamics, and mass transfer in the environment - Apply physical principles to model environmental processes
109	Environmental Biotechnology	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand microbial processes for pollutant degradation - Apply biotechnology in wastewater and soil treatment
110	Water and Soil Treatment	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design treatment systems for contaminated water and soils - Apply physico-chemical and biological remediation techniques
111	Environmental Analytics	2	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use modern analytical tools for environmental monitoring - Interpret chemical and physical data from environmental samples
112	Waste Management		10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze solid waste streams and their environmental impacts - Plan and evaluate waste treatment and recycling systems

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
113	Renewable Energy Systems	3	10	- Understand principles of wind, solar, biomass, and hydro energy - Evaluate energy projects from environmental and technical perspectives
115	Master's Thesis	4	30	Conducting scientific research, independent analysis and developing solutions
116	Fundamentals of Environmental Engineering	1	10	Understanding core environmental engineering principles
117	Fluid Mechanics	1	10	Applying fluid mechanics to environmental systems
118	Environmental Process Engineering	1	10	Understanding and designing environmental process systems
119	Water and Wastewater Treatment	2	10	Designing and operating water and wastewater treatment technologies
120	Air Pollution Control	2	10	Understanding air pollution sources and implementing control technologies
121	Solid Waste Management	2	10	Applying technologies and strategies for sustainable solid waste management
122	Environmental Modeling	3	7.5	Building and applying models to simulate environmental processes
123	Environmental Biotechnology	3	7.5	Using biotechnological methods in environmental engineering
124	Sustainable Energy Systems	3	7.5	Analyzing and implementing sustainable energy solutions
126	Master's Thesis	4	30	Conducting independent research, analyzing scientific results, and developing solutions
127	Environmental Process Engineering	1	10	Understanding key environmental processes and their technical management
128	Hydrology	1	10	Analyzing and managing surface and groundwater systems
129	Environmental Chemistry	1	10	Understanding chemical processes in environmental systems

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
130	Water and Wastewater Engineering	2	10	Designing and optimizing water and wastewater treatment technologies
131	Air Pollution Control	2	10	Implementing technologies for air quality improvement
132	Environmental Analytics	2	10	Applying data analysis and measurement techniques to environmental problems
133	Waste Management	3	7.5	Developing and applying waste treatment and recycling strategies
134	Renewable Energy Systems	3	7.5	Understanding and integrating renewable energy technologies
137	Master's Thesis	4	30	Independent scientific research and development of solutions to environmental problems
138	Fundamentals of Air Pollution Control	1	10	Fundamentals of air and water quality control, waste management
139	Water Quality Management	1	10	Fundamentals of air and water quality control, waste management
140	Waste Engineering Basics	1	10	Fundamentals of air and water quality control, waste management
141	Advanced Air Pollution	2	10	Solve complex problems and develop practical engineering projects
142	Waste Water Treatment	2	10	Solve complex problems and develop practical engineering projects
143	Solid Waste Processing	2	10	Solve complex problems and develop practical engineering projects
144	Environmental Process Engineering	3	10	In-depth knowledge of specific fields and research project experience
146	Master's Thesis	4	30	Independent scientific research and development of practical solutions
147	Environmental Process Engineering	1	10	Fundamentals of understanding and managing environmental processes

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
148	Hydrology	1	10	Fundamentals of understanding and managing environmental processes
149	Environmental Chemistry	1	10	Fundamentals of understanding and managing environmental processes
150	Water and Wastewater Engineering	2	10	Fundamentals of understanding and managing environmental processes
151	Air Pollution Control	2	10	Fundamentals of understanding and managing environmental processes
152	Environmental Analytics	2	10	Fundamentals of understanding and managing environmental processes
153	Waste Management	3	7.5	Integrated engineering, energy and waste management projects
154	Renewable Energy Systems	3	7.5	Integrated engineering, energy and waste management projects
157	Master's Thesis	4	30	Independent scientific research and development of solutions to environmental problems
158	Environmental Chemistry	1	6	Understanding chemical processes in the environment
159	Environmental Microbiology	1	6	Ability to analyze microbiological processes
160	Environmental Fluid Mechanics	1	6	Water and air flow modeling skills
161	Environmental Data Analysis	1	6	Application of data analysis and statistical methods
162	Wastewater Treatment Processes	2	6	Design of wastewater treatment technologies
163	Solid Waste Management	2	6	Development of solid waste management strategies
164	Air Pollution Control	2	6	Application of air pollution reduction methods

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
165	Environmental Impact Assessment	2	6	Environmental impact assessment of projects
166	Advanced Environmental Technologies	3	6	Application of modern environmental technologies
167	Environmental Policy and Management	3	6	Understanding environmental policies and management strategies
168	Research Methodologies in Environmental Science	3	6	Planning and implementation of scientific research
169	Master's Thesis	4	30	Conducting independent scientific research and presenting results
170	Environmental Chemistry	1	6	acquire laboratory analysis skills.
171	Environmental Microbiology	1	6	Students learn about the role of microorganisms in natural and engineering systems.
172	Water and Wastewater Treatment	1	6	Students gain knowledge about water treatment processes and the design of treatment systems.
173	Solid and Hazardous Waste Management	1	6	In students, various waste management and treatment competencies are formed.
174	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	1	6	Students are taught to study environmental impact and apply the EIA methodology.
175	Environmental Chemistry	1	6	Be able to analyze chemical processes affecting the environment, know the chemistry of pollution
176	Environmental Microbiology	1	6	Understanding microbial processes in ecosystems, methods of bioremediation
177	Environmental Fluid Mechanics	1	6	Ability to model and analyze water and air flows associated with environmental systems

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
178	Environmental Systems Analysis	1	6	Competence in environmental systems modeling, risk analysis and decision-making tools
179	Research Methodology & Scientific Writing	1	6	Formation of scientific research, critical analysis and professional communication skills
180	Waste Management and Treatment Technologies	2	6	Ability to design and evaluate solid waste and wastewater treatment systems
181	Air Pollution Control Technologies	2	6	Knowledge and skills in design and management of atmospheric pollution reduction systems
182	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	2	6	Ability to conduct EIA research, understanding legal framework
183	Renewable Energy and Sustainability	2	6	Understanding sustainable energy solutions and their integration into environmental projects
184	Master's Thesis	3.4	30–60	Conducting independent scientific research and presenting results
185	Environmental Chemistry	1	6	Understanding chemical processes in the environment; being able to analyze pollution pathways and chemical changes
186	Environmental Microbiology	1	6	Knowing microbiological processes; being able to apply microbiological processing methods to water and soil
187	Environmental Systems Analysis and Modelling	1	6	Environmental systems modeling skills; competence in the use of environmental change predictors
188	Water and Wastewater Treatment Technologies	2	6	Mastering physical, chemical and biological methods of treatment; design of sustainable treatment systems
189	Air Pollution Control Engineering	2	6	Ability to analyze air polluting sources; design and management of air quality control systems
190	Master's Thesis	3.4	90	Conducting independent research, analyzing scientific results and developing solutions

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
191	Air Pollution Control Systems	1	6	Develops the ability to design and evaluate air pollution control systems.
192	Chemistry and Physics of Gas and Aqueous Phases in the Environment and Climate Change	1	6	Enhances understanding of chemical and physical properties of gas and liquid phases in the environment, and assesses their impact on climate change.
193	Environmental Analytical Chemistry	1	6	Improves the ability to use analytical methods for detecting pollutants in environmental samples.
194	Liquid Waste Treatment	1	6	Develops understanding of liquid waste treatment processes and the ability to manage them effectively.
195	Seminars of Environmental Law, Economics and Management	1	6	Strengthens knowledge in the fields of environmental legislation, economics, and management.
196	Data Analysis	2	6	Develops the ability to analyze and interpret environmental data.
197	Environmental Microbiology and Laboratory (Applied Biotechnology)	2	6	Enhances the ability to analyze the role of microorganisms in the environment using biotechnological methods.
198	Environmental Processes Laboratory (Theory, Laboratory and Field)	2	6	Develops the ability to study and analyze environmental processes in laboratory and field conditions.
199	Modern Instrumental Analysis	2	6	Improves the ability to apply and utilize modern instrumental analysis methods.
200	Solid Waste Management	2	6	Develops the ability to create effective management and recycling strategies for solid waste.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
201	Environmental Impact Assessment	3	6	Develops the ability to study environmental impact assessment methods and apply them in practical situations.
202	Environmental Management	3	6	Enhances the capability to develop and implement environmental management strategies and policies.
203	Air Quality Models	3	6	Develops the ability to study air quality modeling and analysis methods and apply them in practical situations.
205	Master's Thesis	4	30	Lecture, laboratory, workshop, field, project, independent research
206	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	6	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments <p>Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources</p>
207	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
208	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
209	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
210	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science.</p> <p>Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python.</p> <p>Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues.</p> <p>Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.</p>
211	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
212	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
213	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
214	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
215	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
216	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
217	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
218	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
219	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
220	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool</p> <p>Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting</p> <p>Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome</p> <p>Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts</p> <p>Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context</p> <p>Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner</p> <p>Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study</p> <p>Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.</p>
221	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
222	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
223	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <p>a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems</p> <p>b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management</p> <p>c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services · Understand environmental policy instruments · Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations · Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work · Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies · Understand the economics of pollution · Understand and assess economics of climate change · Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy · Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment · Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management · Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
224	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
225	Innovation in Engineering		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering.</p> <p>Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	(Polytechnical Foundation)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
226	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
227	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
228	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
229	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
230	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste.</p> <p>Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved.</p> <p>Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions.</p> <p>Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved.</p> <p>Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system.</p> <p>Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies.</p> <p>Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems</p> <p>Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region</p>
231	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
232	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
233	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
234	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
235	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <p>Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles</p> <p>Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support</p> <p>Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches</p> <p>Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories</p> <p>Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation</p> <p>Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures</p> <p>Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues</p> <p>Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
236	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
237	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		10	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
238	Life Cycle Assessment of		10	Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	Products and Systems			<p>and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
239	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
240	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
241	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services · Understand environmental policy instruments · Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations · Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work · Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies · Understand the economics of pollution · Understand and assess economics of climate change · Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy · Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment · Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management · Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
242	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
243	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
244	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
245	Environmental Modelling		10	This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
246	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	To provide the participants knowledge of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
247	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
248	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
249	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
250	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
251	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
252	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
253	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
254	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
255	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science.</p> <p>Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python.</p> <p>Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues.</p> <p>Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.</p>
256	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
257	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
258	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
259	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
260	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
261	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
262	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
263	Environmental Modelling		10	This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
264	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
265	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
266	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
267	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
268	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <p>a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems</p> <p>b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management</p> <p>c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services · Understand environmental policy instruments · Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations · Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work · Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies · Understand the economics of pollution · Understand and assess economics of climate change · Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy · Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment · Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management · Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
269	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
270	Innovation in Engineering		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering.</p> <p>Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	(Polytechnical Foundation)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
271	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
272	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
273	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
274	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
275	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digester and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
276	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
277	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
278	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
279	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
280	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <p>Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles</p> <p>Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support</p> <p>Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches</p> <p>Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories</p> <p>Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation</p> <p>Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures</p> <p>Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues</p> <p>Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
281	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
282	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
283	Life Cycle Assessment of		10	Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	Products and Systems			<p>and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
284	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
285	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
286	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services · Understand environmental policy instruments · Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations · Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work · Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies · Understand the economics of pollution · Understand and assess economics of climate change · Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy · Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment · Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management · Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
287	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
288	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
289	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
290	Environmental Modelling		10	This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
291	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	To provide the participants knowledge of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
292	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
293	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digester and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
294	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
295	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
296	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
297	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
298	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
299	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
300	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science.</p> <p>Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python.</p> <p>Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues.</p> <p>Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.</p>
301	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
302	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
303	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
304	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
305	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
306	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
307	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
308	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
309	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
310	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool</p> <p>Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting</p> <p>Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome</p> <p>Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts</p> <p>Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context</p> <p>Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner</p> <p>Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study</p> <p>Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.</p>
311	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
312	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
313	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <p>a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems</p> <p>b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management</p> <p>c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services · Understand environmental policy instruments · Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations · Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work · Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies · Understand the economics of pollution · Understand and assess economics of climate change · Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy · Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment · Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management · Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
314	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
315	Innovation in Engineering		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering.</p> <p>Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	(Polytechnical Foundation)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
316	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
317	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
318	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
319	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
320	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digester and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
321	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
322	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
323	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	<p>This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
324	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
325	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <p>Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles</p> <p>Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support</p> <p>Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches</p> <p>Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories</p> <p>Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation</p> <p>Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures</p> <p>Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues</p> <p>Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
326	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
327	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
328	Life Cycle Assessment of		10	Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	Products and Systems			<p>and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
329	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
330	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
331	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services · Understand environmental policy instruments · Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations · Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work · Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies · Understand the economics of pollution · Understand and assess economics of climate change · Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy · Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment · Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management · Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
332	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
333	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
334	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
335	Environmental Modelling		10	This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
336	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	To provide the participants knowledge of * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
337	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
338	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
339	Climate change - physics and observations		5	<p>To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
340	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
341	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating 'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
342	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
343	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
344	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
345	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science.</p> <p>Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python.</p> <p>Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues.</p> <p>Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.</p>
346	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
347	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	<p>This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
348	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.
349	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	General objective: To give students a general understanding of: a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services Understand environmental policy instruments Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies Understand the economics of pollution Understand and assess economics of climate change Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality
350	Quantitative Sustainability (Polytechnical Foundation)	1	5	This course provides the understanding and quantitative tools needed by engineers and scientists to create engineering solutions for a sustainable society within their own educational disciplines. The students learn about terms, definition, and units related to sustainability, the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability and the importance of geographical and temporal scale when considering engineering solutions. Focus will be placed on understanding sustainability and developing sustainable solutions from an industrial perspective. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: · Describe and critically reflect on the environmental, social, and economic considerations and challenges to creating

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>'sustainable engineering solutions' in practice across multiple geographical and temporal scales</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Critically evaluate sustainability in current practice across the three Sustainability Pillars; environment, society and economy · Analyze and quantify, from a life cycle perspective, the sustainability of a chosen product or service through a group assignment using the sustainability tools introduced during the course · Apply current state-of-the-art tools to quantify sustainability whilst considering the complex interlinkage of sustainability challenges currently faced within climate change and the sources impacting climate change, effects on human health and the environment, effects on biodiversity of ecosystems, and the scarcity of certain resources · Explain the uncertainties associated with sustainability assessments · Explain the importance of a systemic perspective when assessing the sustainability of all technology and practices considering the current and future technological, environmental, social, and economic landscape · Describe main components of an absolute environmental sustainability assessment · Critically engage with the principles of life cycle assessment (LCA) in practice by evaluating the outputs of several life cycle assessments · Describe the principle of Circular Economy and how that affects societal flows of resources
351	Innovation in Engineering (Polytechnical Foundation)		5	<p>The course aims to equip students with key competencies regarding innovation in engineering. Students will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand how to apply an innovation process to a real-life engineering challenge - Experience the big picture of the innovation landscape by learning to navigate their role in it - Contribute to innovation initiatives in team context - Collaborate in facilitated innovation methods - Acquire the signature DTU mindset and approach to innovation - Be able to communicate to relevant stakeholders - Acquire a toolkit of methods to structure innovation - Create new solution-oriented ideas and mature these to a final concept proposal
352	Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		5	<p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe several basic ethical theories and applied environmental ethical principles Discuss different approaches to environmental management, regulation and decision support Differentiate between the ethical and environmental ethical theories and management approaches Reflect on environmental issues from the perspective of different ethical theories Demonstrate how regulation can be designed so that both helps protect the environment as well as sparks innovation Debate the social and ethical implications of different regulatory measures Analyse uncertainties and risks in complex environmental issues Formulate a regulation and policy strategy for coping with the environmental issues Write a political brief on an environmental issue with relevant facts, analysis of problems and solutions and policy recommendations
353	Environmental Modelling		10	<p>This course aims to provide students the basic knowledge to work with mathematical models and apply them to environmental problems, providing the theoretical basis for subsequent applications in specialization courses. The course has four major elements: i) simple mass balances using big environmental datasets, ii) deterministic modelling using ordinary differential equations, iii) deterministic modelling using partial differential equations and iv) model optimisation, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis. The course builds on a series of examples drawn from the field of environmental engineering and</p>

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				<p>employs programming tools and languages (e.g., COMSOL Multiphysics, Python) to illustrate the general modelling principles. The course will teach students how to integrate observed data with models and apply them to describe environmental problems and evaluate model results</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply fundamental physical, chemical and biological knowledge to mathematically describe an environmental problem Identify and describe the governing processes, boundary and initial conditions that are relevant to environmental problems. Formulate mass balances, ordinary and partial differential equations based on process understanding Employ numerical and analytical techniques, using programming and modelling tools to simulate environmental systems Evaluate model results and their uncertainty Understand model behaviour through sensitivity analysis Apply parameter estimation by employing measured data Communicate modelling results in a clear, concise, and convincing manner
354	Introduction to Machine Learning and Data Mining		5	<p>To provide the participants knowledge of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * fundamental and widely applied methods for data modeling and machine learning, * a framework for data modeling, * Matlab, R or Python as a tool for data analysis (the participant can freely choose between these programming languages). <p>The course enables the participants to apply machine learning for modeling of real world data.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the major steps involved in data modeling from preparing the data, modeling the data to evaluating and disseminating the results. Discuss key machine learning concepts such as feature extraction, cross-validation, generalization and over-fitting, prediction and curse of dimensionality. Sketch how the data modeling methods work and describe their assumptions and limitations. Match practical problems to standard data modeling problems such as regression, classification, density estimation, clustering and association mining. Apply the data modeling framework to a broad range of application domains in medical engineering, bio-informatics, chemistry, electrical engineering and computer science. Compute the results of the data modeling framework by use of Matlab, R or Python. Use visualization techniques and statistics to evaluate model performance, identify patterns and data issues. Combine and modify data modeling tools in order to analyze a data set of their own and disseminate the results of the analysis.
355	Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Systems		10	<p>Participants will acquire a thorough understanding of Life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method and tool for analysing the environmental impacts of products and technical systems. They will obtain the concrete skills and master the methodologies and tools to perform an LCA and to critically analyse LCA results produced by others. They will know the most frequent uses of LCA in industry and government and be able to identify LCA main strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate a fundamental understanding of life cycle thinking in the analysis and management of technological systems Plan and execute a life cycle assessment of a product or a technological system in co-operation with a company or other type of organisation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define a relevant functional unit for a product or a system Ensure equivalency of products or systems through system expansion or allocation

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				Model a carbon footprint using a spreadsheet and model an inventory using a dedicated LCA tool Perform a life cycle impact assessment including midpoint and damage characterisation, normalisation and possibly weighting Perform sensitivity analysis and interpret the results of the LCA in accordance with the outcome Identify the life cycle stages, processes and inventory flows that affect most category specific environmental impacts Interpret the LCA results of an individual product in a sustainable consumption and absolute sustainability context Report in accordance with the capabilities of the company partner Interpret and use life cycle assessments performed by others and perform a critical review of an LCA study Explain the most important industrial and regulatory applications of LCA and describe the tools of the Integrated Product Policy, IPP.
356	Solid Waste Technology and Management		10	This course provides an overview of the problems related to solid waste and insight into important technologies and management issues. Specific skills are developed regarding waste management planning, source separation, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion and landfilling. Principles and tools for environmental assessment of waste management systems are also provided. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: Explain and use important terms related to waste generation: waste source, waste types, waste fractions, source separation, unit generation rates. Describe methods for characterization of waste. Design and explain systems for waste collection, transport, and transfer of waste. Describe waste treatment technologies, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe technologies for recycling of important waste fractions. Describe technologies for landfilling of waste, and explain important physical, chemical, and biological processes involved. Describe amounts and composition of waste in Denmark, and explain how these affect the design of the waste management system. Describe important aspects related to consumption of resources as well as emissions from waste collection, treatment, recycling, and landfilling of waste, and identify potential environmental impacts from the relevant technologies. Identify critical aspects related to environmental assessment of waste management systems Prepare and argue a plan for management of the waste in a specific region
357	Climate change - physics and observations		5	To understand where our knowledge of Earth's climate comes from. To be able to analyse climate data and put it into the context of Earth's climate system. A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to: analyze relevant climate data critically appraise scientific literature compare climate forcing and feedback evaluate trends in global temperature data explain how global climate models work explain how temperature is measured and how temperature measurements are used in global analysis discuss how observations are used in models to compute atmospheric reanalysis. appraise sea surface temperature changes and consequences for the climate system appraise sea level changes and their relation to the melting of glaciers and heating of the oceans appraise the role of sea ice for the radiation balance and its effect on the climate system explain different greenhouse gas emission scenarios and their effect on future climate.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
358	Environmental and Resource Economics		5	<p>General objective: To give students a general understanding of:</p> <p>a) How economic analysis can be used in addressing sustainability and environmental problems</p> <p>b) How economic tools can be used in a sustainable optimum resource management</p> <p>c) How the three pillars of sustainability (economy, environment, society) are related</p> <p>A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:</p> <p>Discuss how we can conceptualize an optimal use of environmental goods and services</p> <p>Understand environmental policy instruments</p> <p>Conduct economic analysis to find optimum non-renewable resource allocation over generations</p> <p>Explain and debate how environmental valuation methods work</p> <p>Understand and qualify the role of discount rate in conducting cost-benefit analysis of environmental policies</p> <p>Understand the economics of pollution</p> <p>Understand and assess economics of climate change</p> <p>Understand and discuss the differences in private and social costs of wind energy</p> <p>Understand and discuss the links between population growth, food production and the environment</p> <p>Use economic analysis and estimate optimum renewable resource management</p> <p>Understand and relate to economics of water use and water quality</p>
359	Statistics	1	3	<p>Overview of probability theory and statistics; Event (a subset of the sample space); Entropy of the set of events; Markov chain; Empirical distribution; Random variable; Basic distributions of the one-dimensional random variables; Multivariate normal distribution; Normal distribution – characterization, properties; Probability distributions of the meteorological and hydrological processes; Regression analysis; Linear and nonlinear regression; Correlation and dependence; Statistical population; Sample (a subset of a population); Confidence interval (CI); Estimation Theory (for topics involving inferences about probability distributions); Flow sequences; Thomas-Fiering model; t-distribution; Chi-square test; A reliable method of calculating the maximum precipitation; Statistical hypotheses – testing; Parametric and non-parametric models; Comparison with a data; Statistics in forecasting (meteorology and hydrology); Probable maximum and minimum flow.</p>
360	Project Management	1	3	<p>Definition of a project; project characteristics; classification of projects; meaning and scope of projects and project management; project life cycles; project processes, the roles of the project manager, scope management, building a work break structure, stakeholders management; stakeholders roles; responsibility matrix; time planning – the process; activity identification; identify activity relationships; estimating; creating a network; activity –on –arrow diagram and critical path analysis; activity-on-node diagrams; estimating project time; effective time management; scheduling - Gantt charts; assign and level resources; Program Evaluation Review Techniques (PERT); cost planning process; cost –estimating techniques; cost build-up; cost management –budgets; risk management; identify the risk; risk quantification techniques; how to reduce risk; organising for project management; the role of teams; functional organization; the pure project organisation; matrix organizational form; structure selection.</p>
361	Interactive Decision Making	1	2	<p>The course provides students with knowledge on development and application of statistical- strategic approach to decision making and conflict resolution. The students will become familiar with modelling methods used to analyze and solve interactive decision making problems common in contemporary engineering projects such as:</p> <p>contract negotiations, bid competition process, choosing optimal actions to maximize the payoffs in uncertain environments, and design of information-value based monitoring systems.</p> <p>The students will be working with modern methodologies and computer tools for these problems.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
362	Fluid Mechanics	1	5	Behaviour, properties and definition of a fluid. Fluid statics, pressure, hydrostatics on flat and curved surfaces, buoyancy. Kinematics of fluid, definition of velocity, acceleration, material derivative, streamlines, streaklines and pathlines. Fluid flow concepts. Finite control volume analysis with continuity, momentum, and energy equations. Navier–Stokes equations. Laminar and turbulent flow. Reynolds equations. Bernoulli and Euler equation. Viscous flows. Pipe flow, energy losses. Open channel flow and its classifications. Uniform flow, rapidly varied flow, gradually varied flow, unsteady flow. Hydraulic structures: weirs, flumes, culverts. Velocity and flow measurement. Principles of groundwater flow. Water quality modelling.
363	Environmental Chemistry	1	2	Microorganisms in production and decomposition of organic matter and in nutrient cycling in aquatic and soil ecosystems. Abiotic factors limiting or enhancing the biological processes. Quality analyses of different ecosystems using the physical, chemical and microbiological parameters. Natural and anthropogenic contaminations. Understanding of the anthropogenic impact on ecosystems. Importance of ecosystems quality in the public health aspects. Ecosystems protection. The practical knowledge about field and experimental ecology. The ecosystems quality in field scale. The relationships between physical, chemical and biological parameters in aquatic and soil ecosystems. The key parameters for ecosystem functioning. The role of anthropogenic impact on ecosystems.
364	Environmental Microbiology	1	2	Microorganisms in production and decomposition of organic matter and in nutrient cycling in aquatic and soil ecosystems. Abiotic factors limiting or enhancing the biological processes. Quality analyses of different ecosystems using the physical, chemical and microbiological parameters. Natural and anthropogenic contaminations. Understanding of the anthropogenic impact on ecosystems. Importance of ecosystems quality in the public health aspects. Ecosystems protection. The practical knowledge about field and experimental ecology. The ecosystems quality in field scale. The relationships between physical, chemical and biological parameters in aquatic and soil ecosystems. The key parameters for ecosystem functioning. The role of anthropogenic impact on ecosystems.
365	Water Supply and Wastewater Disposal	1	5	Water resources; types of water intakes; elements of water supply system; system configurations; water demand estimates; transportation and distribution system design and analysis; distribution reservoirs and service storage – types, construction, design; pumps and pumping stations; pump characteristics; wastewater types and quantities; open channel flow sewer system; pressure sewer system; system layout; average rates of flow; variability in sanitary sewage flows; infiltration and exfiltration; design of open channel sanitary sewers; wastewater pumping stations and pressure pipes; pipes materials; manholes; siphones; basics on non-digging methods of sewer renovation; design of stormwater drainage systems; hydrologic considerations; runoff estimation and design flow; system layout; hydraulic design of urban storm drainage systems; stormwater inlets; possibilities of flow reduction by retention and infiltration of stormwater.
366	Water Reuse	1	2	Water reuse – a strategy for water conservation in the framework of water resources management. Quality of reclaimed water (treated wastewater) versus potential health and environmental risks associated with water reuse applications. Conditions affecting the development of water reuse applications: irrigation (agriculture and landscape), non-potable urban applications, industry, groundwater recharge, environmental and recreational applications. Regulations on water reuse. Planning, design and monitoring of reuse of reclaimed water. Economic assessment of water reuse projects. Communication and public acceptance of water reuse.
367	Groundwater and Soil Protection	1	4	Lecture: Basic hydrogeological properties of soils and rocks (porosity, storage, permeability, capillarity, soil water retention curve); occurrence of groundwater; groundwater dynamics (flow in saturated and unsaturated zone, interaction with atmosphere and surface water); chemistry of groundwater; major types of contaminants and their properties; transport of dissolved substances (diffusion, advection, dispersion, adsorption); reactive transport; non-aqueous phase liquid contaminants (multiphase flow); overview of soil protection and remediation techniques for hydrocarbons contamination.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
368	Environmental Impact Assessment	2	2	Environmental management - origins of the Environmental Impact Assessment. Scope and purpose of the Council Directive 85/337/EEC of 27 June 1985 on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (EIA Directive). The transposition of a EIA Directive into domestic law. Implementation of the EIA procedure into the Polish legal system of environmental protection (objective and stages, examples). The history of performance evaluations and legal regulation in this area. Legal determinants of performance of the EIA. Access to information concerning the environment and public participation in EIA procedure. Duties of administrative authorities in the scope of availability of the information about how to proceed in terms of the EIA issue. Background and current status of the ISO 14000 series, the requirements of ISO 14001. A detailed discussion of the procedures for implementing the EIA and the Environmental Review - stages, examples.
369	Engineering Surveying and GIS Applications	2	3	Basic concepts of surveying: principles, basic measurements, control networks, locating position. Basic survey measurement: 1) distance measurements - measuring principles, meteorological correction, geometrical reduction, errors, development in EDM (electromagnetic distance measurement), 2) levelling - curvature and refraction, principle of levelling, source of error and closure tolerances, levelling applications, types of levelling (reciprocal, precise, digital, trigonometrical, heighting with GPS), 3) angle and direction measurement - location of points, bearings, azimuths, theodolite and transit, electronic digital theodolites, setting up the theodolite, 4) combined distance and angular measurement systems - total station systems, general function of total station systems, applications of total station systems. Survey measurements and adjustment. Types of surveys: control and topographic surveying, route surveying, construction surveying. Field and office work: planning and design of the survey, remarks, data recording, data collectors, computation and checking. Conventional control surveys: plane rectangular coordinates, traversing, triangulation, networks. Modern surveying: global positioning system, photogrammetric surveying and mapping (sensors and platforms, cameras, scanners and linear sensors, platforms, orthophotography, digital elevation model, geographic information systems). Mapping: digital mapping and spatial information systems. GIS applications.
370	Wastewater Engineering	2	5	Wastewater sources and flows. Wastewater characterization based on physical and biodegradation criteria. Preliminary treatment unit operations (screens, grit chambers, primary clarifiers). Biological processes (suspended growth vs. attached growth) for wastewater treatment. Principles of biological nutrient removal (nitrification, denitrification, enhanced biological phosphorus removal). Implementation of biological nutrient removal processes in mainstream and sidestream treatment lines. Secondary clarifiers. Advanced treatment processes (tertiary treatment, physical-chemical treatment). Sludge handling processes (thickening, anaerobic vs. aerobic digestion, dewatering). Mathematical models of wastewater treatment processes.
371	Water Treatment	2	4	Water sources - classification of pollutants. Water components and quality standards. Drinking water regulations and recommendations (WHO, Poland, EU). Health effects. Water treatment operations and processes (physical, chemical and biological). General rules of the Water Treatment Plant design. Types of devices, principles of operations, design directions. Disinfection - kinetics and practice. Drinking water tanks. Calculations: reagent storages, hydraulic and mechanical mixers, reaction tanks, settling tanks, rapid filters, drinking water tanks, distribution pipes. Design of level map and level scheme. Selection and calculations of water treatment installations.
372	Waste Management	2	4	Waste sources, definitions and classifications, Polish and European Union law regulations; Waste management concepts – waste hierarchy, extended producer responsibility (EPR), PPP –polluter pays principle; waste; waste handling and transport, technologies and integrated waste management- landfill and landfill leachate, design and monitoring, incineration, recycling (glass, paper ,plastic, metals), source separation, waste to energy; Sustainability –biological reprocessing, energy recovery (pyrolysis, plasma, RDF, waste to fuel- Polymer Energy), biogas production; Sewage sludge as waste, e-waste, medical waste, hazardous waste management, and bulky waste handling , LCA in waste management

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
373	Urban Hydrology	2	5	The hydrological cycle in natural and modified environment. Urban catchment and its specificity. Impact of urbanization on the hydrology cycle and quantity of runoff. Effect of "urban heat island". Role of urban hydrology in designing, verifying and exploitation of engineering structures in urban terrain. Definition of "rainfall-runoff" model. Classifications of hydrological models. Catchment characteristics and their influence on runoff formation. Rainfall as the basic factor determining runoff. Design rainfall. Statistical analysis of rainfall data for local rainfall formulas estimation. Time of concentration. Engineering methods of runoff estimation. Soil Conservation Service Method for determining discharge and volume of runoff. Integrated models (e.g. HEC-HMS) as engineering tools in hydrological analysis of catchment.
374	Water Resource Management	2	4	Overview of Water: A Physical Perspective; The Hydrologic Cycle - Components, Processes, Human Modification; Global Variation of Precipitation and Evaporation; Factors of the Annual Global Water Budget; Surface Water Hydrology; Water Resource Problems – Global, Poland; Flood, Drought; Water Usage and Supply; Water Demands (Agriculture, Industry, Communal, Recreational); Water Quality - The Complexity of Water Pollution; Major Water Pollutants - Point and Non-Point; Water Supply Systems/Water Treatment; Reservoirs/River Management; Water Uses - Power, Flood Control, Recreation, Water Supply, Navigation; Multiple Use Reservoirs, Multiple Conflicts; Single Purpose Reservoirs; Floods Classification, Reasons and Results; Floods in Polish Water Act and European Water Directive; Modelling of Floods; Numerical Simulations and Mapping (GIS); Flood Risk Zones Determination; Flood Risk Management; The Future of Water Resources Management; Global Water Management Issues; Water Demand in Poland; Climate Change - Global Warming; River Restoration; Cross-vanes; Water Management in Winter Season; Ice Formation Impact on Water Management; Sediment Transport; Erosion and Reservoir Sedimentation;
375	Numerical Modeling of Hydrosystems	3	4	Lecture: Role of computer tools in water resources management; mathematical models of flow and contaminant transport in hydrosystems, development of numerical model: preprocessing, simulation and postprocessing; verification, validation and calibration of the model, sensitivity analysis; numerical solution of partial differential equations: spatial discretization methods (finite difference, finite element, finite volume), time discretization methods (explicit and implicit schemes), solution of systems of linear and nonlinear algebraic equations; stability and accuracy of numerical methods, boundary conditions; solution strategies for coupled problems. Examples: one-dimensional advection-diffusion equation; Saint-Venant equations; two-dimensional shallow water flow equations; two-dimensional groundwater flow equations.
376	Modeling Methodologies for the Environment	3	4	Control volumes and mass balances. Completely vs. incompletely mixed systems. Advective/dispersive transport. Kinematic mixing. Chemical equilibria and mass conservation. Chemical kinetics and partitioning. Air-water gas exchange. Sedimentation. Biodegradation and microbial growth kinetics. Dissolved oxygen behaviour. Eutrophication and heat budgets. Transport and fate in rivers, lakes and estuaries. Water quality models (WASP, QUAL2K, Aquatox, EPD-RIV1, IWA RWQM No. 1).
377	Reliability Safety and Risk of Engineering Systems		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MSc Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
378	Sustainable Development and Management (HES)		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf

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				Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
379	Computational Methods in Environmental Engineering		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
380	Environmental Fluid Mechanics		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
381	Surface Water Protection		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
382	Principles of Soil Diagnostic Techniques		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
383	Acquisition and Management of Environmental Data		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
384	Monitoring of Environment		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
385	Applied Climatology		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
386	Geostatistics	2	3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
387	Air Pollution Control		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
388	Biological Techniques for Environmental Monitoring		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
389	Environmental Chemistry II		6	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
390	Scientific Programming and Data Analysis		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
391	Spatial Data Analysis		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
392	Groundwater Protection		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
393	Municipal Solid Waste Treatment Technology		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf</p>

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				Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
394	Irrigation and Drainage		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
395	Environmental Physics	3	3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
396	Global Climate Change		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
397	Pro-ecological Technologies		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
398	Introduction to Remote Sensing of Environment		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
400	Land Reclamation and Development	4	3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/
401	Environmental Risk Assessment		3	For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
402	Alternative Energy Sources		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
403	Energy Systems Modelling and Optimization		3	<p>For subject curriculum see link below. Link to study plan: https://is.pw.edu.pl/images/kandydaci/informator_PL_2019_ENG_v_04.pdf https://is.pw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MSc_EPE_2024_accepted_03_2024.pdf Link to MsC Curricula: https://is.pw.edu.pl/en/curriculum-of-the-graduate-msc-level-study-in-environment-protection-engineering/</p>
405	Energy And Environment	1	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify, analyze and interpret the main relationships between the energy sector and the environment; - Identify different types of energy resources, evaluate their advantages, disadvantages and their environmental impacts; - Demonstrate the use of thermodynamic concepts, namely through the understanding of the role of energy conservation and entropy production in the analysis and resolution of environmental issues; - Carry out energy analysis applied to energy conversion equipment and systems.
406	Environmental Planning		6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand the importance of the territory dimension for environmental problems comprehension, minimization and prevention – be able to do spatial analyses and identification of potentialities and vulnerabilities; - Understand technical, procedural and political specificities of planning process; - To know, how to actively participate in the planning processes, through critical analyses of territorial information and associated decision making contexts, and contribute to the adoption of sustainable development strategies.
407	Industrial Ecology		6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyse systems of production of goods and services as an integral part of the environmental systems - Understand the relationship between production, consumption, sustainability and industrial ecology - Understand and apply industrial ecology quantitative analytical methods
408	Treatment Systems Engineering I		6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and characterize the relevant properties for the treatment process; - Define a technology and to design the suitable equipment for the control of pollutant emission for the environment in order to comply with appropriate standards; - Establish the design and operational conditions of the equipment in a given treatment process; - Analyze the performance of the equipment.
409	Environmental Management Systems	2	6	<p>Understanding of the concepts related to environmental management systems, standards and requirements. Awareness of the various voluntary instruments designed for environmental and social promotion of an organization and its products. Understanding of similarities between quality, environmental and health and safety management systems. Ability for the designing of EMS elements – policies, procedures and work instructions, record forms, action plans – and designing indicators for environmental performance. Ability to carry out small environmental audits and designing audit plans and reports. Understanding of the concepts of life cycle analysis and related methodology.</p>
410	Treatment Systems Engineering II		6	<p>Design, dimension and operate treatment systems</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
411	Environmental Infrastructures I		6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate processes for the treatment of pollutants in environmental infrastructures in order to comply with legal regulations, in the search for a sustainable use of natural and technological resources; - To monitor, analyze, design and operate environmental infrastructures applied to waste management, including treatment of gaseous effluents, energy conversion and environmental life cycle assessment.
412	Urban Metabolism		6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand the functioning of cities as a living organism, complex and in close interaction and dependence on the surrounding environment, particularly in terms of the flows of materials, energy, infrastructure, emissions and waste; - Develop analysis of inflows and outflows, and analysis of quality, through the application of dedicated tools; - Evaluate the efficiency and performance of cities and help to identify opportunities to promote efficiency, improvement and transformation of urban areas, applying the adequate technologies/infrastructures.
413	Environmental Impact Assessment	3	6	To promote skills that allow the understanding and elaboration of environmental impact studies under environmental impact assessment procedures associated to large Project development proposals. To understand, evaluate and simulate the use of available methods of environmental impact assessment. To understand and evaluate concepts and tools for strategic environmental assessment. To propose guidelines for strategic environmental assessment for particular case-studies.
414	Environmental Infrastructures II		6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To integrate in environmental infrastructures processes and technologies concerning pollution control and environmental systems sustainable usage - To analyze, to operate, to monitories and to manage different environmental infrastructures such as water treatment and supply, sewage collection and wastewater treatment - To consider blue and green infrastructures as pollution control mechanisms
415	Aquifer and Soil Rehabilitation	1	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ability to distinguish between contamination and soil degradation and recognise how both can affect soil functions, in perspective with the Sustainable Development Goals. - Ability to characterise the dispersion of an underground contamination. - Select the most appropriate rehabilitation technologies. - Determine the most relevant design parameters. - Predict and project monitoring technology. - Develop a Corrective Action Plan.
416	Environmental Engineering Laboratories I		6	Acquisition of competences in experimentation and scientific research in the treatment of liquid effluents, gases e solid wastes
417	Environmental Acoustics	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indispensable technical knowledge in Acoustics in order to understand and correctly apply Portuguese regulations in the area of Environmental Acoustics; - Personal and professional skills, so that they can be efficient in the resolution of problem and basic experimentation in this area; - the necessary skills to conceive and design in this area.
418	Environmental Engineering Laboratories II		4.5	Knowledge of environmental quality monitoring methodologies and technologies for treatment of liquid, gaseous and solid (residues and contaminated soils) steams, based on continuous semi-pilot scale tests and modeling tools to predict the behavior of the studied systems.
419	Environmental Law and Economics		3	Now the fundamentals of law and economics, incorporate legal and economics components in decision-making processes and interact effectively with economists and jurists to solve complex environmental engineering problems.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
421	Environmental Management		6	(Webpage information: "Available soon")
422	Waste Prevention and Recovery		6	Basic concepts on policies on waste management, the waste management systems and the basic technologies of recovery and eliminate the solid wastes, and to enable them to the resolution of problems related with waste management
423	Drinking Water and Wastewater Systems		6	(Webpage information: "Available soon")
424	Entrepreneurship	Between 1/2	3	To motivate and prepare students to undertake innovative projects in companies or develop technology-based startups.
425	Organisations Sustainability	2	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand major corporate sustainability strategies and their contribution to creating shareholder and stakeholder value. - Understand the concepts of ecoefficiency, natural capitalism and corporate sustainability. - Ability to promote the adoption of cleaner production strategies in companies. - Ability to identify and assess circular economy opportunities and develop circular business models - Master ecodesign, corporate social responsibility and business sustainability assessment and reporting tools. - Writing and oral communication skills and teamwork.
426	Sustainability Assessment of Policies, Plans and Projects	3	6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concepts, theories and trends related with Sustainability Assessment (SA). 2. Understanding of the main SA tools, at strategic (policies, plans and programmes) and project level, in particular Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), Health Impact Assessment (HIA), Social Impact Assessment (SIA), on different aspects: conceptual, ethical, legal, methodological, technical and scientific, administrative and decision-making. 3. Exploring the role of SA in the assessment of the UN Sustainable Development Goals implementation and follow-up at different scales. 4. Training of specific EIA and SEA techniques, with emphasis on those that invoke different domains of knowledge. 5. Understanding and resolution of practical EIA problems by simulating professional practice. 6. Ability to use EIA and SEA as decision support tools, respectively for projects and for policies, plans and programmes (PPP).
427	Project in Environmental Engineering		6	Conception of solutions for a real job, in one of the core areas of intervention of Environmental Engineering
428	Environmental, Biological and Chemical Engineering Processes	1	9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand the principles of biological processes in the treatment of waste and wastewater. - Understand the physical and chemical phenomena underlying reaction and separation processes used in waste and wastewater treatment. - Select, design and establish the operating conditions of the physical, physico-chemical and biological processes for treatment of wastewater, sludge, solid waste and polluted environment remediation. - Identify new greener advanced technologies and develop process intensification schemes towards sustainability. - Foster sludge, biosolid and waste by-products valorisation following a circular bioeconomy approach.
429	Environmental Modeling		6	(1) Understanding the importance and role of numerical and computational models in environmental studies; (2) Assimilation of fundamental knowledge in numerical / computational modeling (terminology, methods, etc.); (3) Development of process-

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				oriented models to study environmental phenomena; (4) Improvement of programming skills; (5) Acquisition of experience in building models using existing modeling tools.
430	Materials and Circular Economy		9	Identify, characterize and classify waste, components and materials; know the physical / chemical and biological principles associated with the collection, storage and selection of unit operations and transformation processes; prepare flowcharts of material and / or energy recycling processes; establish energy and mass balances; analyze in an integrated way the technological issues associated with the intensification of recycling and obtaining secondary raw materials.
431	Computer Aided Drawing		3	Learning of stroke and reading of plan projections and skills in free hand stroke. Representation by elevated projections applied on ground intervention works. Use of graphics systems in the design of ground works. Introduction to BIM and practice of BIM base tools.
432	Sanitary Engineering	2	6	Students learn concepts related to environmental sanitation, namely learn to design water supply infrastructures (including storage tanks and water distribution networks) and wastewater drainage systems. Basic concepts related to characterization of water quality. Simplified sanitation systems for developing countries.
433	Air Quality Engineering		6	i) Understand the chemistry of the atmosphere; ii) Identify the sources, properties and impacts of the main air pollutants; iii) Quantify atmospheric emissions from different sectors iv) Select and design the main equipment for gaseous and particulate pollutants control.
434	Environment and Territory Management and Policies		6	Concepts: environment, territory, resources, sustainability, systems, resilience, carrying capacity. Socio-ecological systems. Study cases: sustainability strategies, integration of environment into urban and rural planning. Mega trends and global challenges for environment and the territory I: climate issues. EU Climate Strategy. Climate Change policies in Portugal. II: biodiversity, ecosystem services, poverty and development. EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030. Biodiversity policy in Portugal. Innovative policy landmarks: EU Green Deal, strategies and the 8th environmental action framework. Agenda 2030 and Territorial Framework. Public participation and stakeholders' engagement. Territorial components I: biophysical. EU Soil Strategy. EU Forest Strategy. Portuguese related policies. Territorial components II: socioeconomic. Community Well-being, sense of place. Territorial value in socio-ecological systems. Territorial Governance: multi-level, multi-scale, multi-actor. Instruments. Participatory and Integrated approach in planning. Negotiation, conflict, and conciliation of interests.
435	Environmental Economics and Natural Resources	3	6	Understand the relationship between economic activity and the biophysical environment. Learn the fundamentals of macroeconomic theory: national accounts; theory of economic growth. Learn the fundamentals of microeconomic theory: consumer theory; producer theory; Market balance. Learn the economic theory approach to the environment, namely the economy of pollution and natural resources. Apply the economic approach to the environment to practical cases.
436	Water and Wastewater Treatment Plants		6	Addresses the concepts related to water treatment for human consumption and to domestic wastewater treatment and final discharge, with the fundamental objective of providing training in the design of water treatment plants (WTP) and wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), it also aims to develop the capacity for critical analysis and interpretation of the results obtained in WTP and WWTP, after implementation, namely in the operation phase.
437	Impact Assessment		6	Students are expected to know by end of the semester what are environmental impacts in a broad sense, as a key analytical dimension in environmental policy and management. In particular how environmental impacts are proactively analysed and assessed, in an integrated way, in support of sectorial decision-making, regarding the development of new projects as well as in the recuperation and rehabilitation of existing projects. Students are also expected to learn what is environmental impact assessment (EIA) as an environmental policy and management instrument, and explore its proactive role in support of

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				decision-making, acting at the levels of projects planning, conception, construction, operation and abandonment. By the end students should know how to identify environmental impacts, justify why its analysis is important, how to collect information, how to assign values in a multi-actor and multi-level context, how to assess impacts, how to mitigate negative and enhance positive impacts.
438	Environmental management	1	15	Environmental impact assessment and management systems Ecodesign of processes and products Clean technologies Application of GIS in territorial analysis2
439	Entrepreneurship and governance	2	12	Business creation and management Management skills Environmental governance, institutions and CSR Environmental law
440	Implementation and innovation	45689	36	Master's Thesis External internships Emerging challenges in water treatment Treatment of gaseous effluents Analysis and mining of environmental data Management of natural systems
441	Environmental Engineering	1	7.5	Air Quality Control Engineering
442	Sustainable Process Engineering	1	7.5	Advanced Techniques in Water Treatment and Purification
443	Specialisation	2	12	Waste and Soil Management and Treatment
444	Environmental Science and Technology	45689	35	Water pollution and treatment Measurement, analysis and control of atmospheric pollution Waste management and recovery Characterisation and treatment of contaminated soils Renewable energies Measurement, analysis and control of noise pollution Radiation in the environment Bioengineering applied to the environment
445	Environmental management	45689	16	Environmental impact assessment and prevention Environmental management systems Project management Environmental law

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
446	Tools for environmental research.	45689	16	Environmental monitoring and instrumentation Experimental data processing Transport of pollutants in the environment Remote sensing and environmental protection systems
448	Master's Thesis	3	30	Carry out, present and defend before a university examining board an original exercise carried out individually, consisting of a comprehensive study or project in the field of environmental engineering, consisting of a comprehensive study or project in the field of Environmental Engineering, in which the competences acquired in the course are synthesising the skills acquired in the course, adopting the advances and new developments in the field of environmental engineering and contributing novel ideas.
449	Theory and Methodology of Science with Applications (Natural and Technological Science)	1.2	7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Identify definitions and descriptions of concepts, theories and problem areas, as well as identify the correct applications of these concept and theories. · Account for concepts, theories and general problems areas, as well as apply concepts and theories to specific cases. · Critically discuss the definitions and applications of concepts and theories as they apply to specific cases of scientific research. These learning outcomes are examined via seminars, and in a written exam. After having completed the course, the student should also be able to (applies to students that do not take the master's programme medical engineering (TMLEM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Summarise and present research reports or scientific articles in a way that makes them accessible to a non-expert audience. · Account for standard structural and qualitative criteria for scientific writing and apply these to research reports or scientific articles. · Identify and critically discuss specific theoretical and methodological problems in research reports or scientific articles. These learning outcomes are examined in writing via a project part. Students from the master's programme medical engineering (TMLEM) should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Account for and apply the most common theories and methods of applied ethics and account for their relevance for medical technology. · Carry out independent moral reflections concerning practical problems in the ethics of medical technology.
450	Environmental Measuring and Monitoring		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formulate, realize and analyse site investigation programmes for hydrological, hydrogeo logical and environmental monitoring • Use field equipment and instruments (especially geophysical measurement techniques) for measurements of soil, water and environmental properties • Scientifically select investigation strategies, estimate data quality and analyse and evaluate measurement data using statistical and modelling technique
451	Environmental Dynamics/Physical Processes		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · understand the basic principles for modelling and have a grasp of the dynamic nature of environmental systems; · know what the general steps are when building mathematical models in environmental engineering; · understand stochastic nature /randomness in natural systems and familiarize with elementary tools that are used for quantifying uncertainty; · understand the basis of commercial modelling tools based on their documentation; · have at least rudimentary experience with process modelling in all major areas of environmental engineering and science, from eutrophication, estuary, surface-, and groundwater water quality assessment, to climate change and anthropogenic systems.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
452	Water and Wastewater Handling		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain water and material flow in society, need for sustainable development, recycling and reuse. - analyse problems connected to water scarcity, water quality and health, based on historical perspectives and trends. - describe requirements and formulate goals of water and wastewater handling, and distribution systems. - apply their knowledge in treatment methods to choose an appropriate technology for water and wastewater handling as a part of urban infrastructure. - implement their knowledge in hydraulics, chemistry, and/or microbiology in water and wastewater handling and distribution. - understand and discuss management of water and wastewater handling and distribution systems based on experiences and trends from urban areas in different countries.
453	Environmental Impact Assessment		7.5	<p>the key principles of the EIA process, the terminology and methods used in EIA, the role of EIA in relation to the planning and decision-making process, EIA trends and practices in an international perspective, the methodological issues related to the performance of EIA, quality requirements concerning the EIA process and the Environmental Impact Statement (EIS), interdisciplinarity in relation to the performance of EIA.</p> <p>After fulfilling the course the student should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · perform the screening and scoping of an EIA, based on existing requirements, evaluate the impacts and draw meaningful conclusions from the results of the EIA; · present an appropriate EIS considering the general criteria of consistency, transparency and systematicness; · perform a critical quality review of an EIA and EIS; · clarify the concept of EIA and its application in an international context to those involved in or affected by the EIA process; · structure the EIA working process considering the need for interdisciplinarity; · interpret an EIA, present its conclusions and translate its conclusions into actions.
454	Environmental Data		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe the way geographical information systems (GIS) are built up and operate. · Compare and evaluate data collection methods and input techniques. · Interpret remote sensing data and describe related physical phenomena. · Characterize different types of spatial data using visualization and statistics. · Choose and justify appropriate data processing and analysis approaches according to the characteristics of data and intended analysis outcome. · Build models comprising sequences of GIS operations, and perform and evaluate sensitivity analysis. · Interpret and relate the GIS analysis outcomes to source data quality, discuss errors and uncertainty and suggest ways of improving the result. · Design a GIS case study to solve a specific task. · Document and communicate the results of a GIS study.
455	Strategic Environmental Assessment		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the key principles of the SEA process; • the terminology and methods used in SEA; • the role of SEA in relation to the planning and decision-making process; • SEA trends and practices in an international perspective; • the methodological issues related to the performance of SEA; • interdisciplinarity in relation to the performance of SEA.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
456	Applied Hydrology		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The overall aim of the course is to give applied knowledge of rural and urban hydrological systems. After the course the student should be able to: • Describe the process in the hydrologic cycle in rural and urban environments and solve problems dealing with water balance, evapotranspiration, hydrographs, infiltration, frequency analysis, hydrologic risk analysis and more. • Describe lumped and distributed flow routing and solve problems with analytical and numerical methods. • Derive a conceptual model diagram representing a compartment model of an urban hydrological system. • Apply uncertainty based modelling techniques. • Describe the main features of important climate variability phenomena and discuss the current climate change scenarios for the next 100 years and the possible effects on hydrological systems in different regions of the world. • Describe the layout and perform a hydraulic design of municipal water supply and waste water systems.
457	Hydraulic Engineering		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After the course the student should be able to: • Perform hydraulic design of spillways, energy dissipators and selected hydraulic structures. • Perform computations for different types of unsteady flow, for example: water hammer, mass oscillations in pipe systems - surge chambers, surge waves in open channels. • Describe the erosion process and design erosion protection for a channel. • Analyse and design different flood mitigations measures.
458	Environmental Chemistry and Risk Assessment		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - estimate the geochemical fate of pollutants from basic information and by applying geochemical models - interpret analytical measurements of metals and organic pollutants in different media - interpret ecotoxicological information for contaminants - understand the principles of environmental risk assessment - apply today's risk assessment systems for contaminated soils and waters, although with a critical mind - understand the principles of some common and successful soil remediation methods - be familiar with some of the most important research issues in the field of environmental geochemistry.
459	Urban Infrastructure		7.5	<p>Be conversant in a range of theories addressing technology, society, and urban development; Recognise and appreciate the relational and spatial aspects of urban infrastructure development; and Have the ability to apply analytical skills to critically assess infrastructure networks in terms of sustainability, liveability, and resilience.</p>
460	Political Economy for Environmental Planners		7.5	<p>The aims of the course are to: familiarise students with the mechanisms of the global political economy system and its impacts on global, national, regional and local environmental and sustainability issues, provide an understanding of decision-making processes concerning sustainability issues at all levels, with an emphasis on environmental negotiation</p> <p>After the course the student will be able to: describe some common economic and political tools to solve environmental problems, understand the meaning of specific economic and political concepts and exemplify how these concepts have been applied to environmental issues, like e.g. prosperity, development, economic growth, burden sharing, efficiency, cost/benefit, present an analysis of the impact of political economy and social institutions on both local environments and the global environment, explain the special attributes of international environmental negotiation, particularly within the climate change debate,</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				write a literature review paper of scientific writing style comprising a critical assessment of the main ideas brought up in the literature
461	Sustainable Rural and Urban Development		7.5	<p>define key concepts such as Urbanization, Rural-Urban Linkages, Urban Sprawl, Urban-Rural Planning, Urban Agriculture, Food Security, Enabling Development Strategy and Sustainable City;</p> <p>Evaluate the rural-urban linkages in relation to socio-economic and environmental aspects of the sustainable development;</p> <p>Explain types of contemporary natural disasters related to climate change and discuss the different challenges that society faces before, during and after a disaster in urban and rural settings;</p> <p>Explain the complexity of a 'city' through analysing the interconnectedness of its socio-economic, environmental and political aspects and their influence on the urban living conditions.</p> <p>Analyse the impacts of poverty, gender aspect and citizens participation on sustainable development.</p> <p>Demonstrate through practical examples the urban/rural linkages and the diverse views of different actors from the built environment.</p>
462	Governance of Land and Water		7.5	<p>The course intends to deepen the students' knowledge and understanding in administration and control of soil and water resources in a global context that brings up cross cutting questions in control e.g. water as social power, human rights, gender, public/private debate and corruption.</p> <p>On completion of the course, students are expected to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand key concept and the frames for governance of land and water, such as water governance, property rights of land use and accessibility, customary law, resource ownership, the EU: Water Directive (WFD), Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), land reform, acquisition and compensation; water utilities management models. Be aware about that soil and water are not merely physical resources that can be exploited for human benefit using appropriate technologies, but there is need to conceptualize them as 'social' resources that need to be 'governed' & 'managed' sustainably in a fast changing world; - Identify main issues/factors, roles, and actors underlying the processes of land and water governance and understand the various operational challenges in different societal settings; - Understand the complexity of land and water governance processes through analysing its connection with political, socio-economic, environmental and ecological aspects and also recognising cross cutting issues such as poverty, gender, social inequality, culture and climate change; - Learn from concrete case studies & reflect upon sustainable approaches for land & water governance processes and goals. - Examine the land and water linkages and demonstrate through practical examples and project work opportunities and challenges in integrated land and water planning approach for creative and efficient uses of resources in relation to socio-economic and environmental aspects;
463	Natural Resources Management Tools		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - use Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for providing management relevant information about natural resources and environmental issues - review and give examples of other technologies and tools to increase accessibility and availability of environmental information, such as indicators, and - understand the significance of data and environmental information in planning, management and other decision-making and policy-making processes, for solving environmental problems and for sustainable use of natural resources.
464	Modelling of Water Systems	3	7.5	The course gives skills in the use of different engineering tools to facilitate an optimal design of water resources within a specific area. The work will be organised as projects and allow both detailed familiarity with a specific well designed task and general skill in communication to understand the usability of the obtained results.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				The course provides detailed familiarity to applied hydrological areas by using different quantitative tools to elucidate a number of different problems. Example of areas where the students should be able to work after fulfilling the course: Improving water management by using models for increased understanding Developing methods for monitoring and regulation of water system Evaluation of climate variability and climate change for various spatial and temporal scales Understanding the potential and the risk when using mathematical models.
465	Water Treatment Processes and Technology		7.5	Calculate how to construct and manage different processes involved in sustainable water and wastewater treatment. Apply chemical and biological knowledge that the processes are based on for use in case studies. Apply innovative technologies for new systems and improvement of old systems to get better function and fulfill the requirement of the society. Propose sludge treatment technologies. Use computer models for development and design of processes. Operate and optimize treatment plants.
466	Engineering Geology		7.5	The goal of the course is to increase the student's knowledge and understanding of geology, and apply this knowledge to engineering projects such as dams, landfills, rock quarries, roads, tunnels and slopes. Another goal is to increase the students' presentation skills, both oral and in written.
469	Applied Hydrogeology		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a conceptual hydrogeological model for a catchment area - Develop a numerical hydrogeological model for a catchment area - Perform flow and contaminant transport modelling of subsurface water for scenario analyses - Identify and quantify crucial parameters for contaminant transport with groundwater - Interpret field measurements and experimental data - Identify water quality problems and suggest appropriate treatment techniques for private water supplies/wells.
472	Resilience Thinking in Sustainable Planning		7	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. explain and use central concepts in resilience thinking 2. discuss how these central concepts relate to each other 3. reflect on and critically discuss resilience thinking in general and in relation to sustainable planning in particular 4. apply social-ecological resilience in a planning context 5. present written work in a scientifically sound way 6. work in a collaborative project setting
473	Life Cycle Assessment		7.5	Give an account of the aim applications of the LCA method. Explain the analytical phases and central concepts of the LCA method. Apply the analytical phases and central concepts of the LCA method on complex systems in technology and urban planning. Identify uncertainties in LCA method and data and evaluate how these influence the results. Report in writing the completed LCA study according to ISO's standard for LCA. Use LCA software. Give an account of the results orally of the completed LCA the study. Work in a collaborative project setting Report in writing and give an account of a critical review orally of an LCA report.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
474	Earth Systems Science	1	7.5	This foundational course focuses on the physical, chemical, and biological aspects of the global Earth system as they relate to sustainability challenges and intersections with society.
475	Social Sciences and Sustainability		7.5	<p>- The Social Sciences and Sustainability course discusses different theories of modern society and relates them to different approaches to sustainability and environmental problems.</p> <p>The course introduces social science approaches to sustainability in three parts: the origin, theory and practice for studying society in the close relation to nature.</p> <p>- The first section provides an introduction to the ideas that link and define the material conditions of our current societies, such as the use of natural resources, the evolution of property relations, and notions of progress.</p> <p>- The second part highlights different theories of society and relates them to environmental problems. This part of the course focuses on the tensions and synergies that arise in the interactions between different analytical concepts and categories such as individual/society, agency/structure and anthropocentrism/ecocentrism in relation to social change.</p> <p>- The third part provides basic understanding of current sustainability solutions. This is done from different perspectives, and practical examples are taken from various geographical origins including the Global South. The aim is to stimulate critical discussion and more in-depth reflection on existing solutions from diverse societal positions.</p>
476	Methodology for Sustainability Science		7.5	The aim of the Methodology for Sustainability Science course is to provide students with the fundamental methodological knowledge needed to understand and analyse sustainability challenges, as well as to contribute to knowledge on sustainability challenges.
477	Sustainability Science		7.5	<p>Upon the completion of the course, the students shall</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - demonstrate the ability to critically and systematically integrate knowledge and analyse, assess and handle complex phenomena, issues and situations, even with limited information, - demonstrate the ability to independently, creatively, and critically identify and formulate issues; to plan and, with adequate theories and methods, to carry out qualified tasks within given time frames, thereby contributing to the development of knowledge; and to evaluate this work, - demonstrate the ability, in both national and international contexts, to express, orally and in written, and to discuss with clarity, one's/their conclusions and the knowledge and arguments that underlie them in dialogue with different groups, and - demonstrate the skills required to participate in research, and to independently work in other qualified professions and activities.
478	Politics of Sustainability	2	7.5	<p>Knowledge and understanding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate a deepened understanding of different political processes and systems and their relevance for sustainability challenges • demonstrate understanding of how different political approaches and issues affect the ability, or lack of ability, to address sustainability challenges on different levels and scales <p>Competence and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop a deepened proficiency in academic writing and independent work including the ability to identify, critically analyse, and present sustainability challenges from different political perspectives • demonstrate the ability to assess political approaches to sustainability challenges as well as be able to present alternative approaches
479	Geographies of Sustainability		4.5	<p>Knowledge and understanding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate the ability to discuss and compare different geographical approaches and their relevance for analysing social

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>and environmental processes from a sustainability perspective</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate the ability to analyse how social and environmental change and natural resource use at the local scale is intertwined with economic, political and social conditions and processes at other scales • show a deepened understanding of the complex flows between urban and rural systems as well as the ability to analyse how and why these flows cause social differentiation and unequal distribution. <p>Competence and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • show an understanding for the spatial dimensions of social, economic, and environmental processes and their importance for natural resource use and sustainability challenges in different geographical contexts • demonstrate the ability to identify and discuss drivers of social and environmental processes in specific places and on various scales • demonstrate the ability to critically and independently identify problems and to formulate and present analysis and conclusions, orally as well as in writing • demonstrate the ability to constructively and respectfully engage in group work to successfully complete defined tasks.
480	Economy and Sustainability		7.5	<p>Knowledge and understanding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate knowledge of different economics paradigms and their relevance for sustainability, for example neoclassical economics, heterodox economics, environmental economics, capital theory, ecological economics, de-growth and post-growth • identify different claims and strategies for reconciling environmental and social concerns with the pursuit of economic growth and development, such as privatisation and marketisation, regulatory arrangements, and civil society initiatives • describe the implications of different economic paradigms for sustainability in different geographical and societal contexts, for instance circular economy, care economy, environmental and ecological economics, alternative currencies, green bonds, social and care economy, etc. <p>Competence and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate the ability to use economic tools and methods of various economic paradigms, for example circular economy, alternative currencies, green bonds, and social economy • constructively and respectfully engage in group work to successfully complete defined tasks • demonstrate skills in communication and the ability to present own conclusions orally and in writing.
481	Methods & Tools - from Knowledge to Action		7.5	<p>Knowledge and understanding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • discuss participatory methods for sustainability science, including their rationale and focus • develop a nuanced and critical understanding of participatory processes • identify and distinguish opportunities and purposes for inter- and transdisciplinary approaches in solutions-oriented research practice • express and defend which participatory approach and solutions options may be appropriate for a given solutions-oriented sustainability project. <p>Competence and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify and systematically develop a solution orientated project • demonstrate basic collaborative abilities in a participatory process • effectively and respectfully engage in small group settings to successfully complete defined tasks • systematically and respectfully engage with groups to devise interventions to a targeted sustainability challenge • effectively convey information and knowledge in written form in a manner that abides by academic standards • effectively discern and convey to an audience salient information and knowledge about a sustainability-relevant project.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
482	Geological and geotechnical site Characterisation (compulsory)	1.2	7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Describe the principles of geological genesis with a focus on the Swedish environment ○ Describe the particulars of various geo-materials ○ Describe the principles, benefits and limitations of different site investigation methods and laboratory test types ● Comprehension <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Distinguish between different features of basic geological processes ○ Understand the interdependence of engineering design and design of site characterisation, depending on the composition of the shallow subsurface. ● Application & Analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Design, execute and interpret of field and laboratory tests for a wide range of geo-materials (soft-soils to crystalline rock mass) ○ Evaluate several techniques used in the desk study phase (geological maps lineage etc). ● Synthesis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Integrate knowledge on large scale geological and hydrogeological processes, as well as future engineering needs, in the design of a site specific (hydro-)mechanical investigation for engineering properties. ○ Demonstrate insight into the possibilities and limitations of the geological and geotechnical site characterisation techniques, its role in society and the responsibility of the individual for how it is used, including both ethical and economic aspects and also environmental and safety considerations. ○ Demonstrate the ability in speech and writing clearly report and discuss his or her conclusions and the knowledge and arguments on which they are based in dialogue with different audiences within the field of geological, hydrogeological and geotechnical site characterisation techniques.
483	Infrastructure and urban systems (compulsory)		7.5	<p>Technical knowledge and reasoning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Differentiate between the phases of infrastructure and urban systems (e.g. planning, design and construction, operation and maintenance and decommissioning), and relate to their relation with the engineering role. - Demonstrate the relationship between infrastructure, urban system and connected concepts, in particular land, water, transport, energy and waste - Describe responsibilities and types of information needed to plan, design, operate, maintain and decommission infrastructure. - Select and collect relevant datasets related to infrastructure and urban systems. - Select appropriate strategies for infrastructure and urban systems to make the planning, design and construction, operation and maintenance and decommissioning more resilient, sustainable and efficient. - Quantify and argue for trade-offs, prioritize solutions, and evaluate how well they meet social, environmental and technical constraints. <p>Personal and professional skills and attributes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Search, read and use technical texts and scholarly articles in a systematic, conscious, critical and effective manner. - Apply systematic approaches by taking an holistic perspective. - Specify the multiple roles that actors have and what type of activities need to be conducted depending on the stakeholder type. <p>Interpersonal skills: teamwork and communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work in groups in a multi-cultural international setting.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Show the ability to reflect on equality, diversity and inclusion in group work. - Understand the type of information to communicate with different stakeholders.
484	Water systems and modelling (elective)		7.5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the hydraulic, hydrodynamic and pollutant transport processes in natural and constructed water systems 2. Distinguish between different models, considering both simple and advanced models 3. Be able to select and use an appropriate model for a given analysis to assess the quantity and quality of water, including model calibration, validation and uncertainty 4. Evaluate appropriate input values for the model parameters of the models considered, and to appreciate the sensitivity of the simulation results to the selected parameter values;
485	Contemporary topics in geomechanics (elective)		7.5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the principle of effective stresses in a partially saturated state (single Bishop effective stress measure versus two independent stress measures). 2. Recognise the effect of partial saturation on the shear strength and stiffness of soil. 3. Use conventional methods to estimate the slope stability with partial saturation effect. 4. Apply conventional method(s) to estimate 1D soil collapse/swelling due to variation in suction. 5. Describe the principles of various tunnelling methods in soils and rocks, and understand the main challenges and environmental effects. 6. Understand the principles and execution of various ground improvement techniques, in order to be able to select the most appropriate methods for a given problem from a technical and sustainability point of view. 7. Apply the best practice in designing ground improvement. 8. Understand the additional geotechnical challenges in the construction of new railways (high speed rail) and foundations for renewable energy, related to soil dynamics.
486	Sustainable transportation (elective)		7.5	<p>After completion of this course, the student should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain the unsustainable impacts of the transport sector - Analyse the potential and challenges of alternative fuels and innovative vehicle technology for the road transport sector - Analyse the potential and challenges of alternative transport modes - Analyse the potential and challenges of transport policy measures
487	Transportation engineering and traffic analysis (compulsory)		7.5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Know the role of transport engineering in society. 2. Understand the concepts of planning, design, implementation, operation and maintenance of transport infrastructure. 3. Use computational methods to solve practical problems in transportation engineering. 4. Understand the four-step model for the transport planning process. 5. Learn and use the models/methods in the four-step planning including trip generations, trip distributions, fashion choice and traffic assignment. 6. Know practical software for transportation planning. 7. Understand the principles and models of traffic flow and theories. 8. Understand horizontal, vertical alignment and road structure for the design and function of roads. 9. Understand the geometric design and signal timing at intersections. 10. Evaluate and design the capacity and service level of road sections and intersections. 11. Acquire the information about the innovative transportation technologies such as automated vehicles and transport electrification. 12. Solve transport engineering problems through active and engaging individual and team-based problem solving. 13. Practice transportation engineering problems through active and engaging individual and team-based problem-solving, and connect the problem-based learning to real-world examples of transportation infrastructure projects.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
488	Sustainable urban water engineering (compulsory)		7.5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the importance of water issues and environmental legislation to achieve sustainable development of urban infrastructure and construction. 2. Design sampling and monitoring strategies, and select relevant measurement techniques, to determine and assess water and sediment quality affected by urban pollution. 3. Propose and design appropriate innovative and sustainable preventive measures and engineered treatment methods for polluted landfill leachate, road runoff, urban stormwater and urban sediment. 4. Present results and knowledge, obtained from case-study investigations and the scientific literature, through oral and written presentations, and critically review the work in a professional and qualified manner.
489	Contaminated sites and remediation (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop conceptual site models for contaminated sites as a basis for sampling strategies and risk assessment. - Apply methods to design site investigations and methods to evaluate sampled data at contaminated sites, as well as evaluate limitations and uncertainties. - Apply methods for human health and ecological risk assessment at contaminated sites, and critically evaluate the result. - Understand and describe the design and functionality of commonly used remediation technologies as well as identify technically feasible remediation strategies for contaminated sites of different characteristics. - Evaluate the sustainability of remediation strategies, as well as critically review the result. - In written report and oral presentation, clearly present and thoroughly evaluate and discuss risk assessment results and remediation strategies at contaminated sites, as well as critically review other groups project reports.
490	Soil modelling and numerical analyses (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply 2D geotechnical finite element (FE) analyses to geotechnical problems - understand the role of the constitutive model and numerical analyses in geotechnical design, and how some special features (such as stress initialization, initial state, coupled flow-deformation analyses, non-linear soil models and structural elements) are needed for performing geotechnical finite element analyses; - distinguish between different constitutive (soil) models, considering both simple and advanced soil models, and thus be able to select an appropriate model for a given geotechnical analysis; - evaluate appropriate input values for the model parameters of the constitutive models considered, and well as to appreciate the sensitivity of the simulation results to the selected parameter values; - simplify geotechnical and soil-structure interaction problems to create numerical models with increasing complexity - perform coupled 2D analyses of typical geotechnical problems (embankments, slopes, foundations, excavations) with geotechnical finite element analyses, considering both Ultimate Limit State (ULS) and Serviceability Limit State (SLS); - present, study and critically assess the results of geotechnical numerical analyses;
491	Urban metabolism and resources (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain critical aspects of sustainable development for urban areas with focus on environmental impacts and resource constraints; - study urban systems, including water and transportation systems, and resource flows to identify eventual problems in relation to sustainable development; - suggest improvements to technical systems, technology, resource management and lifestyles that may enable efficient resource use, mitigate climate impacts and prevent pollution; - simulate, predict and evaluate the effect of suggested improvements in urban systems on resource flows and the environmental impact.
492	Railway technology (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe the railway system and its main components - Explain main concepts regarding the railway in the society related to market, economics and environmental influence - Describe the most common track and vehicle concepts

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe the fundamentals of asset management systems - Understand the basics of railway mechanics and the possibilities of employing numerical simulations in evaluating loading and predicting deterioration of different parts of the railway system - Explain how different design and maintenance concepts affect deterioration, reliability, safety and environmental impact - Explain the basics of mechanical deterioration of the different parts of the railway system and describe how increased deterioration affects safety, life cycle costs, reliability and environmental impact
493	Vehicle and traffic safety (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List the most important sensor technologies for automotive safety applications (active safety and automated vehicles) - Explain the advantages and limitations of different sensor technologies - Explain the role of active safety in the context of traffic safety - Describe the general architecture of active safety systems - Provide examples of active safety systems on the market and describe their operation and implementation - Explain what cooperative systems are and how they can be used to extend the functionalities of active safety systems - Discuss the importance of human factors in relation to active safety and automated vehicles Illustrate the tools currently available for evaluating active safety systems and automated vehicles - Describe various means to reduce traffic related fatalities and injuries - Discuss the effect of different car structure design and crash configurations on in-crash load paths in the vehicle and in the occupants - Explain means to avoid incompatibility between different road vehicles and road furniture - Describe how car restraints and car structure can reduce injury risk - Relate the biomechanics of the human body to crash safety - Describe the basics of the explicit finite element method and give examples of how simulations can be used to assess crash safety - Design and perform a crash test, filter and analyse data, suggest applicable injury criteria and calculate injury criteria values - Discuss ethical aspects, privacy issues and legal responsibility questions concerning vehicle safety systems as well as research methods
494	Advanced transportation engineering (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand and conduct transport planning with state-of-the-art tools and software that are widely used in industry and public agencies. - Analyze traffic facility performance, such as queue time and queue length, under various demands, capacities, and reasons for breakdown. - Design operations for efficient transport and mobility of passengers and goods, such as vehicle route design. - Address fleet operation problems for shared mobility (e.g., e-scooter fleet maintenance). - Investigate and solve battery charging and routing problems for vehicle fleets in the era of electrification.
495	Drinking water engineering (elective)		7.5	<p>The overall teaching goal is that the students will become highly motivated to learn more in the drinking water engineering area and adapt a deep learning approach.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and explain the entire technical drinking water system - from source to tap · Explain the connection of raw water quality, treatment requirements and distribution network to drinking water quality and consumer's health · Identify and categorize risks and hazards in drinking water systems to consumer health · Apply the gained knowledge to design new or redesign existing processes in a drinking water treatment plant · Combine gained hydraulic knowledge when designing a new or redesigning an existing drinking water distribution network -

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				including working pressure, reservoir volume and water demand · Analyse and design the drinking water network layout using hydrodynamic computer models · Combine knowledge of water processes and network hydraulics to design a sustainable drinking water network · Criticize and modify existing water supply systems to become sustainable
496	Risk assessment and decision support (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estimate risk levels using risk assessment methods in order to evaluate analysed systems. - Evaluate and critically review risk reduction measures by using decision analysis methods in combination with risk assessments. - Analyse and evaluate uncertainties in risk calculations and decision analysis outcomes. - Identify and demonstrate strengths and limitations of methods for risk assessment and decision analysis. - In written report and oral presentation, clearly present and thoroughly evaluate and discuss results of risk assessments and decision analyses in infrastructure and environmental engineering projects.
497	Advanced wastewater engineering (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the most important concepts of the entire wastewater system from collection of sewage and stormwater to treatment systems and understand the consequences of discharge to recipient. - Describe different types of collection systems, including the sewer system and storm water collection system. - Understand how the wastewater collection system influences the treatment system. - Apply existing theories to design different types of treatment systems and to identify critical parameters and make appropriate assumptions and judgements. - Understand the microbial, chemical and physical processes involved in advanced wastewater treatment systems. - Explain the performance of treatment systems by analysing either monitored data or results from computer simulations. - Understand the main concepts of sustainability related to the wastewater system. - Obtain the skills to present the project assignment in a professional manner, both orally and in written text as well as in a critical manner assess and discuss the project performed by another group.
499	Applied hydrogeology (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a conceptual hydrogeological model of an aquifer. - Plan, establish and perform an investigation program for hydraulic analysis of a groundwater aquifer. - Perform a hydraulic analysis of a groundwater aquifer. - Evaluate groundwater quality and quantity for water supply. - Design a groundwater supply facility. - Design a groundwater infiltration facility. - Evaluate the protection need for a long-term sustainable use of groundwater resources.
501	Water systems and modelling (elective)	3.4	7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand the hydraulic, hydrodynamic and pollutant transport processes in natural and constructed water systems - Distinguish between different models, considering both simple and advanced models - Be able to select and use an appropriate model for a given analysis to assess the quantity and quality of water, including model calibration, validation and uncertainty - Evaluate appropriate input values for the model parameters of the models considered, and to appreciate the sensitivity of the simulation results to the selected parameter values;
502	Contemporary topics in geomechanics (elective)		7.5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the principle of effective stresses in a partially saturated state (single Bishop's effective stress measure versus two independent stress measures). 2. Recognise the effect of partial saturation on the shear strength and stiffness of soil. 3. Use conventional methods to estimate the slope stability with partial saturation effect.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				4. Apply conventional method(s) to estimate 1D soil collapse/swelling due to variation in suction. 5. Describe the principles of various tunnelling methods in soils and rocks, and understand the main challenges and environmental effects. 6. Understand the principles and execution of various ground improvement techniques, in order to be able to select the most appropriate methods for a given problem from a technical and sustainability point of view. 7. Apply the best practice in designing ground improvement. 8. Understand the additional geotechnical challenges in the construction of new railways (high speed rail) and foundations for renewable energy, related to soil dynamics.
503	Sustainable transportation (elective)		7.5	After completion of this course, the student should be able to: - Explain the unsustainable impacts of the transport sector - Analyse the potential and challenges of alternative fuels and innovative vehicle technology for the road transport sector - Analyse the potential and challenges of alternative transport modes - Analyse the potential and challenges of transport policy measures
504	Master's Thesis		60	The learning objectives for a thesis are based on the objectives for Master of Science in Engineering/ Architecture/Master of Science degrees formulated in Chalmers' local Master's degree procedures. Specific learning objectives that are to be fulfilled in the master's thesis are that the student should be able to: - in their project use essential in-depth knowledge of the major subject/field of study and, in a scientifically correct way, relate to current research and development work; - choose and state one's reasons for selecting their project method with respect to the major subject/field of study; - contribute to research and development work, and be able to relate their work to relevant scientific or technical/industrial/architectonic contexts; - based on a holistic view, critically, independently and creatively identify, formulate and deal with complex issues; - plan and, with adequate methods, carry out qualified tasks within the designated framework and also be able to evaluate this work; - create, analyse and critically evaluate different technical/architectonic solutions; - critically and systematically integrate knowledge; - present and discuss their conclusions as well as the knowledge and arguments these are based upon both in spoken and written English; - within the framework for the specific project, identify which issues need to be addressed for relevant societal, ethical and ecological factors to be observed, and - observe and discuss ethical aspects of research and development work, both pertaining to how the work is carried out as well as what it explores/develops; - identify and discuss needs for further elucidation of different project aspects before decision-making or project realisation, when relevant. Upon completion of the degree work, the student shall have demonstrated such knowledge and ability as are required to work independently as a Master of Architecture/Master of Science in Engineering/ Master of Science.
505	Master's Thesis		60	The learning objectives for a thesis are based on the objectives for Master of Science in Engineering/ Architecture/Master of Science degrees formulated in Chalmers' local Master's degree procedures. Specific learning objectives that are to be fulfilled in the master's thesis are that the student should be able to:

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in their project use essential in-depth knowledge of the major subject/field of study and, in a scientifically correct way, relate to current research and development work; - choose and state one's reasons for selecting their project method with respect to the major subject/field of study; - contribute to research and development work, and be able to relate their work to relevant scientific or technical/industrial/architectonic contexts; - based on a holistic view, critically, independently and creatively identify, formulate and deal with complex issues; - plan and, with adequate methods, carry out qualified tasks within the designated framework and also be able to evaluate this work; - create, analyse and critically evaluate different technical/architectonic solutions; - critically and systematically integrate knowledge; - present and discuss their conclusions as well as the knowledge and arguments these are based upon both in spoken and written English; - within the framework for the specific project, identify which issues need to be addressed for relevant societal, ethical and ecological factors to be observed, and - observe and discuss ethical aspects of research and development work, both pertaining to how the work is carried out as well as what it explores/develops; - identify and discuss needs for further elucidation of different project aspects before decision-making or project realisation, when relevant. <p>Upon completion of the degree work, the student shall have demonstrated such knowledge and ability as are required to work independently as a Master of Architecture/Master of Science in Engineering/ Master of Science.</p>
506	Contaminated sites and remediation (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop conceptual site models for contaminated sites as a basis for sampling strategies and risk assessment. - Apply methods to design site investigations and methods to evaluate sampled data at contaminated sites, as well as evaluate limitations and uncertainties. - Apply methods for human health and ecological risk assessment at contaminated sites, and critically evaluate the result. - Understand and describe the design and functionality of commonly used remediation technologies as well as identify technically feasible remediation strategies for contaminated sites of different characteristics. - Evaluate the sustainability of remediation strategies, as well as critically review the result. - In written report and oral presentation, clearly present and thoroughly evaluate and discuss risk assessment results and remediation strategies at contaminated sites, as well as critically review other groups project reports.
507	Soil modelling and numerical analyses (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply 2D geotechnical finite element (FE) analyses to geotechnical problems - understand the role of the constitutive model and numerical analyses in geotechnical design, and how some special features (such as stress initialization, initial state, coupled flow-deformation analyses, non-linear soil models and structural elements) are needed for performing geotechnical finite element analyses; - distinguish between different constitutive (soil) models, considering both simple and advanced soil models, and thus be able to select an appropriate model for a given geotechnical analysis; - evaluate appropriate input values for the model parameters of the constitutive models considered, and well as to appreciate the sensitivity of the simulation results to the selected parameter values; - simplify geotechnical and soil-structure interaction problems to create numerical models with increasing complexity - perform coupled 2D analyses of typical geotechnical problems (embankments, slopes, foundations, excavations) with geotechnical finite element analyses, considering both Ultimate Limit State (ULS) and Serviceability Limit State (SLS); - present, study and critically assess the results of geotechnical numerical analyses;

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
508	Urban metabolism and resources (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain critical aspects of sustainable development for urban areas with focus on environmental impacts and resource constraints; - study urban systems, including water and transportation systems, and resource flows to identify eventual problems in relation to sustainable development; - suggest improvements to technical systems, technology, resource management and lifestyles that may enable efficient resource use, mitigate climate impacts and prevent pollution; - simulate, predict and evaluate the effect of suggested improvements in urban systems on resource flows and the environmental impact.
509	Railway technology (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe the railway system and its main components - Explain main concepts regarding the railway in the society related to market, economics and environmental influence - Describe the most common track and vehicle concepts - Describe the fundamentals of asset management systems - Understand the basics of railway mechanics and the possibilities of employing numerical simulations in evaluating loading and predicting deterioration of different parts of the railway system - Explain how different design and maintenance concepts affect deterioration, reliability, safety and environmental impact - Explain the basics of mechanical deterioration of the different parts of the railway system and describe how increased deterioration affects safety, life cycle costs, reliability and environmental impact
510	Vehicle and traffic safety (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List the most important sensor technologies for automotive safety applications (active safety and automated vehicles) - Explain the advantages and limitations of different sensor technologies - Explain the role of active safety in the context of traffic safety - Describe the general architecture of active safety systems - Provide examples of active safety systems on the market and describe their operation and implementation - Explain what cooperative systems are and how they can be used to extend the functionalities of active safety systems - Discuss the importance of human factors in relation to active safety and automated vehicles Illustrate the tools currently available for evaluating active safety systems and automated vehicles - Describe various means to reduce traffic related fatalities and injuries - Discuss the effect of different car structure design and crash configurations on in-crash load paths in the vehicle and in the occupants - Explain means to avoid incompatibility between different road vehicles and road furniture - Describe how car restraints and car structure can reduce injury risk - Relate the biomechanics of the human body to crash safety - Describe the basics of the explicit finite element method and give examples of how simulations can be used to assess crash safety - Design and perform a crash test, filter and analyse data, suggest applicable injury criteria and calculate injury criteria values - Discuss ethical aspects, privacy issues and legal responsibility questions concerning vehicle safety systems as well as research methods
511	Advanced transportation engineering (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand and conduct transport planning with state-of-the-art tools and software that are widely used in industry and public agencies. - Analyze traffic facility performance, such as queue time and queue length, under various demands, capacities, and reasons for breakdown.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design operations for efficient transport and mobility of passengers and goods, such as vehicle route design. - Address fleet operation problems for shared mobility (e.g., e-scooter fleet maintenance). - Investigate and solve battery charging and routing problems for vehicle fleets in the era of electrification.
512	Drinking water engineering (elective)		7.5	<p>The overall teaching goal is that the students will become highly motivated to learn more in the drinking water engineering area and adapt a deep learning approach.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Describe and explain the entire technical drinking water system - from source to tap · Explain the connection of raw water quality, treatment requirements and distribution network to drinking water quality and consumer's health · Identify and categorize risks and hazards in drinking water systems to consumer health · Apply the gained knowledge to design new or redesign existing processes in a drinking water treatment plant · Combine gained hydraulic knowledge when designing a new or redesigning an existing drinking water distribution network - including working pressure, reservoir volume and water demand · Analyse and design the drinking water network layout using hydrodynamic computer models · Combine knowledge of water processes and network hydraulics to design a sustainable drinking water network · Criticize and modify existing water supply systems to become sustainable
513	Risk assessment and decision support (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estimate risk levels using risk assessment methods in order to evaluate analysed systems. - Evaluate and critically review risk reduction measures by using decision analysis methods in combination with risk assessments. - Analyse and evaluate uncertainties in risk calculations and decision analysis outcomes. - Identify and demonstrate strengths and limitations of methods for risk assessment and decision analysis. - In written report and oral presentation, clearly present and thoroughly evaluate and discuss results of risk assessments and decision analyses in infrastructure and environmental engineering projects.
514	Master's Thesis		30	<p>The learning objectives for a thesis are based on the objectives for Master of Science in Engineering/ Architecture/Master of Science degrees formulated in Chalmers' local Master's degree procedures.</p> <p>Specific learning objectives that are to be fulfilled in the master's thesis are that the student should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in their project use essential in-depth knowledge of the major subject/field of study and, in a scientifically correct way, relate to current research and development work; - choose and state one's reasons for selecting their project method with respect to the major subject/field of study; - contribute to research and development work, and be able to relate their work to relevant scientific or technical/industrial/architectonic contexts; - based on a holistic view, critically, independently and creatively identify, formulate and deal with complex issues; - plan and, with adequate methods, carry out qualified tasks within the designated framework and also be able to evaluate this work; - create, analyse and critically evaluate different technical/architectonic solutions; - critically and systematically integrate knowledge; - present and discuss their conclusions as well as the knowledge and arguments these are based upon both in spoken and written English; - within the framework for the specific project, identify which issues need to be addressed for relevant societal, ethical and ecological factors to be observed, and - observe and discuss ethical aspects of research and development work, both pertaining to how the work is carried out as

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>well as what it explores/develops;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify and discuss needs for further elucidation of different project aspects before decision-making or project realisation, when relevant. <p>Upon completion of the degree work, the student shall have demonstrated such knowledge and ability as are required to work independently as a Master of Architecture/Master of Science in Engineering/ Master of Science.</p>
515	Master's Thesis		30	<p>The learning objectives for a thesis are based on the objectives for Master of Science in Engineering/ Architecture/Master of Science degrees formulated in Chalmers' local Master's degree procedures.</p> <p>Specific learning objectives that are to be fulfilled in the master's thesis are that the student should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in their project use essential in-depth knowledge of the major subject/field of study and, in a scientifically correct way, relate to current research and development work; - choose and state one's reasons for selecting their project method with respect to the major subject/field of study; - contribute to research and development work, and be able to relate their work to relevant scientific or technical/industrial/architectonic contexts; - based on a holistic view, critically, independently and creatively identify, formulate and deal with complex issues; - plan and, with adequate methods, carry out qualified tasks within the designated framework and also be able to evaluate this work; - create, analyse and critically evaluate different technical/architectonic solutions; - critically and systematically integrate knowledge; - present and discuss their conclusions as well as the knowledge and arguments these are based upon both in spoken and written English; - within the framework for the specific project, identify which issues need to be addressed for relevant societal, ethical and ecological factors to be observed, and - observe and discuss ethical aspects of research and development work, both pertaining to how the work is carried out as well as what it explores/develops; - identify and discuss needs for further elucidation of different project aspects before decision-making or project realisation, when relevant. <p>Upon completion of the degree work, the student shall have demonstrated such knowledge and ability as are required to work independently as a Master of Architecture/Master of Science in Engineering/ Master of Science.</p>
516	Advanced wastewater engineering (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the most important concepts of the entire wastewater system from collection of sewage and stormwater to treatment systems and understand the consequences of discharge to recipient. - Describe different types of collection systems, including the sewer system and storm water collection system. - Understand how the wastewater collection system influences the treatment system. - Apply existing theories to design different types of treatment systems and to identify critical parameters and make appropriate assumptions and judgements. - Understand the microbial, chemical and physical processes involved in advanced wastewater treatment systems. - Explain the performance of treatment systems by analysing either monitored data or results from computer simulations. - Understand the main concepts of sustainability related to the wastewater system. - Obtain the skills to present the project assignment in a professional manner, both orally and in written text as well as in a critical manner assess and discuss the project performed by another group.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
518	Applied hydrogeology (elective)		7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a conceptual hydrogeological model of an aquifer. - Plan, establish and perform an investigation program for hydraulic analysis of a groundwater aquifer. - Perform a hydraulic analysis of a groundwater aquifer. - Evaluate groundwater quality and quantity for water supply. - Design a groundwater supply facility. - Design a groundwater infiltration facility. - Evaluate the protection need for a long-term sustainable use of groundwater resources.
520	Graduate Seminar		Non-credit	It is a proposal seminar given by the M.S. Candidate either in the second or third term of the graduate study. If available, the candidate may present the initial findings of his/her thesis. Credits will be given upon the completion of the seminar.
521	Graduate Seminar		Non-credit	This is a second graduate seminar course in the M.S. program. Students register to this course in all semesters except the semester that they register to ENVE 598 to give their proposal seminar. Attendance is required in this course.
522	Pollution Control in Sea Environment I		3	Hydrodynamic/oceanographic characteristics (current, turbulent mixing, density, structure, etc.) . Waste dispersion characteristics. Turbulent diffusion / dispersion theories. Turbulent diffusion / dispersion measurements. Dilution and mixing of pollutants and heated discharges from sea outfalls. Jet and plume mixing. turbulent buoyant jets in uniform and stratified environments. Technical Elective
523	Modeling Soil and Groundwater Pollution		3	Mathematical models for flow and transport of contaminants in soil and groundwater systems. Analytical and numerical solutions of mathematical models. Stochastic aspects of subsurface flow and contaminant transport. Case studies and applications of selected computer programs to investigate problems of various complexity. Current research topics and directions. Technical Elective
524	Industrial Water and Wastewater Treatment		3	Industrial wastewater and sludge treatment with special reference to hazardous wastes. Case studies for various industries; characteristics and composition of the wastes and availability of waste treatment technology. Radioactive and thermal pollution control. Technical Elective
525	Pollution Transport in River Systems		3	Introduction to Advanced River Water Quality Models. General Model Formulation Structures. Constituent Reactions and Interrelationships. Computer Applications to Selected Cases. Uncertainty Analysis. Technical Elective
526	Industrial Air Pollution Control		3	Air pollution indices. Planning industrial air pollution surveys; sources, inventories, emission factors, other factors, stack sampling; isokinetic sampling, sampling trains. Area sampling for industrial pollutants. Air quality monitoring design for industrial areas. Various strategies for industrial air pollution control. Technical Elective
527	Advances in Water Supply Engineering		3	Use of computer models for pipe sizing of distribution network design; Computer analysis of pipe networks (Loop and Node Methods; Optimization of Networks with a Discrete Methods; Extended Period Simulation). Treatment of waters which requires non-standard (special techniques) approaches. Technical Elective

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
528	Advanced Water and Wastewater Treatment		3	Purpose and benefits of advanced treatment; processes for solids removal. Processes for nutrient removal. Membrane processes, biological-chemical treatment, physical- chemical treatment. Selecting and combining unit processes to obtain the desired water quality. Technical Elective
529	Advanced Atmospheric Dispersion		3	Review of dispersion characteristics of the atmospheric boundary layer. Complex models of dispersion. Numerical modelling techniques. Heavy gas dispersion. Effects of clouds in dispersion. Deposition of pollutants on soil and water. Complex terrain dispersion. Effects of buildings on dispersion. Dispersion in buildings. Design of monitoring programs for atmospheric air quality. Technical Elective
530	Contaminated Site Remediation		3	Properties of contaminants, phase distribution, source control; site characterization and monitoring(vadose zone and aquifer characteristics, the extent of contamination) ; in situ soil and groundwater remediation technologies e.g., pump and treat, capture zone analysis, permeable reactive barriers, air sparging, soil vapor extraction, bioventing, land treatment, monitored natural attenuation; design, operation and performance assessment of the remedial systems; remedial goal and risk assessment; assessment of remedial alternatives, cost analyses; case studies and computer application on remedial systems. Technical Elective
531	Principles of Risk Assessment and Management		3	Assessment of acute hazards of toxic and flammable materials used in chemical industries. Hazard identification using fault trees, and consequence assessment using mathematical models. Physical principles of consequence modelling. Estimation of industrial risks and comparison with other commonly understood risks. Risk management decision making in design of chemical industries and land use planning. Technical Elective
532	Atmospheric Chemistry		3	Description of the atmosphere. Greenhouse effect. Stratospheric ozone. Photochemical smog. Acid rain. Brief introduction to atmospheric aerosols. Technical Elective
533	Environmental Applications of Biomolecular Engineering		3	Problems posed by natural and engineered environments for monitoring microorganisms; advantages and pitfalls of molecular techniques for microbial community analyses, FAME, PCR, 16S/18S rRNA sequencing, phylogenetic analysis and relationship between phylogenetic information and ecological function of the microbial communities; profiling of complex microbial populations by DGGE, TTGE, SSCP, RAPD, ARDRA, T-RFLP, LH-PCR, and RISA; enumeration, identification and monitoring of pollutant-degrading bacteria by using nucleic acid probes, FISH, MAR, and SIP; application of omic technologies and post-genomic approaches in environmental engineering. Technical Elective
534	Environmental Biotechnology		3	Advanced biological reactors, enzyme reactors, treatment with immobilized cells and enzymes, biodegradation of unusual compounds and tests for biodegradability, effect of metals on biological kinetics, biological recycling of mineral wastes and residues, thermophilic microorganisms and their application to waste treatment. Technical Elective
535	Advanced Biological Treatment		3	Review of biological treatment processes. Mechanism, kinetics and microbiology of nutrient removing activated sludge.IAWQ Task group models for nutrient removing activated sludge. Calibration techniques for the Task group models. Hands-on practice with SSSP and ASIM computer models. Microbiology of bulking and population dynamics of activated sludge. Sequencing

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				batch, GAC and PAC activated sludge. Technical Elective
536	Advanced Environmental Chemistry		3	Nature and properties of environmental chemistry. Ingredients of environmental chemical work, sampling and sample storage, analysis method adoption and standard methods of analysis, chemical for environmental analysis, their grades and purification techniques primary standards in env. chemical work. Case studies. Technical Elective
537	Environmental Systems Engineering		3	Handling and treatment of engineering data. Experimental design. Systems approach to problem solving. Formulation of management models. Linear and non-linear programming. Selected applications in water, air, and soil quality management, solid and hazardous waste management. Technical Elective
538	Heuristic Optimization and Modeling of Environmental Systems		3	Introduction to heuristic optimization and modeling techniques; genetic algorithms; ant colony optimization; neural networks; simulated annealing; case studies on application of heuristic optimization and simulation methods to environmental engineering problems including air pollution control, groundwater remediation, solid waste management, water quality management. Technical Elective
539	Anaerobic Treatment of Wastes		3	Chemistry, microbiology. Environmental requirements and control conditions for anaerobic treatment. Toxic materials and their control. Process design. Anaerobic treatment of organic wastes. Advances in anaerobic pond system design. Anaerobic treatment modeling. Energy recovery, effluent treatment of wastes. Anaerobic sludge treatment, utilization of digested sludge. Biogas recovery from anaerobic treatment plants. Technical Elective
540	Marine Pollution		3	Present health of the oceans. The need of control of pollution due to potentially harmful substances in the ocean. Definition of potentially harmful substances; Inorganics, organics, radioactive matter, solid waste. Marine environment as a waste receiving body Environmental capacity. Potential impairment of marine ecosystems and water uses. Case studies. Technical Elective
541	Fate of Pollutants in the Environment		3	Fundamental concepts regarding the fate of a pollutant once released into the environment. Classification of pollutants, equilibrium partitioning between gaseous, liquid and solid phases: vapor pressure, solubility in water, air-organic solvent, air-water partitioning, organic liquid-water partitioning, sorption, solid-water distribution, partitioning to living media. Abiotic and biotic transformation processes: hydrolysis, redox and photochemical reactions, biodegradation. Transport of pollutants and modeling concepts. Case studies. Technical Elective
542	Research Methods & Ethics in Environmental Engineering		Non-credit	Research methods, ethics and ethical conduct in engineering research, setting a research goal, structuring a research plan, designing an independent research proposal, ethical behaviour in academic writing and presentation.
543	Energy and Environment		3	Energy resources in the world and in Turkey. Efficient use of resources, energy conversion technologies and their general environmental impacts, traditional and advanced energy conversion technologies based on fossil fuels, renewable energies and applications, sustainability in energy production. Green House Problem, CO2 capture and CO2 sequestration

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				technologies, recent advances in research in this field. Comparative analysis of the existing systems with new systems and case studies on specific applications. Technical Elective
544	Remote Sensing for Environmental Engineers			Introduction to remote sensing science and technology, data sources and structures; use of remote sensing in environmental problem detections; applications in the literature for various environmental problems and environmental system management; example applications for monitoring and management of water, soil, and air quality as well as contemporary environmental issues. Technical Elective
545	Special Topics in Environmental Engineering		Non-credit	Courses not listed in the catalogue are given as Special Topics courses. Contents vary from year to year according to interest of students and instructor in charge. Courses include various environmental engineering topics.
547	Physicochemical Processes and Treatment	Fall	7.5	<p>Course description: Review and analysis of theoretical basis of physical and chemical processes commonly employed in environmental engineering systems and taking place in receiving media. Definition and formulation of design and operation parameters for the unit processes of aeration and gas transfer, mixing, coagulation and flocculation, sedimentation, filtration, flotation, adsorption-ion exchange, chemical oxidation and disinfection.</p> <p>Course objectives: To introduce the theoretical basis of physical and chemical unit processes of environmental engineering To evaluate physical-chemical processes in terms of Environmental Engineering applications to provide a basis for environmental modeling and treatment applications To derivate design and operation parameters of physical-chemical processes</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: - Advanced theoretical knowledge and engineering analysis of the unit physical and chemical processes of environmental engineering (knowledge) - Design and operation basis and related criteria for aeration and gas transfer (knowledge + skill + communication and social competency) - Design and operation basis and related criteria for mixing-coagulation and flocculation (knowledge + skill+ communication and social competency) - Design and operation basis and related criteria for sedimentation, filtration, flotation (knowledge + skill+ communication and social competency) - Design and operation basis and related criteria for neutralization and pH adjustment (knowledge + skill+ communication and social competency) - Design and operation basis and related criteria for chemical oxidation and disinfection (knowledge + skill+ communication and social competency) - Design and operation basis and related criteria for adsorption, ion-exchange (knowledge + skill+ communication and social competency)</p>
548	Statistical Analysis for Experimental		7.5	<p>Course description: Introduction, Basic Concepts of Statistics, Probability Theory, Probability Distributions, Sampling Distributions, Statistical</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
	Design and Data Processing			<p>Hypothesis Testing, Regression Analysis, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Tolerance intervals and prediction intervals, Experimental design methods, sizing the experiment, Parameter estimation for empirical models.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting the approaches for the evaluation of experimental data and interpretation of - Supporting experimental design by using statistical methods - Evaluation of experimental results with the aid of advanced statistical methods <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of statistical concepts in the field of Environmental Engineering - Implementation of statistical methods in Environmental Engineering applications - Evaluation and analysis of experimental data and results - Computer aided statistical calculations and visualization of results - Experimental design using advanced statistical tools
549	Air Pollution		7.5	<p>Course description: Fundamentals of air pollution. Air pollutants. Impacts of air pollution on human health, welfare, and ecosystem. Air pollution sources. Air pollutant formation mechanisms. Atmospheric transformation and transport of pollutants. Atmospheric reactions. Meteorology. Dispersion models. Industrial air pollutant control technologies. Air quality measurement techniques. Air pollutant measurement techniques at the source. Emission inventories, Greenhouse gases inventories, IPCC approximation. Air quality management. Legal statute. (Control of Industrial originated air pollution Large Combustion Plants, Ambient Air pollution Evaluation and Management, Control of air pollution originating from Home Heating) Global air pollution problems and effects. Climate change and air quality.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have the students to develop a background in air pollution by understanding the fundamental knowledge in air pollution thought in class and connecting this knowledge to other environmental engineering fields, - Develop a solid understanding of local and global air pollution problems, describing of specific air pollution problems and solving the problems - Understanding of Air pollutants sampling and measurement techniques and legal statutes and management principles of air pollution <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing and intensifying knowledge in the related program's area, based upon the competency in the undergraduate level (sufficient knowledge) (knowledge). - Interpreting and forming new types of knowledge by combining the knowledge from the area and the knowledge from various other disciplines (skill). - Assessing the specialistic knowledge and skill gained through the study with a critical view and directing one's own learning process (Learning Competence) - Using the knowledge and the skills for problem solving and/or application (which are processed within the area) in inter-disciplinary studies (Area Specific Competency).

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
550	Integrated Watershed Management		7.5	<p>Course description: Introduction to integrated watershed management; land-use planning, disaster mitigation and watershed management, categories of watershed degradation and water-related disasters, Integrated watershed management; development of a management system, funding arrangements, institutional/legal requirements, public involvement, human resource and policy development, Data collection, watershed management, land resource and natural hazard assessment; models and decision-support systems, Options for watershed management and hazard reduction.</p> <p>Course objectives: - Main components of integrated watershed management, their necessity, principal approaches - Importance of land-use and planning in watershed management, mitigation of disaster hazards and effects, development of management strategies, resource utilization and contribution of public to the process - Use of tools like models and decision support systems in watershed management studies</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: - Intensifying knowledge on integrated watershed management (knowledge). - The ability to evaluate and use information gathered from scientific literature studies and applications related with integrated watershed management (skill). - The ability to analyze, synthesize and evaluate information about principles and applications of integrated watershed management, land-planning and water resources management (skill). - Preparing a presentation and report in English on integrated watershed management (Communication and Social Competency).</p>
551	Scientific Research, Ethics and Seminar		NA	<p>Course description: Definition and development of science, scientific research approach, literature survey, research design, quantitative and qualitative research methodologies, data gathering, writing techniques for thesis, project, and scientific article, ethical principles to be followed when conducting research, ethical principles to be followed when publishing, citation ethics, tips for a successful presentation, students presentations within the scope of their thesis topics/own engineering field.</p> <p>Course objectives: 1. To learn what is science, scientific research methods 2. To learn scientific methodology, research design and data gathering 3. To learn types of scientific publications (thesis, scientific article, report etc.), 4. To learn ethical principles that need to be carried out in scientific researches and publications 5. Evaluating outstanding presentation techniques, systematically transferring the current developments in the area or one's own work to other groups in and out of the area; in written, oral and visual forms</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: 1. To learn what science, scientific knowledge, and historical development of science are 2. To learn scientific research methods and to be able to apply them 3. To be able to carry on a literature survey and analysis 4. To learn about various types of scientific publications and their basic properties 5. To learn, to anticipate and to follow ethics while pursuing a scientific work 6. To prepare presentations about technical or non-technical subjects.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				7. To learn how to address the audience orally and audio-visually 8. To appreciate the importance of communication during presentation, to acquire the skill to perform presentations in front of communities
552	Biological Nitrogen and Phosphorus Removal From Wastewater		7.5	<p>Course description: Nitrogen and Phosphorus in wastewaters: sources and quantities, impact of nitrogen and phosphorus. - Principles of Biological Nitrogen Removal: Kinetics and Stoichiometry of Nitrification and Denitrification. Principles of Biological Phosphorus Removal: biochemical mechanism. - Design of Activated Sludge Biological Nutrient Removal Plants: Process Configurations, Effects of Wastewater Characteristics and Operation Conditions, Design Algorithm for Nitrogen Removal Systems, Enhanced Biological Phosphorus Removal with Nitrogen Removal.</p> <p>Course objectives: - Forms, sources, quantities and impacts of Nitrogen and Phosphorus - Principles of Biological Nitrogen and Phosphorus Removal - Design of Activated Sludge Biological Nutrient Removal Plants</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: - Developing and intensifying knowledge in nutrient removal processes (knowledge). - The ability to analyze, synthesize and evaluate information about principles and applications of biological nutrient removal processes (skill). - The ability to design Biological Nutrient Removal - - - Activated Sludge Systems (skill). - The ability to design Biological Nutrient Removal Activated Sludge Systems (skill).</p>
553	Odor and Emission Control in Environmental Systems		7.5	<p>Course description: Introduction, definition of odor and VOC. Odor sampling and measurement techniques on the sources and ambient air. Olfactometric and analytical techniques. Toxic air emission. Odor generation and release on the Environmental Systems (collection systems, wastewater treatment plants, sludge digestion and drying plants, combustion plants, gasification plants, solid and hazardous waste deposition plants, compost plants). Odor emission inventory. Odor nuisance and effects on the public health issues. Minimizing odor and fugitive VOC emissions. Containment of odors and emissions from wastewater Treatment plants. Biological, physicochemical and thermal odor control. odor modeling. Odor pollution legislation</p> <p>Course objectives: - Giving the basic knowledge to student about odor and VOC pollution arising environmental systems, and raising the awareness - To be informed of students about odor and VOC pollutants sampling and measurement, air quality management application and legal statue. - Understanding of odor and VOC formation mechanism and control methodologies for environmental systems and take into consideration for design criteria of env. Systems.</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: - Developing and intensifying knowledge in the related program's area, based upon the competency in the undergraduate level (sufficient knowledge) (knowledge). - Interpreting and forming new types of knowledge by combining the knowledge from the area and the knowledge from</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				various other disciplines (skill). - Assessing the specialistic knowledge and skill gained through the study with a critical view and directing one's own learning process (Learning Competence). - Using the knowledge and the skills for problem solving and/or application (which are processed within the area) in inter-disciplinary studies (Area Specific Competency).
554	Wastewater Reclamation and Reuse		7.5	Course description: Definitions of terms related to water reclamation and reuse; potential uses of reclaimed wastewater; benefits of wastewater reuse; reasons for the growing use of reclaimed wastewater, technical issues in planning wastewater reclamation and reuse systems, Evaluation of the wastewater reuse technology and potential, wastewater reuse regulations and guidelines, Reuse applications: Urban reuse, industrial reuse, agricultural reuse, groundwater recharge, recreational reuse, Funding alternatives for water reuse systems. Course objectives: - Potential uses of reclaimed wastewater - Technical issues in planning wastewater reclamation and reuse systems - Reuse applications Course learning outcomes: - Developing and intensifying knowledge in potential uses of reclaimed wastewater (knowledge) - The ability to evaluate and use information gathered from scientific knowledge related to technical issues in planning wastewater reclamation and reuse systems (skill) - The ability to evaluate and apply the information on wastewater reuse (skill) - Preparing a presentation and report in English (Communication and Social Competency)
555	Water and Wastewater Treatment Systems		7.5	Course description: Scale-up and scale-down concepts and problems. Fundamentals of scale up: Physical models, general techniques for model development. Similitude and dimension analysis. Scaling up of bioreactors. Scale up methods in use: Fundamental method, semi-fundamental method, dimensional analysis, rules of thumb and regime analysis. Modelling of flows in reactors. Scale up and down applications: Aeration systems, activated sludge and trickling filters, anaerobic contact reactors, anaerobic fluidized bed reactors. Course objectives: - to find solutions for occurring problems in water and wastewater treatment plants with the help of laboratory studies and pilot-scale physical models - to develop scientific and technological principles to compare and reduce the data differences between full-scale plants and different scale model reactor results Course learning outcomes: - To understand basic engineering approaches to water and wastewater treatment process design - To assess the relationship between systems of different scale by applying the theory of similarity - To apply the dimensional analysis and physical modeling principles between different scale systems

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To understand the role of modeling for scaling-up and scaling-down in water and wastewater systems - To choose the suitable design parameters for scale-up and scale-down applications
556	Groundwater Contamination		7.5	<p>Course description: Groundwater hydrology. Water quality standards. Groundwater pollution sources. Transportation of pollutants. Determination of priority pollution sources in ground water. Groundwater monitoring techniques. Groundwater sampling. Groundwater analyses methods. Treatment of organic matter in ground water. In-situ chemical treatment. In-situ biological treatment (bioremediation).</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to define the sources of groundwater pollution - to describe the principles of transport and control of groundwater pollutants <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To describe the groundwater pollutants - To describe the transport the pollutants to groundwater - To make prioritization among the groundwater pollutants - To conduct a groundwater monitoring program - To control the groundwater pollution - To manage the groundwater quality
557	Urban Infrastructure and Environmental Planning		7.5	<p>Course description: All the other urban infrastructure factors that affect environment such as population immigration and urbanization, maintainable development, urbanization, use of land, development policies and planning, social and technical infrastructure, urban protection and transformation, the relationships of planning of the city and urban infrastructure, the place of perception from a distance on environment planning, water assurance, departing of used water, treatment, solid wastes, transportation and planning relationships, special subjects about of studies of urban planning and environment dimension, the preparation of environment maps for urbanization, the quality of life and environment, the urban infrastructure and environmental planning examples in Turkey and abroad.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Putting forward of the relationship between urbanization and environment engineering. - The importance and place of environment structures in urban planning. - Development policies, environmental planning and applications <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The public works of municipalities and Special Urban Administration, the relationship between urban applications and environment engineering about the subjects of urban infrastructure and environment planning (knowledge) - The relationship between urban applications and environment engineering about the subject of the relationship between the planning of the country, district and urban planning and urban infrastructure taking into consideration the maintaining development principle (knowledge) - Forming a relationship between the applications of urbanization and urban infrastructure (environment engineering) and preparing a project (skill)

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The contribution in building healthy cities by working on urban infrastructure and environment planning (skill) - Presentation and preparation of an advanced report about the applications of urban infrastructure. (Communication and social competency)
558	Fate and Management of Micropollutants		7.5	<p>Course description: MPs characterization. Sources of MPs, point, impact assessment of MPs for human health and aquatic life, advance treatment, detoxification, biodegradability, Inhibition effect of MPs, probable improvements in treatment, Control of MPs, priority pollutant lists, black lists, control of organochlorine compounds in drinking water, dioxin, asbestos, heavy metals. Micropollutants in food chain, law and regulations. Special topics.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effect of hazardous and toxic chemicals in water and wastewater, classification and control difficulties, control modes in different countries with different names - Protective management modes and control methodologies for human health and aquatic life - Studies on useful models to create discharge limits and standards for legal enforcements <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about the definitions of constituents related management of MPs, to control of MPs including information about all factors. - Learn about the classification, inventory, control methodologies, legal framework and assessment on MPs. - Learn about to develop the appropriate prevention, control methodology and risk management information. - Learn about the control of TMs at source, environmental management system (EMS). - Learn about the modelling of appropriate management of TMs and determination of the criteria - Learn about the standardization with environmental risk assessment concept <p>Learn about the preparing of suitable proposal project in their professional future</p>
559	Special Topics in Environmental Sciences and Engineering Program		7.5	<p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The objective of the course is to teach special topics in Environmental Science and Engineering area. The course will be conducted by both domestic and international academics.
560	Advanced Analytical Tools in Environmental Engineering		7.5	<p>Course description: The course topics cover theoretical information on chromatography, spectroscopy and advanced analytical techniques for students in Environmental Science and Engineering area, especially for those focusing on the fate of pollutants in treatment systems and the environment as well as information on sampling, data analysis and troubleshooting in laboratory to support the experimental studies of their thesis.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The planning and conducting of all steps from sampling to the evaluation of data that will be needed for the experimental analysis by students studying the fate of pollutants in treatment systems and the environment - Analytical approaches for emerging pollutants

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				Course learning outcomes: - Determination of the parameter to be measured and the method to be used - Planning of the experiments - Selection of sampling points - Fundamentals of analytical methods used in environmental analysis - Data evaluation
561	Energy Efficiency in Wastewater Treatment		7.5	Course description: Definition, importance and scope of energy efficiency in wastewater treatment plants, Scientific and technological fundamentals need to be applied to achieve energy efficiency, Differences between conventional wastewater treatment processes and energy efficient treatment processes, Basic design and operational principles for energy efficient treatment processes, Methods for increasing the performance and energy efficiency of existing wastewater treatment processes, World wide application examples of energy efficient wastewater treatment plants. Course objectives: - Definition of energy efficiency concept in wastewater treatment - Achieving of energy balance and energy saving in wastewater treatment plants - Basic design and operational principles for energy efficient treatment processes - World wide application examples of energy efficient wastewater treatment plants Course learning outcomes: - Having the current and high-level knowledge in the area of energy efficient wastewater treatment (knowledge). - Grasping the inter-disciplinary interaction related to energy efficiency and design and operation of biological wastewater treatment processes (knowledge). - The ability to evaluate and use information in the area of energy efficient wastewater treatment processes with a systematical approach (skill). - Applying the term of energy efficiency and information about processes to an existing wastewater treatment plant in order to increase the performance (skill). - Proficiency in preparing presentation and report in English (Communication and Social Competency).
562	Energy Production from Waste and Biomass		7.5	Course description: Nowadays waste disposal and renewable energy issues are becoming increasingly important issue in our country as well as in the world. Especially in order to reduce carbon dioxide emissions of fossil fuels that are taking first place among the reasons of climate change, energy production from waste and biomass are taking primacy. The master plans of our country intended to European Union are pointed out need of waste disposal and renewable energy facilities in order to achieve the objectives and goals adopted for waste and biomass combustion. Within this course master students will be familiar about waste and biomass potential, waste and biomass characterization, thermal conversion (combustion, pyrolysis, gasification) reactions, thermal conversion systems, waste recovery, pollutant (air, water, solid) generation, control of generated pollutants, ash storage and management, environmental impacts of facilities. Course objectives: 1. Be familiar about waste and biomass reserves and their utilization potential at energy production, actual utilization rates, goals stated at master plans and newest global improvements and applications.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>2. To learn of waste and biomass characterization, proximate and ultimate analyses, thermal conversion methods (combustion, pyrolysis, gasification, condensation, thermochemical biorefinery), thermal conversion reactions and energy production within new applications.</p> <p>3. To learn determination of thermal conversion system wastes emissions (solid, liquid, gas) and their legal status, control of waste, environmental impacts of thermal conversion systems within working from different engineering fields of environmental engineering and increase efficiency on making decisions.</p> <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <p>I. Students will be familiar about biomass and waste potential of our country and goals presented on master plans for waste recovery. (knowledge)</p> <p>II. Students will be familiar about thermal conversion processes (combustion, pyrolysis, gasification) and will be capable to do principal reaction calculations for system design and will be familiar about energy recovery and energy utilization applications. (Combine cycle, cogeneration). (knowledge)</p> <p>III. Students will be familiar about thermal conversion technique wastes and their control and management. They will use their knowledge at the problems on environmental engineering that they are encountered. (skill)</p> <p>IV. Students will gain the ability to create a good communication with other engineering colleagues and to write an article and prepare a presentation for evaluation of thermal systems on biomass and waste energy utilization. (Communication and social competence)</p>
563	Treatment of Industrial Wastewaters by Nano catalysts		7.5	<p>Course description: Nanotechnology is regarded as the technology revolution of the 21st. Century and also plays a major role in the solution of problems encountered in the treatment of industrial wastewater. Within the scope of this course, graduate students will gain knowledge in subjects including structural features of nano catalysts, synthesis and characterization, environmental impacts, recent applications in industrial wastewater treatment, performance and economic analysis.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> To gain knowledge about recent developments and innovative applications of nano catalytic treatment processes in wastewater treatment Be familiar with the preparation/synthesis method and impacts of nano catalysts, state-of-the-art of nano catalytic treatment processes To communicate successfully in the area of nanoscience and nanotechnology interfacing with environmental chemistry, industrial wastewater treatment and environmental engineering <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Students will gain knowledge in the application of nano catalytic treatment processes for industrial pollutants (knowledge). Students will gain knowledge about the recent developments in nanomaterials and nano catalytic processes used for industrial wastewater treatment (knowledge). Students will be able to apply the knowledge in nanoscience and nanotechnology to solve problems related with industrial wastewater treatment (skill). Students will learn to prepare oral presentations and review papers related with the application of nano catalytic processes for industrial wastewater treatment (communication and social competence).

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
564	Microalgae Applications with Biorefinery Approach		7.5	<p>Course description: In this course, the fundamentals of microalgae systems are discussed. The basics of the microbiology and classes of microalgae are covered. Applications and design of microalgae systems, energy analysis and introductory economics are also covered. As a source of cheap feedstock for a wide range of applications (nutrition, animal food, biofuels, nutraceuticals, pigments etc.) are explained in detail. Moreover, genetic engineering of microalgae will be covered for explaining the production of value-added ingredients. Also, by examining the large-scale applications of microalgae, the future of microalgae world will be discussed.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General information about microalgae microbiology. 2. Provision of the necessary information about the proper conditions of microalgae production 3. Examining the application of microalgal biotechnology 4. Improvement of basic laboratory skills related to microalgae production. 5. Demonstration of large-scale work of microalgae globally. <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. be able to describe the basic concepts of algal biology and ecology, II. be able to identify the role algae play in critical environmental issues, such as eutrophication, and algal toxins III. be able to design photobioreactor for algal biomass production IV. be able to describe the basic applications of algae in biotechnology, such as the production of food, chemicals, and biofuels. V. be able to have algal laboratory experience for their further studies. VI. be able to understand biorefinery understanding about microalgae.
565	Environmental Risk Assessment for Hazardous Materials		7.5	<p>Course description: Overview of hazardous materials. The Properties of Hazardous Materials. Toxicology and Hazardous Materials. The Classification of Hazardous Materials. The Regulatory Implicit of Hazardous Materials. Risk management in engineering. Introduction to Environmental Risk Assessment. Environmental Risk Assessment methodologies. Fuzzy logic, AHP and FAHP. The Disciplinary Interactions on Environmental Risk and Impact Assessment. Environmental Effects of Hazardous Material Spills. Environmental Risk Assessment Modeling within EIA. Case studies and special topics.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are able to define and designate to control the all factors covering environmental risk, hazard and pollution base for TMs and their derivatives. - risk criteria and environmental fate. - are able to assess TMs with a systematic approach including classification, to determine the hazard and risk criteria and environmental fate. - are able to prepare an emergency action plan including prevention, cobatting and remediation facilities according to risk assessment of HMs. - are able to use this information based on self-confidence, creativity and ethical responsibilities. <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about the definitions of constituents related management of TMs, to control of TMs including information about all

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>factors and design criteria.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about the classification, inventory, control methodologies, legal framework and assessment on TMs. - Learn about to develop the appropriate prevention, control methodology and risk management information. - Learn about the control of TMs at source, environmental management system (EMS) and control methods based on risk characterization. - Learn about the modelling of appropriate management of TMs, conceptual design and determination of the criteria - Learn about the standardization with environmental risk assessment concept and legal aspects for decision makers - Learn about the preparing of suitable proposal project in their professional future <p>Learn about the monitoring of existing safety systems, modification and auditing</p>
566	Fate and Transport of Pollutants in the Environment	Spring	7.5	<p>Course description: Pollutant characteristics, transformation processes: sedimentation, partitioning, partitioning in different phases and organic tissues, elimination, biomagnification, redox reactions, photolysis, biodegradation, hydrolysis, pKa and Kow estimation, ionization, complexation, fate of pesticides and mercury, transport mechanisms, mathematical expressions for the diffusive and advective transport of pollutants, turbulent diffusion and dispersion in rivers, transport mechanisms in the subsurface environment, soil-pollutant interactions, atmospheric transport mechanisms.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Properties of pollutants and how these properties affect their fate in the environment - Pollutant transformation processes <p>Transport mechanisms and their mathematical expressions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applications of diffusive, advective transport, turbulent diffusion and dispersion in the environment, calculations of the pollutant concentration profiles - Soil and pollutant interactions and their effect on the transport properties <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Properties of pollutants (knowledge) - Transformation processes that affect the pollutants (knowledge) - Assessment of the fate of pollutants in the environment (skill) - Transport by diffusion, mathematical expression and its solution, applications, (knowledge, skill) - Advective transport, mathematical expression and its solution, applications, (knowledge, skill) - Turbulent diffusion and dispersion in the environment, mathematical expression and its solution, applications, (knowledge, skill), kinetic expressions for chemical, physical and biological transformations (knowledge) - Transport mechanisms and behaviour of pollutants in the subsurface environment, calculation of the concentration profiles, (knowledge, skill) - Prediction and calculation of the dispersion coefficients and pollutant concentration profiles in the atmospheric environment (knowledge, skill)
567	Advances in Biological Processes and Treatment		7.5	<p>Course description: Suspended Growth Systems; Attached Growth Systems; Biological Nutrient Removal Processes; Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) Technology; Integrated Fluidized Fixed Film/ Activated Sludge (IFAS); Membrane Bioreactors; New Technology for Biological Nitrogen Removal: CANON, SHARON, ANAMMOX; Sludge Minimization and its Applications; Bioremediation Applications; Integration of Chemical and Biological Oxidation Processes; Modelling of Activated Sludge Processes.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General properties of advanced biological treatment processes - Application of advanced biological treatment processes and modeling - Innovative technologies in advanced biological treatment processes <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing and intensifying knowledge in advanced biological treatment processes (knowledge). - The ability to evaluate and use information gathered from scientific studies and applications related with advanced biological treatment processes (skill). - The ability to evaluate information about principles and applications of advanced biological treatment processes and innovative technologies (skill). - Preparing a presentation in English about applications of advanced biological treatment processes (Communication and Social Competency).
568	Solid Waste Recycling and Treatment Technologies		7.5	<p>Course description:</p> <p>Characteristics of solid waste. Collection and transport of solid waste. Recycling. Biological treatment of solid waste. Land filling. Rehabilitation of old landfills. Construction and debris waste management. Medical waste management. Special waste management. Thermal conversion technologies of solid wastes. Fundamentals of hazardous waste management. Hazardous waste management practices. Treatment and disposal methods of hazardous wastes. Hazardous waste regulations.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Principles of solid and hazardous waste management. - Treatment and disposal methods of solid and hazardous wastes - Construction and debris waste management, medical waste management, special waste management. <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing and intensifying knowledge in solid and hazardous waste management (knowledge). - The ability to use the expert-level theoretical and practical knowledge acquired in solid and hazardous waste management area (skill). - The ability to carry out a specialistic study related to solid and hazardous waste management area independently. (Competence to work independently and take responsibility). - Assessing the specialistic knowledge and skill gained through solid and hazardous waste management area with a critical view and directing one's own learning process (Learning Competence).
569	Aquatic Chemistry			<p>Course description:</p> <p>Thermodynamic basis of chemical equilibrium; Structure of water and solvent properties; Acid and base chemistry, definitions, equilibrium solutions; Applications of acid and base chemistry: pC-pH diagrams; titration, buffer intensity; Coordination chemistry and complex compounds; Precipitation and dissolution; Crystallization: equilibrium solutions, phase diagrams; Oxidation and reduction: definition and basic concepts, oxidation and reduction diagrams, equilibrium solutions</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To introduce basic thermodynamic concepts and equilibrium chemistry and structure of water

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To define basic concepts and reactions of acids-bases, complexed compounds, precipitation-dissolution and oxidation-reduction - To provide information and examples of application aspects of equilibrium chemistry <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermodynamic basis of chemical equilibrium, structure of water, solvent properties of water (knowledge) - Acids and bases, concepts, definitions, equilibrium composition, application aspects of acids and bases, pC-pH diagrams, titration, buffer index (knowledge) - Computer aided solutions to equilibrium chemistry (skill) - Coordination chemistry, complex compounds and their equilibrium chemistry (knowledge) - Precipitation-dissolution, concepts, crystallization, equilibrium composition, phase diagrams (knowledge) - Oxidation-reduction, concepts, oxidation-reduction equilibria and oxidation-reduction diagrams (skill)
570	Waste Minimization, Recycling and Cleaner Technologies		7.5	<p>Course description: Sustainable production, end-of-pipe treatment versus in-plant control, cleaner technologies, waste minimization, recovery and recycling, substitution of auxiliaries, systems for sorting of chemicals, green production, eco-efficiency, eco-labelling, rebound effect, waste management strategies in cleaner production, sustainable production for developing countries, case studies such as textile, pesticide, food, pulp and paper, polymer production sectors.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clean technologies, waste minimization, recovery and recycling alternatives within the frame of sustainable production - Systems for sorting of chemicals, green production, eco-efficiency, eco-labelling, rebound effect, - Waste management strategies aiming clean production, sustainable production for developing countries <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing and intensifying knowledge in cleaner technologies, waste minimization, recovery and recycling alternatives, systems for sorting of chemicals, green production, eco-efficiency, eco-labelling, rebound effect (knowledge). - The ability to evaluate and use information gathered from scientific literature related to cleaner technologies, waste minimization, recovery and recycling (skill). - The ability to analyze, synthesize and evaluate information about principles and applications of waste management strategies aiming cleaner production (skill). - Preparing a presentation and report in English (Communication and Social Competency).
571	Specialization Field Course			<p>Course description: Investigation on study fields and developments on these study fields as well as following scientific publications of all students, under the supervision of an advisor, who are progressing their M.Sc. thesis.</p> <p>Course objectives: Evaluations and discussions of the new developments and articles in the study fields of the students who are progressing their M.Sc. / Ph.D. thesis.</p> <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solving the problems faced in the area by making use of the research methods.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessing the specialistic knowledge and skill gained through the study with a critical view and directing one's own learning process. - The ability to critically analyze, synthesize and evaluate the new and complex ideas. - Developing and intensifying knowledge in the related program's area, based upon the competency in the undergraduate level.
572	Advances in Industrial Pollution Control		7.5	<p>Course description: Review of basic concepts of industrial pollution control; The impact of industrial pollution on the environment; Micropollutants and their regulation EPA and EU approaches; Risk assessment and environmental management systems and standards; Labelling and other international measures; Discharge standards and pre-treatment standards; BAT concept and its applications; IPPC approach of EU; Case study examples</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To introduce basic concept of industrial pollution control - To review industrial pollution control approaches and regulatory framework - To provide information on risk assessment, environmental management, labelling and discharge standard setting approaches - To introduce integrated pollution control concept, best available technology (BAT) and IPPC applications - To provide case study examples to explain and strengthen the conceptual approaches <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Basic concepts of industrial pollution (knowledge) - Evaluation of the impact of industrial pollution on the environment and micropollutants (knowledge) - Risk assessment, environmental management in industrial systems (knowledge) - Life-cycle analysis concept and applications, sustainability (knowledge) - Discharge standards and regulatory framework (knowledge) - Integrated pollution prevention systematics (skill; communication and social competency)
573	Anaerobic Treatment for Industrial and Municipal Wastewaters		7.5	<p>Course description: Fundamentals of anaerobic biochemical treatment process; reactor or system types used in anaerobic treatment; Biogas production; Energy recovery potential; Modeling of process kinetics and anaerobic treatment; Treatment of purification studies; Design and operation of conventional airless sludge decayers; Design and operation of high-speed anaerobic reactor systems; Anaerobic treatment of domestic wastewater; concept and applications together.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To introduce fundamentals of anaerobic biochemical treatment, - To introduce modelling of anaerobic systems and methods for obtaining necessary data, - To introduce biogas production technologies in order to design and define the appropriate operational conditions for different kinds of wastewater streams. <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fundamentals of anaerobic treatment process, - Basic characteristics of different anaerobic treatment systems,

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The methods used for modeling of anaerobic processes and for obtaining the necessary data, - Design and operation of sludge digesters, - Design and operation of high-rate anaerobic bioreactors used for wastewater treatment, - Design and operation of anaerobic systems used for the treatment of domestic wastewaters, - Select the appropriate systems which allow different waste streams to be co-digested, - Determine the most suitable waste/wastewater management among different anaerobic treatment options.
574	Special Waste Management		7.5	<p>Course description: Integrated waste management, medical waste management, management of waste electrical and electronic equipment, management of end-of-life vehicles and scrap tires, construction and demolition wastes management, used oil management.</p> <p>Course objectives: Principles related to Special Wastes, Management of Special Wastes.</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing and intensifying knowledge in special waste management (knowledge). - The ability to use the expert-level theoretical and practical knowledge acquired in special waste management (skill). - The ability to carry out a specialistic study related to special waste management independently. (Competence to work independently and take responsibility). - Assessing the specialistic knowledge and skill gained through special waste management area with a critical view and directing one's own learning process (Learning Competence). </p>
575	Soil Pollution: Processes and Dynamics		7.5	<p>Course description: The structure and classification of soil; the soil as a porous medium: the solid, liquid and gaseous phases of soil; soil biota; pollutants - soil solution interactions; volatilization into the soil atmosphere; retention of pollutants on and within the soil solid phase; pollutant behaviour in soils: reversible and irreversible retention - release and bound residues; transformation and metabolite formation; pollutants transport in the soil medium; modeling the fate of pollutants in the soil.</p> <p>Course objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The purpose of the course is to give the students a scientific background to solve the problems related with soil pollution - The purpose of the course is to give the students a scientific background to solve the problems related with soil pollution </p> <p>Course learning outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To describe and classify the soils - To analyze the fate of pollutants through the soils - To analyze the transformation of pollutants through the soils - To make modelling the movement and fate of pollutants through the soils </p>
576	Hazardous Waste Management: Treatment and Disposal		7.5	<p>Course description: Hazardous waste perspective. Hazardous waste and materials. Sources and generators of HW. Hazardous waste management, determination, listing. Treatment, storage and disposal, T/S/D methods and processes. Hazardous waste minimization, reuse and recycling. In situ and on-site applications of hazardous waste. Transportation of hazardous wastes.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Stabilization/Solidification Process. Hazardous waste site and remediation. Law and regulations. Case studies.</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are able to define and designate the all factors covering waste management and constituents requirements based on environmental pollution control. - are able to analysis the hazardous wastes with a systematic approach including designation step of HW by sources, hazard criteria and composition. - are able to design systems of remediation, treatment and disposal. Application to waste management systematic and improvement of listing methods. - are able to use this information based on self-confidence, creativity and ethical responsibilities. <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about the definitions, pollution sources, criteria of pollution profile of industrial systems and constituents; - Learn about the industrial categorization, control methodologies, legal framework and assessment; - Learn about the basic systematic approach to industry with methodology of process survey, mass balance and waste survey - Learn about the EMS and control methods based on industrial pollution sources, waste and risk management - Learn about the system design for best practical treatment of the wastes, their conceptual design and criteria - Learn about the pre-treatment concept, Standard improvement and legal aspects for decision makers - Learn about the monitoring of existing treatment systems, modification and auditing - Learn about the preparing of suitable proposal project in their professional future
577	Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) for Environmental Activities		7.5	<p>Course description: Introduction to Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). MCDA Methods – AHP/ANP. MCDA Methods – ELECTRE/TOPSIS/PROMETHEE. Uncertainties in Environmental Systems and Fuzzy Logic. MCDA Applications for Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA). MCDA Applications for Waste Management. MCDA Applications for Sustainable Energy Alternatives. MCDA and Environmental Policy Making. Case Study – Environmental Risk Assessment. – Integration of Site Selection with EIA Process – Decision Support for Energy Policy</p> <p>Course objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main aim of the course is to teach multiple criteria analysis (MCDA) which is focused on main factors and environmental parameters for solving of conflictions and problems at decision making step to environmental activities and systems. - It is aimed to teach most widely used methods such as Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP), Analytical Network Process (ANP), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in framework of MCDA and Environmental Risk assessment (ERA) and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). - Conflict on big projects such as planning of watershed, power stations, mining, integrated enterprises, highways, bridges and dams can be solved. - An EMS algorithm based on ERA and EIA results will also be given to students in the course. <p>Course learning outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). MCDA Methods - AHP/ANP. MCDA Methods. - Uncertainties in Environmental Systems and Fuzzy Logic. - MCDA Applications for Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA). MCDA Applications for Environmental Impact Assessment

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				(EIA). - MCDA Applications for Site Selection of Treatment Facilities. MCDA Applications for Integrated Watershed Management (IWM). MCDA Applications for Waste Management. MCDA Applications for Sustainable Energy Alternatives. - MCDA and Environmental Policy Making. Case Study – Environmental Risk Assessment. Case Study – Integration of Site Selection with EIA Process. - Case Study – Decision Support for Energy Policy
578	Chemical Treatment of Industrial Wastewater		7.5	Course description: This laboratory-based course involves undertaking a series of experimental studies which will introduce the students to the principles of chemical treatment technologies for industrial wastewaters. With over 10 weeks of laboratory work, the students will gain an in-depth understanding of the practice and operational experience in chemical treatment technologies and the student will strengthen the theoretical background of these technologies. Course objectives: - To enable the student to identify the treatability-oriented characteristics of different industrial wastewaters and to perform essential analyses relevant to wastewater pollutant parameters, - To advance the students' abilities in applying chemical treatment technologies for industrial wastewater treatment. - To improve the students' teamwork skills through group laboratory assignments and presentations. Course learning outcomes: - Students will gain knowledge in the application of chemical technologies for industrial wastewater treatment (knowledge). - Students will be able to apply this knowledge to solve problems in industrial wastewater treatment (skill). - Students will use research methods learned in this class to solve the problems in industrial wastewater treatment (skill). - Students will learn to write reports and prepare oral presentations related with the application of chemical technologies for industrial wastewater treatment (communication and social competence).
579	Management of Aquatic Ecosystems		7.5	Course description: Aquatic ecosystems (Lakes, Streams, Groundwater, Wetlands, Estuaries and lagoons, Marine ecosystems) Decision making, Decision support system tools (Monitoring, modelling, databases and Geographical Information Systems), Integrated water resources management, Contribution of water resources to natural capital and ecosystem goods and services, Impacts of climate change, National and international case studies Course objectives: - Introducing aquatic ecosystems and gaining expertise on the solution of related environmental problems - Providing the necessary requirements and abilities for the integrated water resources management Course learning outcomes: - Fundamentals of water management - Comprehending general characteristics and vulnerabilities of aquatic ecosystems and solving related problems. - Comprehending the fundamentals of decision-making process and integrated water resources management - Utilizing of decision support system tools - Awareness on the contemporary issues about aquatic ecosystems management

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
580	Industrial Ecology and Sustainable Engineering		7.5	<p>Course description: Biological and Industrial Ecosystems, Metabolic Analysis, Industrial Symbiosis, Anthropogenic Resource Cycles, Energy and Water in Industrial Ecology, Buildings and Infrastructure as Products, Urban Ecology and Urban Metabolism, Material Flows of National Economies, Modeling in Industrial Ecology, Scenario Development, The Status of Resources, Industrial Ecology in Developing Countries, The Future of Industrial Ecology</p> <p>Course objectives: - Advanced knowledge of industrial ecology and sustainable engineering (information) - To demonstrate the relationships among production, consumption, sustainability, and industrial ecology - To show how industrial ecology serves as a framework for the consideration of environmental and sustainability-related aspects of science and technology - To define and describe tools, applications, and implications of industrial ecology.</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: I. Developing and intensifying knowledge in industrial ecology and sustainable engineering (knowledge). II. The ability to evaluate and use information gathered from scientific literature related to industrial ecology and sustainable engineering (skill). III. The ability to analyze, synthesize and evaluate information about principles and applications of industrial ecology (skill). IV. Preparing a presentation and report in English (Communication and Social Competency).</p>
581	Nutrient and Water Cycles in Circular Economy			<p>Course description: Definition, importance and scope of natural water and nutrient cycle, Investigation of urban water cycle from a sustainable point of view, Water conservation and reuse in industry and agriculture, Social, economic, regulatory, environmental and technological dimensions of wastewater recovery reuse, Resource recovery from wastewater, Paradigm shift from nutrient removal from conventional perspective to nutrient recovery from resource recovery perspective, Recovery techniques of nutrients, Role of water and resource recovery in circular economy</p> <p>Course objectives: - Definition and importance of sustainability concept in water cycle - Environmental, socio-economic, and technological dimensions of wastewater recovery and reuse - Resource and nutrient recovery technologies for wastewaters - Role of water and resource recovery in circular economy - Definition and importance of sustainability concept in water cycle - Environmental, socio-economic, and technological dimensions of wastewater recovery and reuse - Resource and nutrient recovery technologies for wastewaters - Role of water and resource recovery in circular economy</p> <p>Course learning outcomes: - Having the current and high-level knowledge in the area of water and resource recovery from wastewaters (knowledge). - Grasping the inter-disciplinary interaction related to sustainability, circular economy and water cycle (knowledge). - The ability to evaluate and use information in the area of recovery technologies with a systematical approach (skill). - Applying the information on water and resource recovery technologies and process knowledge to an existing wastewater treatment plant (skill).</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
582	Waste Management and Renewable Energy	Specified Elective Classes:		<p>https://iesc.bogazici.edu.tr/content/urban-waste-management-and-renewable-energy-w2e Urban Waste Management and Renewable Energy (W2E)</p> <p>Population increase, industrial development and rapid urbanization cause an increase in the quantity and diversity of the generated wastes. Furthermore, the world's limited resources are being depleted to meet human beings' increasing demands. In order to prevent global warming, environmental pollution and to conserve our limited resources for future generations, both scientific and professional community are seeking ways to dispose of industrial and urban wastes in an environmentally friendly manner and to recover resources from these wastes for further utilization. Renewable energy sources, particularly waste to energy systems, have also been emphasized more significantly during the last couple of decades as substitutes to fossil fuel sources. Therefore, more attention is now globally being directed towards management of urban wastes, subsequent recovery of resources and production of renewable energy.</p> <p>The objective of this concentration area is to introduce the fundamentals and principles of urban waste management, waste to energy practices and renewable energy systems to graduate students, with a particular focus on recovery of resources from urban and rural waste and residues, including biological production of renewable energy (bioenergy) from biomass and management of hazardous wastes.</p>
583	Pollution Control and Modeling (PCM)			<p>https://iesc.bogazici.edu.tr/content/pollution-control-and-modeling-pcm</p> <p>Pollution Control and Modeling (PCM)</p> <p>Environmental pollution is one of the most widespread and challenging problems the world is facing today. The rapid and unsustainable industrial and urban development of the past decades, along with unabated population growth, has resulted in extensive pollution of the air, water and land, leading to significant impacts on human health and the environment. Climate change is likely to further exacerbate these threats.</p> <p>Specific topics covered in this track include, exposure to pollutants, adverse impacts of pollution on the environment and human health, the fate and transport of pollutants in the environment, environmental modeling, the measurement of aquatic toxicity, and methods for environmental protection and remediation with a focus on the removal of conventional and emerging pollutants from water and wastewater by physiochemical and biological processes. Both field/laboratory investigations and numerical modeling of environmental systems are encompassed in this concentration area.</p>
584	Molecular Ecology and Microbial Biotechnology (MNM)			<p>https://iesc.bogazici.edu.tr/content/molecular-ecology-and-microbial-biotechnology-mnm</p> <p>Molecular Ecology and Microbial Biotechnology (MNM)</p> <p>Recent advancements in molecular biology now help us to differentiate organisms within three domains i.e. bacteria, archaea and eukarya, and identify evolutionary traits that result in speciation, which ultimately shapes the ecosystems. Meanwhile, anthropogenic activities greatly impact life and ecosystems at both micro and macro levels. This area covers a broad range of research topics including microbial ecology and genetics, environmental microbiology and biotechnology, conservation biology, bioinformatics, and molecular ecology and evolution.</p> <p>The objectives of this concentration area are to introduce key concepts in environmental microbiology, molecular biology and</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				genetics and use them for better understanding of natural and engineered systems, specifically the ecology and evolution of species, and the effects of environmental and geographical conditions on individual organisms, populations and communities.
585	Socio-Ecological Sustainability (SES)			<p>https://iesc.bogazici.edu.tr/content/socio-ecological-sustainability-ses</p> <p>Socio-Ecological Sustainability (SES)</p> <p>Sustainability encompasses environmental, economic and social spheres of human life. With growing material welfare and consumption of societies, pure science and engineering approaches for pollution control and resource conservation has become inadequate for creating systemic, long-term solutions to pressing sustainability problems at the climate, water, food and energy nexus. There is a growing need for creating a shared understanding of human-ecosystem interactions that should inform environmental policy and decision-making at private and public scales. The “sustainability” concentration area aims at developing fundamental knowledge and skills required for research at the science and society interface. The focus is on systems thinking and modeling, sustainability assessment at product, project and macro-economic scales, economic analysis of the resources and environment with a particular focus on learning and participatory approaches to environmental policy design.</p> <p>“Sustainability” area is an interdisciplinary program, recruiting students with undergraduate science, engineering and social science degrees who are able to demonstrate sufficient skills in quantitative and model-based inquiry, as well as social and political awareness on pressing environmental problems of our times. Area objective is to educate experts on sustainability assessment and environmental policy, acquainted with diverse socio-environmental problems such as climate change, water, food and energy security, and overconsumption of nature’s resources. Students are expected to develop strong skills in systems thinking and modeling, sustainability assessment, ecological-economic inquiry and policy design. Graduates can pursue their career in environmental policy in national and international NGO’s, private companies and public institutions in charge of environmental protection. They are expected to act as the sustainability leaders and educators in their organizations. Sustainability area provides a firm knowledge and skills base for further studies at international Ph.D. programs along similar purposes.</p>
586	Numerical Methods in Environmental Engineering	1	9	<p>Course content: Introduction to Numerical Analysis and Review of Software, Environmental Problems Involved in Linear Equations and Their Solutions (Direct and Iterative Solution Methods), Polynomial Curve Fitting and Numerical Integration Applications, Derivative Concept in Environmental Engineering, Environmental Problems Involving Ordinary Differential Equations, Population Problems, Partial Differential Equations.</p> <p>At the end of this course the student learn using numerical methods and apply them to solve environmental engineering problems.</p>
587	Sustainability	2	9	<p>Course content:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Systems concept; types and characteristics of systems. 2. Sustainability concept, scope and different sustainability definitions. 3. Sustainable mobility and infrastructure. 4. Urban sustainability.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				5. Systems analysis, environmental systems modeling. 6. Computer based system analysis. 7. Agent based modeling. 8. Monte Carlo analysis. 9. Geographical information systems and environmental management. 10. Cost-benefit analysis. Learning outcomes: 1. Will learn to examine environmental problems from a systems perspective, and 2. Develop environmental problems and solving skills with sensing environmental system analysis framework.
588	Master's Thesis	3	30	Course content: 1. Determination of the thesis subject 2. Domestic and foreign literature review on thesis subject 3. Planning of all aspects of the research 4. Development of data collection tool 5. The reliability and validity studies of data collection tool 6. Implementation of data collection tool, and assessment of findings 7. Reporting of research results Learning outcomes: 1. Review of the literature on the study 2. Organizing ability of the information based on literature, and to develop data collection tool 3. To collect research data 4. To analyse data 5. To tabulate and interpret research findings 6. To draw results from research findings, and to make recommendations 7. To prepare reports about the research, and to defend the research
589	Master's Thesis	4	30	Course content: 1. Determination of the thesis subject 2. Domestic and foreign literature review on thesis subject 3. Planning of all aspects of the research 4. Development of data collection tool 5. The reliability and validity studies of data collection tool 6. Implementation of data collection tool, and assessment of findings 7. Reporting of research results Learning outcomes: 1. Review of the literature on the study 2. Organizing ability of the information based on literature, and to develop data collection tool 3. To collect research data

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				4. To analyse data 5. To tabulate and interpret research findings 6. To draw results from research findings, and to make recommendations 7. To prepare reports about the research, and to defend the research
590	Scientific Research Techniques and Publication		5	Course content: Scientific Research and Research Process Research Design and Problem, Variables and Types, Hypothesis Development Sampling and Data Collection Tools Data Analysis and Interpretation Research Methodologies: Descriptive or Assay Method, Experimental Method Research Proposal and Report Research and Publication Ethics Concepts Scientific Validity and Reliability for Most Discussed Current Research Ethics Issues Most Frequent Infringement Cases in Research Ethics and Prevention Measures Infringement Detection, Current Available Technologies and Routes, Legal Extent Learning outcomes: - Understand the concepts of scientific research techniques and publication ethics and define the responsibilities of the researcher for ethically valid and reliable research by related scientific research techniques - Design and manage research according to scientific research and ethics requirements - Know related local and international regulations and definitions about research and publication ethics - Know definitions of plagiarism and examples, results and related methodologies towards producing plagiarism-free work
591	Environmental Applications of Biosensors			https://akts.hacettepe.edu.tr/ders_detay.php?ders_ref=410c62646915763e016b7a0e93f978df&ders_kod=ENV606&zs_link=2&prg_kod=20143&submenuheader=2 Course content: -Introduction of biosensors -Selection of detection methods -Biosensor based polymerization methods and their characterization -Environmental Applications Learning outcomes: - The students will learn in detail the definition of biosensors, types of biosensors, biosensor-based polymerization methods, selection of the appropriate method and preparation and characterization methods of polymers. The course will provide the scientific background to graduate students who want to advance their knowledge in the area of environmental applications of biosensor-based detection methods. - The students will acquire the skills to apply relevant methods under research and practice settings. The students will learn to provide the knowledge and skills to select relevant techniques and research methodology. The students will be able to develop scientifically sound solutions and strategies for specific problems by adapting theoretical and practical knowledge gained through this course.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
592	Energy and Environment		10	<p>Course content:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Global and national energy use and supply 2. Thermodynamic principles of energy conversion 3. Electrical energy generation, transmission, and storage 4. Fossil and nuclear fuelled power plants 5. Renewable energy 6. Transportation and vehicle emissions 7. Environmental effects of fossil fuels 8. Climate change <p>Learning outcomes: The environmental effects of energy conversion, use and power production will be identified The relationship between the human activities and the environment in terms of global and national energy usage will be identified.</p>
593	Sustainable Basin Management		10	<p>Course content: Develop a Working Definition of Sustainability That Can Be Used to Assess Water Resources Projects, Policies and Strategies, Become Familiar With Key Water Management Concepts, Such As Integrated Water Resource Management, Examine How Cultural, Economic, Social, Political, Organizational and Institutional Factors Combine to Yield Strategies, Policies and Projects That Are Unsustainable or Sustainable, Review Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA), Benefit-Cost Analyses and Other Approaches and Tools for Ensuring The Sustainable Development and Management of Water Resources.</p> <p>Learning outcomes: The students will learn components of basin, quantities and/or magnitudes of these components, potential uses and environmental limits of the basin, impact of social factors and their effect on management, uses of measurement tools in decision making and management.</p>
594	Operation of Wastewater Treatment Plants		7	<p>Course content:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sampling of wastewater, wastewater characteristics 2. Plant control, flow measurement 3. Screen, grit chamber, primary sedimentation tanks and their operational problems 4. Trickling filters and operational problems 5. Activated sludge system, modification and operational problems 6. Stabilization Pond and operational problems 7. Sludge treatment, aerobic and anaerobic sludge digestion, thickening, dewatering processes and operational problems 8. The records for plant efficiency and maintenance <p>Learning outcomes: At the end of this course the student will be able to solve operational problems of wastewater treatment plants.</p>
595	Environmental Problems and the Turkish Coast		7	<p>Course content:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oceanographic properties of Black Sea, Mediterranean and Sea of Marmara; 2. Oceanographic properties of Strait of İstanbul and Golden Horn 3. The use of Google earth and Yandex to delineate the coastal properties

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				4. Understand and reiterate the coast side line concept specific to our coasts. 5. The possible impacts of industrial and municipal sites along coasts 6. How to react possible oil pollution events 7. How to utilize Internet sites as to tackle with coastal environmental aspect Learning outcomes: - Understand the oceanographic properties of Turkish Seas - Acquainted with the specific coastal problems of our cities and catchment areas along Turkish coastline - Students are expected to increase their knowledge about Turkish coasts and develop special environmentally sound remediation techniques as to minimize the effect of pollutants
596	Research Methods and Scientific Ethics	2	2.5	The aim of this course is to inform graduate students about the research methods used in today's technical research fields, thesis, the article and the preparation techniques and the stages of designing and preparing research projects, their presentation and the ethical issues to be considered within the framework of all these. Students who successfully complete this program have the following abilities: Learns research methods. Understand the importance of ethics in research. Learn and implement experimental research, design and reporting techniques.
597	Master's Thesis	1	40	Gaining literature scanning skills. Gaining the ability to do research. Gaining the ability to analyze and synthesis. Learning scientific methods
598	Applications of Genotoxicity in Environmental Engineering	Elective courses	7.5	It is aimed to explain the theoretical and practical topics of environmental environments (especially wetlands) to examine pollutants from a genotoxic perspective other than traditional methods, so that students have detailed knowledge about the negative effects of potential pollutants on living DNA, and to gain a new perspective in terms of Environmental Engineering applications. Gaining the ability to evaluate and interpret using the concept of neurotoxicity and engineering knowledge and skills. To learn theoretically and methodologically how polleners cause damage to genes (genotoxicity). To learn the SOS Chromotest methodology, which is one of the in-vitro test methods, and to gain the ability to compare with other methods. In terms of Environmental Engineering, how to evaluate the amplitude measurement data (with statistical and non-linear modeling) and how to interpret it. To gain an interactively involved approach skills by conducting class studies with students about various genotoxicity methodologies such as Ames Test, Mutatox, Umu Test, Vitotox.
599	Environmental Nanotechnology		7.5	Rapid developments in the field of nanoscience and nanotechnology cause a wide range of products such as electronics, pharmaceutical industry, cosmetics, textiles, automotive and food sectors. Although the developments in the field of nanotechnology have taken place very quickly, it is unfortunately not possible to talk about this rapid progress in studies on human and environmental health of nanomaterials, natural environments (water, soil, air) behaviours and interactions, and/or control of final disposal technologies and/or control. Within the scope of this course, it is aimed to determine the current situation of nanotechnology studies, to examine the availability of nanotechnology in the environment and environmental impacts, to create a scientific infrastructure related to the studies and legal regulations that should be done in the future.

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determination of the use areas of nanotechnology in daily life - Examination of the use of nanotechnology in the environmental area (water, wastewater, air) - Learning the environmental impacts of nanotechnology products - Examination of the behaviour of nanotechnology products in water, wastewater, air and solid waste environments - Examination of the toxicity of nanomaterials and its effects on health
600	Biofilters in Wastewater Treatment		7.5	<p>The role of biofilm systems formed by keeping it on a material as an alternative to suspended systems in wastewater treatment will be examined. For this purpose, biological, hydraulic and physical aspects of the system will be investigated.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning the active role in the treatment of biofilm microorganisms held on the environment as an alternative to suspended systems in wastewater treatment - Gaining design factors affecting biofilm systems by the student - The achievement of the theory of model kinetics that constitute the basis for biofilm systems - Learning of different approaches used in efficiency calculations in biofilm systems - Gaining practical applications for biofilm design - Gaining scientific article research and presentation techniques by the student
601	Advanced Chemical Methods in Wastewater Treatment		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to teach the possible treatment methods and application areas of Advanced Chemical Treatment Methods and application areas that contribute to the sustainable protection of the environment, to reuse domestic wastewater, to discharge leakage water and to remove toxicity of industrial wastewater, thus to the sustainable protection of the environment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students who take this course, Learns waste water types and characters. - Treatment of wastewater by advanced chemical oxidation methods, - Electrochemical Treatment Techniques, - Knows the potential and evaluation of purification outputs. - It can determine possible risks or efficiency.
602	Membrane Applications in Environmental Engineering		7.5	<p>General about the theory, applications and business principles of membrane technology it is aimed to create a new perspective for Environmental Engineering applications by gaining information.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To provide information about membrane use in solid-liquid and liquid-liquid separations with the theory of membrane processes. - Learning membrane preparation methods and module designs. - Evaluation of the physical, chemical and surface properties of membranes. - To learn about microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, reverse osmosis, advanced osmosis, membrane distillation, pervaporation, electrovasory and membrane bioreactors. - Identification of the advantages and disadvantages of membrane processes. - Comparison of classical treatment processes and membrane processes. - Evaluation of the economic dimension of membrane use.
603	Gas Transfer and Ventilation Systems		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to transfer the basic information about the principles of gas transfer and ventilation operations used in water and wastewater treatment and ventilation systems used in drinking water and wastewater liquidation, to provide the ability to design and operate the ventilation systems in the treatment plants</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To obtain the necessary information for the development of basic concepts and theories in ventilation applications in the treatment of water and wastewater. - Observing the functions of gas transfer and ventilation units in water and wastewater treatment and learning of physical principles related to the work of these units. - Understanding the basic principles of the design of ventilation units.
604	Pollution in Porous Environment		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to understand the ranks of presence in the porous environment of harmful chemicals, transformation and behaviour, and to teach the techniques of cleaning contaminated environments.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From the students who took this course, harmful chemicals that pollute soil and underground water, - The transport and transformations in the environment, - They are expected to know the treatment techniques that will be applied to contaminated environments.
605	Air Pollution Receptor Models		7.5	<p>To provide detailed information about the buyer environment models used in air pollution. Designing measurement campaigns for the data needs and meeting this need for receptor models To gain the ability to choose the receptor model according to the need. To gain experience with mathematical backgrounds of various receptor models. To gain the ability to modify the receptor models for the need.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to distinguish receptor models - Ability to use CMB, PCA and PMF models effectively - Ability to make appropriate modifications in receptor models - Ability to design measurement campaigns suitable for receptor models - Gain the ability to evaluate the outputs of the receptor models within the framework of legal regulations
606	Compost Production Technologies		7.5	<p>It is aimed to determine the methods to be followed during the conversion of biodegradable substances into beneficial final products by composting method, to determine the final product quality obtained by monitoring and control parameters of the compost process.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the most important contributions of this course will be the practice of laboratory applications and theoretical knowledge to be carried out. - The ability to operate compost reactors, the parameters that need to be checked during the operation and how to intervene in these parameters when necessary, will be earned by the students will be gained by one-to-one applications. - The ability to apply the analysis methods used to determine the maturity, stability and suitability of the compost to the plant and to interpret these results according to the purposes of using the compost will be gained.
607	Anaerobic Treatment Processes		7.5	<p>Learn the anaerobic disintegration, - Learning the advantages and disadvantages of anaerobic purification - Anaerobic process design and study of business information.</p> <p>Students will learn the advantages and disadvantages of anaerobic treatment and aerobic treatment. Students will learn the basic mechanisms of anaerobic fragmentation. Students will learn the design and operation principles of anaerobic treatment plants.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
608	Waste Gas Control		7.5	<p>At the end of this semester, students are expected to learn very well about absorption and adsorption, and to master these issues. It is also the objectives of this course to understand the removal of combustion gases such as sulfur oxides and nitrogen oxides that we often encounter in air pollution applications from chimney gas. The main information about burning and biofiltration as the removal methods of gas and steam pollutants will also be given, and specializing in these issues should be the main objective of the students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To have basic information on gas control in air pollution. - Recognition of gas control equipment in air pollution. - Suitable design of gas control equipment in air pollution.
609	Wastewater Biology		7.5	<p>To provide detailed knowledge about the biological components of wastewater in microbiological applications with the solution of biological problems encountered in treatment systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gaining the ability to comprehend problems that may be effective on human and public health that will be caused by environmental pollution - To provide information about measures to be taken against problems that may affect human and community health due to environmental engineering practices - Gaining engineering application skills
610	Applications of Prediction Models in Environmental Engineering		7.5	<p>To teach the concepts of mathematical modeling and validation techniques for the prediction of a specific process output, the digital data of the experimental and theoretical studies in the field of Environmental Engineering, and to teach the concepts of mathematical modeling and validation/verification techniques for the prediction of a specific process output, to transfer the current applications related to the subject to computer support to the student and to provide students with the ability to judge and modeling in solving the basic problems encountered in Environmental Engineering applications.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taking environmental measures related to output from a specific environmental process (e.g., output pollutant concentration, amount of biogas generated, treatment efficiency, etc.) - Understanding the importance of computer-aided estimation studies and gaining a different mathematical perspective, especially for academic research and graduate thesis studies - In the evaluation of economic factors related to the subject and the development of various warning systems and the mathematical identification of the said process
611	Advanced Techniques in Collapsion Pools		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to convey the basic information about the precipitation pools, precipitators and precipitation processes in the treatment process, to provide the ability to project and operate the precipitation units in the treatment plants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To provide the necessary information for the development of basic concepts and theories in precipitation applications in the treatment of water and wastewater. - Understanding the functions and working principles of precipitation units involved in water and wastewater treatment. - Understanding the basic principles of projecting of collapse units.
612	Ecosystem Modeling		7.5	<p>The aim of the course is to explain the concepts of system and ecosystems, to determine the factors that make up ecosystems and to model natural ecosystems. In addition, soil erosion, modeling of pastures and forests, streaming and lake modeling, thinning ozone layer, and modeling of special ecosystems selected after revealing the basic modeling criteria for acid rains.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students taking the course; Basic features of the concept of ecosystem,

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grouping of ecological factors, - Basic principles of modeling, - Basic principles of ecosystem modeling, - Modeling principles of natural ecosystems, - Determining the parameters to be used in ecosystem modeling, - Principles of lake and river modeling, - They'll learn how to model soil erosion.
613	Filtration		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to convey the basic knowledge about the filters and filtration theory used in water and wastewater treatment, to provide the ability to design and operate the filtration units in the treatment plants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning the necessary information for the development of basic concepts and theories in filtration applications in the treatment of water and wastewater. - Comprehension of the functions of filtration units in water and wastewater treatment, taking physical principles related to the work of these units. - Understanding the basic principles of projection of filtration units.
614	Air Pollution Particle Control		7.5	<p>At the end of this semester, students will have learned about the distribution functions of the particular substances, the log-normal distribution and its properties, the precipitation and retention mechanisms of the particles, and the basic modeling approaches in air pollution control. It is the purpose of this course to teach the structure and working principles of cyclones used for dust removal control in air pollution control. The objectives of the students should be to specialize in this and to have the knowledge and experience to design a cyclone system if such a need is available. The main information about the structure and working principles of wet purifiers, bag filters and electrofilters used for the purpose of holding dust are among the objectives of this course.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Getting basic information about Particles in Air Pollution. - Recognition of Air Pollution Particle Control equipment. - Proper design of Particle Control equipment in Air Pollution.
615	Effects of Air Pollution on Plants		7.5	<p>To teach with all aspects by giving examples of the effects of air pollution on plants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students taking the course; Basic principles of air pollution, - Factors affecting the damages of air pollution on plants, - How the harmful effects of air pollutants on plants occur, phytotoxic effect mechanisms of air pollutants, - The latest researches and results on this subject, - The effect of sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, ozone and other pollutants on their plants - Learns to Monitor the Change/transaction of Air Pollutants with Plants.
616	Solid Waste Storage Techniques		7.5	<p>Field selection of solid waste storage, time-related changes phases in the storage area, solid waste mass balance in storage area, storage area floor impermeability system design, system design for the collection of gases to be formed, storage area top cover design to be closed, leakage water quantity estimate, warehouse gas collection system design, warehouse gas collection system design, warehouse gas collection system design, storage gas energy calculations, leakage water treatment requirement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gain the ability to decide on Solid Waste Storage Site Location Selection with the help of analytical hierarchy from multi-criteria decision-making techniques - Design Leakage Water Drainage and Treatment Systems - Warehouse Gas (Biogas) Production Cal Account Basics, Gaining Sizing Ability

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designing Base and Ceiling Sealing Systems - Understanding Rehabilitation of Old Warehouse Fields
617	Energy and Substance Acquisition from Solid Waste		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to introduce the theoretical and applied topics related to Waste Resources, and Economic Values, Recovery and Transformation Technologies systems. The cost and methods to be used for the economy of recovery and transformation technologies will be explained in the course. Energy acquisition and balance sheet from solid wastes will be given separately</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students are expected to have a basic understanding and know-how on existing technologies, and energy acquisition and savings after taking this course - Calculate energy acquisition and balance sheet from solid waste - Recycling and Transformation Technology systems will have applied topics.
618	Chemical Microbiology		7.5	<p>Learning the basic topics associated with chemistry of microbiology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students taking the course; Biosynthesis, Biological Molecules, Metabolism, Biopolymer Synthesis, Metabolic Cycles, DNA and RNA Genetic Mechanism - Enzymes, Enzyme Kinetics, Michaelis-Menten Kinetics, Enzyme Inhibition and Effects of pH and Temperature - They will learn about Growth Kinetics, Chemostat Cultures and Growth Inhibition and Features of Continuous Cultures.
619	Bioremediation of Polluted Environments		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to introduce, transfer and disseminate scientific and technological knowledge and research-practices in the world in order to increase the quality of soil and water environments that are difficult to remove with biological and advanced treatment methods and polluted by permanent pollution, without creating new wastes, with methods that are compatible with the environment and support spontaneous reactions by natural means, and to make them ready for reuse.</p> <p>Learning the methods of confinement of pollution in contaminated environments that cannot be transported.</p> <p>Implementation of treatment processes to be carried out according to the type of pollution in large water bodies and soil soils.</p> <p>Application of high-tech methods for the removal of persistent impurities.</p>
620	Special and Hazardous Waste		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to introduce the theoretical and practical issues related to the collection, transportation, recovery and disposal of special and hazardous wastes.</p> <p>To be able to classify Special and Hazardous Wastes</p> <p>Management of special and hazardous wastes and have a basic understanding and knowledge</p> <p>Knowledge of current technologies and treatment methods</p> <p>Knowledge about the legal status of Special and Hazardous Wastes in our country and in the world</p> <p>Knowledge of the sources and production status, collection, storage, transportation and disposal practices of Special and Hazardous Wastes.</p>
621	Global Climate Change		7.5	<p>Defining the energy system that balances climate dynamics on a global scale and learning and studying anthropogenic and natural effects and global climate change.</p> <p>Acquisition of basic knowledge about the climate system</p> <p>Learning about the effects of greenhouse gases and aerosols on the climate</p> <p>Learning about the effects of anthropogenic and natural emissions on the climate</p> <p>Learning about the effects of climate change</p> <p>Learning greenhouse gas reduction methods</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
622	Microplastic Pollution and Control		7.5	<p>At the end of this course, students are expected to learn the control and removal methods in order to identify microplastic pollution in water resources on a global scale and to minimize the threat posed by microplastics to aquatic ecosystems.</p> <p>Acquires general information about the formation processes of microplastics.</p> <p>Learn the effects of microplastics on living things in aquatic environments.</p> <p>Learn the effects of microplastics in terms of transport of persistent organic pollutants and heavy metals.</p> <p>Learns the hydrodynamic transport of microplastics and their contribution to global pollution.</p> <p>Learns the control of microplastics and their removal from the aquatic environment.</p>
623	Reuse of Wastewater		7.5	<p>Learning the reuse areas and usage conditions of treated wastewater in order to ensure efficient use of water resources</p> <p>Obtaining information about the status of water resources in Turkey and the world</p> <p>Learning the formation, properties and treatment methods of wastewater</p> <p>Understanding the rationale for treatment and the rationale for water reuse</p> <p>Learning the reuse areas of treated wastewater</p> <p>Understanding the standards required for the reuse of treated wastewater</p> <p>Preparation of project examples for the reuse of wastewater</p>
624	Environmental Sustainability and Circular Economy		7.5	<p>To master the terminology related to sustainable environment and circular economy.</p> <p>To gain knowledge on global and national regulations and policies related to environmental sustainability.</p> <p>To comprehend the relationship between circular water, waste, and resource management and sustainable environment.</p> <p>To learn to analyze problems related to the environment and sustainability.</p> <p>To gain the ability to think critically about the subject, to write and present scientific reports.</p>
625	Active Mud Modeling		7.5	<p>Learning and examining the simulation of activated sludge processes, which are widely used in biological wastewater treatment, mainly physical, chemical and biochemical processes, with biochemical mathematical models</p> <p>Students will gain knowledge of the simulation of full-mix and piston flow reactors.</p> <p>Students will learn techniques for physical precipitation processes and modeling multivariate systems.</p> <p>Students will learn the use of MS Excel-based and open source bioXL3 and bioXL3p software developed by the instructors of the course.</p>
626	Environmental Biotechnology		7.5	<p>To comprehend the applications of microbial ecology and biotechnology in the field of Environmental Technology</p> <p>Learning new biotechnological applications in Environmental Engineering and treatment technologies</p> <p>To have knowledge about the importance of biotechnology in reducing environmental problems and determining its contributions.</p> <p>Using the methods used in biotechnology, understanding the importance of bioethics and biosafety issues in biotechnology.</p>
627	Pollution Flood Processes		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to provide an understanding of the physical, chemical and biological processes that govern the distribution of pollutants in the environment and the transformation and degradation of a pollutant during these processes. Knowledge of these processes is very important for designing pollution prevention, control, monitoring and remediation strategies and risk assessment.</p> <p>Upon successful completion of this program, students will be able to: Learns the convection and fate of pollutants in water, soil, sediment and air environments.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
				<p>Comprehend the basic principles of transport processes. Learn the physical, chemical and biological processes that govern the distribution of pollutants in the environment.</p>
628	Waste Management Technologies		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to provide basic training to environmental engineers in detail on the most important points of waste management. In the course, the most appropriate treatment methods to be applied in the conditions of our country and the necessary issues for these applications to be successful will be explained. After taking this course, students are expected to have a basic understanding and knowledge of issues such as determining the most appropriate treatment and waste management method according to local conditions and knowing the methods to be considered in operating conditions.</p> <p>Gaining the ability to choose the most appropriate waste management system according to local conditions. Obtaining information about improving operating conditions in waste management. Practices related to the reuse of waste.</p>
629	Optimization Applications in Environmental Engineering		7.5	<p>The aim of this course is to introduce the theoretical and practical issues related to optimization techniques and models used in environmental engineering. It is to provide students with the understanding of Linear Programming and Dynamic Programming, which are used in optimization applications included in the planning of mathematical modeling.</p> <p>After taking this course, students will be able to identify and define current Environmental Engineering optimization problems For this purpose, it selects appropriate analytical methods and modeling techniques Designs under realistic constraints to meet desired requirements Environmental Engineering formulates optimization problems Applies the most appropriate design methods in line with constraints</p>
630	Air Pollution Dispersion Models		7.5	<p>To provide detailed information about the modeling of short-distance transport of air pollutants released into the atmosphere, Elaboration of a basic atmospheric dispersion model: Gaussian Dispersion, Investigation of the effects of atmospheric conditions on dispersion, Giving the concepts of limit values and average values in legal regulations, A computer program: ISC3, Gaining the ability to interpret model results.</p> <p>Gaining the ability to distinguish atmospheric pollution patterns, Gaining the ability to use the ISC3 dispersion model effectively, Running an air pollution model for industrial needs and gaining the power to interpret the results according to the relevant regulations</p>
631	Water Chemistry		7.5	<p>The main objectives of this course are: Physical and chemical properties of water, Determining and evaluating the quality and composition of water, Explanation of reactions occurring in the aquatic environment as contamination and treatment mechanisms, The amount of change, transformation and transport of pollutant forms and species through the Chemical Equilibrium, to teach how to calculate possible risks and yields.</p> <p>Students will learn about the physical and chemical properties of water, Knows the nature of chemical reactions that occur in water. Describe and discuss aquatic environment behaviours such as acid-base, dissolution-precipitation, oxidation-reduction through Chemical Kinetics and Chemical Equilibrium. It can determine the composition of water through electroneutrality. It can calculate the risk of possible contamination and toxicity with complex water reactions and the treatment efficiency.</p>

#	Title of the courses	Semester	ECTS	Outcomes and competencies
632	Environmental Risk Management		7.5	Environmental risk assessment and ensuring that ecological elements related to the human environment can be secured. Establishing the concept of ecological risk for human beings and their natural environment. Understanding of risk analysis methods. Learning risk management techniques.

Appendix 3

PART C – Distribution of the course subjects

#	Country	Institution	Engineering Sciences	Natural and Earth Sciences	Physical and Mathematical Sciences	Social and Policy Sciences	Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields	Supervised learning experience
1	Austria	Technical University of Wien	42	25	17	0	8	25
2	Belgium	Ghent University	15	23	18	9	8	27
3	Belgium	University of Antwerp	15	15	5	25	15	0
4	Belgium	Univesrite libre de Bruxelles	0	17	12	12	38	21
5	Czech Republic	University of Chemistry and Technology	30	20	10	5	10	20
6	Denmark	Technical university of Denmark	20	35	25	10	5	5
7	Denmark	University of Copenhagen	20	55	5	10	5	5
8	Denmark	Aarhus University	20	40	10	5	5	20
9	Denmark	Aalborg University	30	40	5	10	5	10
10	Denmark	University of Southern Denmark	30	40	5	5	10	10
11	Estonia	Tallinn University of Technology	20	30	10	5	10	25
12	Finland	Aalto University	35	25	15	10	5	10
13	Finland	University of Oulu	30	30	15	10	5	10
14	Finland	Tampere University	35	25	15	10	10	5
15	Finland	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology LUT	40	25	15	10	10	5
16	Finland	University of Eastern Finland	30	25	15	10	15	5
17	France	École Polytechnique de Paris	35	35	0	15	15	0
18	France	Université de Poitiers - ENSIP	45	0	15	10	15	10
19	France	INSA Toulouse	40	20	15	10	10	5
20	Germany	Leibniz University Hannover	40	20	15	10	10	5

#	Country	Institution	Engineering Sciences	Natural and Earth Sciences	Physical and Mathematical Sciences	Social and Policy Sciences	Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields	Supervised learning experience
21	Germany	Technical University of Munich	35	20	15	10	10	10
22	Germany	KIT, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	40	20	15	10	10	5
23	Germany	Universität Hamburg	40	20	15	10	10	5
24	Germany	Universität Stuttgart (Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering)	40	20	15	10	10	5
25	Germany	Universität Stuttgart (Faculty of Energy, Process and Bio-Engineering)	40	20	15	10	5	5
26	Germany	RWTH Aachen University	40	20	15	10	10	5
27	Greece	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	35	20	15	10	10	10
28	Greece	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	35	20	10	10	15	10
29	Greece	University of Crete	35	20	15	10	10	10
30	Greece	University of Patras	35	20	15	10	10	10
31	Greece	University of Ioannina	35	25	15	10	5	10
32	Ireland	Trinity College Dublin, The University of Dublin	20	35	25	10	5	5
33	Ireland	University College Cork	20	35	25	10	5	5
34	Ireland	University College Dublin	20	35	25	10	5	5
35	Ireland	University of Galway	20	35	25	10	5	5
36	Italy	Politecnico di Milano	20	35	25	10	5	5
37	Italy	Politecnico di Torino	20	35	25	10	5	5
38	Italy	Polytechnic University of Milan	20	35	25	10	5	5
39	Italy	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies – Pisa	20	35	25	10	5	5
40	Italy	Sapienza University of Rome	20	35	25	10	5	5

#	Country	Institution	Engineering Sciences	Natural and Earth Sciences	Physical and Mathematical Sciences	Social and Policy Sciences	Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields	Supervised learning experience
41	Italy	University of Bologna	20	35	25	10	5	5
42	Italy	University of Milan	20	35	25	10	5	5
43	Italy	University of Naples Federico II	20	35	25	10	5	5
44	Italy	University of Padua	20	35	25	10	5	5
45	Italy	University of Pisa	20	35	25	10	5	5
46	Italy	University of Turin	20	35	25	10	5	5
47	Italy	Università di Padova	20	35	25	10	5	5
48	Latvia	University of Latvia	20	35	25	10	5	5
49	Poland	Gdańsk University of Technology	39	9	3	11	11	27
50	Poland	Cracow University of Technology	44	10	3	3	17	22
51	Poland	Warsaw University of Technology	35	23	13	5	5	20
52	Poland	Czestochowa University of Technology	40	10	0	10	20	20
53	Portugal	University of Aveiro	25	0	0	0	35	40
54	Portugal	University of Porto	5	13.75	0	5	42.5	33.75
55	Portugal	Nova University Lisbon	5	0	0	5	57.5	32.5
56	Portugal	University of Lisbon	25	0	5	10	35	25
57	Slovakia	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU)	55	20	10	5	5	5
58	Slovakia	University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Trnava (UCM)	50	25	10	5	5	5
59	Slovenia	University of Ljubljana	60	20	10	5	3	2
60	Spain	Technical University of Madrid	60	20	10	5	3	2
61	Spain	University of Santiago de Compostela (USC)	35	30	10	10	10	5
62	Spain	University of Sevilla (US)	40	25	10	10	10	5

#	Country	Institution	Engineering Sciences	Natural and Earth Sciences	Physical and Mathematical Sciences	Social and Policy Sciences	Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields	Supervised learning experience
63	Spain	Polytechnic University of Cartagena (UPCT)	50	20	10	10	10	10
64	Spain	University of Huelva and International University of Andalucía (UNIA)	50	20	10	10	10	10
65	Spain	University of A Coruña (UDC)	35	35	10	10	10	5
66	Spain	University Rivera i Virgili (URV)	50	20	10	10	5	5
67	Spain	European University of Atlantic	50	20	10	10	5	5
68	Spain	Polytechnic University of Cataluña (UPC)	55	20	10	5	5	5
69	Sweden	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	25	0	0	0	35	40
70	Sweden	Lund University	5	13.75	0	5	42.5	33.75
71	Sweden	Chalmers University of Technology	5	0	0	5	57.5	32.5
72	Turkiye	Middle East Technical University	70	30	0	0	0	0
73	Turkiye	Istanbul Technical University	70	20	0	0	10	0
74	Turkiye	Boğaziçi University	70	30	0	0	0	0
75	Turkiye	Yıldız Technical University	80	20	0	0	0	0
76	Turkiye	Hacettepe University	80	20	0	0	0	0
69	Sweden	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	25	0	0	0	35	40
70	Sweden	Lund University	5	13.75	0	5	42.5	33.75
71	Sweden	Chalmers University of Technology	5	0	0	5	57.5	32.5
72	Turkiye	Middle East Technical University	70	30	0	0	0	0
73	Turkiye	Istanbul Technical University	70	20	0	0	10	0
74	Turkiye	Boğaziçi University	70	30	0	0	0	0

#	Country	Institution	Engineering Sciences	Natural and Earth Sciences	Physical and Mathematical Sciences	Social and Policy Sciences	Interdisciplinary and Applied Fields	Supervised learning experience
75	Turkiye	Yıldız Technical University	80	20	0	0	0	0
76	Turkiye	Hacettepe University	80	20	0	0	0	0

Appendix 3

PART D – List of good practice examples

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
University of Vienna	-	In 2023 its third party research funding reached €117.6 million (up from €107.5 million in 2022)	About one quarter of Vienna's master's programmes—such as Environmental Systems, Communication Science and Global Change & Sustainability—are taught entirely in English, requiring at least CEFR B2/C1 proficiency for admission. Roughly 2,700 exchange students arrive each year and over 30 % of academic staff come from abroad, underscoring the university's global campus profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Trace Analysis Laboratory (CeMESS) Full analytical workflow from field sampling to controlled lab experiments, featuring gas/liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole MS for organic pollutants, plus ICP OES for high throughput elemental analysis. • Accelerated Solvent Extraction Facility High temperature, high pressure extraction system for isolating organic contaminants from soils and sediments prior to chromatographic and mass spectrometric analysis. • Environmental Mass Spectrometry (EMS) Facility State of the art mass spectrometers tailored for environmental tracers down to nano and molecular scales, driving innovations in contaminant and isotope research. • Hydrogeology & Contaminant Interface Laboratory Controlled batch and column experiments using XRD, XRF, ICP MS, and XAS to elucidate mineral–metal–organic interactions governing pollutant mobility in subsurface environments. 	The University of Vienna's internal quality-assurance system has been externally audited and certified by AQ Austria for the period 2022–2029 under the Hochschul-Qualitätssicherungsgesetz, ensuring compliance with national and European standards. AQ Austria is itself an ENQA member and is registered in EQAR, reflecting its role in upholding rigorous quality benchmarks	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
Technical University of Wien	-	<p>TU Wien researchers have secured ERC Starting, Consolidator, Advanced and Proof of Concept grants, e.g. AbinitioDGA (Advanced) and BlockSec (Advanced).</p> <p>“Deciphering River Flood Change” holds an ERC Advanced Grant, and several projects (Maffei’s BlockSec, Kovács’s LEARN!) illustrate the breadth of EU funding at TU Wien</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TU Wien offers several master’s programmes entirely in English, such as Building Science & Environment and an international MSc in Cartography, requiring TOEFL/IELTS proof for non-native speakers • Over 90 % of TU Wien graduates secure employment within six months, reflecting strong alignment with industry needs and career services. Employer reputation indicators place TU Wien among the top 200 in Europe, underscoring graduate employability and institutional prestige • Master’s theses (30 ECTS) require a notification form, a 10–12-page exposé, supervisor approval, plagiarism check via TISS, and submission of bound copies to the library. Theses are publicly defended in an exhibition format, with presentation posters and printed copies, within one semester after registration 	<p>The Research & Transfer Service Unit advises on R&D contracts, patent/licence management and industry collaborations, driving application of TU Wien innovations in society. The Innovation Incubation Center (i²c) offers incubation, training and investor networking, catalyzing spin-offs and start-ups from TU Wien research</p>	<p>TU Wien’s core engineering and science programmes are accredited by ASIIN, the German-speaking accreditation body for technical degrees. Its internal Quality Management System has been certified in seven-year audits by both the Swiss Accreditation Council (2016) and AQ Austria (per the Austrian HS-QSG). Selected continuing-education courses carry the FIBAA seal, ensuring international comparability and transparency of postgraduate offerings</p>	<p>TU Wien participates in Erasmus Mundus joint-master consortia and coordinates modules across partner universities, enriching cross-border academic cooperation</p>
Ghent University	-	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participation in international projects and networks aimed at knowledge sharing and building expertise on impact (eg. ACCOMPLISSH, ENRESSH, ENLIGHT-Rise, EARMA, INORMS, ...) 2. Total research expenditure – 532,6 M€ (2023) 3. Number of publications (2020) – 8194 (Web of Science incl. VABB) 	-	-	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
		4. Number of ERC (The European Research Council) grants (projects) – 120 (since start of ERC, up to and including November 2022) 5. Number of patents – 1273 (2011-2021) Research projects: • IMPROCHARES Improving grid hosting capacity in the electrification process by combining smart truck charging applications with renewable energy sources and local hybrid storage systems. • MAVERICK Measuring, Calibrating and Validating Airborne Wind Energy System Simulation Tools in Offshore Conditions. • FISSCK Fundamental Investigation of Strength and Stiffness of Clays of the Kortrijk Formation.				
University of Antwerp	3. Joint and Double Degree Programs. The MAEH is a joint program with universities in Portugal, Poland, and Germany. The Double Degree in Sustainability Engineering allows students to study at UAntwerp and Vrije	4. Research Funding and International Projects. UAntwerp researchers have secured European Research Council (ERC) grants across various disciplines, including environmental sciences. The university participates in Horizon Europe and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, supporting postdoctoral research in environmental fields.	2. English-Taught Programs and Internationalization. UAntwerp offers several programs in English, including the MAEH and the Double Degree in Sustainability Engineering (in collaboration with Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam). Approximately 18% of UAntwerp's 21,000 students are international, representing over 136 nationalities.	-	1. International Accreditation. The Master of Applied Ecohydrology (MAEH) is an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree, co-delivered by UAntwerp and three other European universities. This program adheres to the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) standards, ensuring international recognition.	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
	Universiteit Amsterdam, combining engineering and environmental management curricula.					
University of Vienna	-	In 2023 its third party research funding reached €117.6 million (up from €107.5 million in 2022)	About one quarter of Vienna's master's programmes—such as Environmental Systems, Communication Science and Global Change & Sustainability—are taught entirely in English, requiring at least CEFR B2/C1 proficiency for admission. Roughly 2,700 exchange students arrive each year and over 30 % of academic staff come from abroad, underscoring the university's global campus profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Trace Analysis Laboratory (CeMESS) Full analytical workflow from field sampling to controlled lab experiments, featuring gas/liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole MS for organic pollutants, plus ICP OES for high throughput elemental analysis. • Accelerated Solvent Extraction Facility High temperature, high pressure extraction system for isolating organic contaminants from soils and sediments prior to chromatographic and mass spectrometric analysis. • Environmental Mass Spectrometry (EMS) Facility State of the art mass spectrometers tailored for environmental tracers down to nano and molecular scales, driving innovations in contaminant and isotope research. • Hydrogeology & Contaminant Interface Laboratory Controlled batch and column experiments using XRD, XRF, ICP MS, and XAS to elucidate mineral-metal-organic interactions governing pollutant mobility in subsurface environments. 	The University of Vienna's internal quality-assurance system has been externally audited and certified by AQ Austria for the period 2022–2029 under the Hochschul-Qualitätssicherungsgesetz, ensuring compliance with national and European standards. AQ Austria is itself an ENQA member and is registered in EQAR, reflecting its role in upholding rigorous quality benchmarks	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
Belgium	Univesrite libre de Bruxelles	-	<p>1. ULB environmental-science researchers secure an average of €4 million per year in EU/Wallonia grants. Between 2020–2023, over 15 ERC and Horizon Europe projects directly involved M-ENVIE faculty or doctoral students (e.g., “Climate-BIP,” “Aquaculture Nexus”). Each year, M-ENVIG attracts €500 k–€1 M in regional and EU funding (e.g., Interreg “GreenCity,” Erasmus+ “E-Manager”), giving students hands-on roles in project development and management.</p> <p>2. Through ULB’s Research & Innovation Service, both tracks maintain formal partnerships with over 30 environmental consultancies and NGOs (e.g., Suez Environnement, Bond Beter Leefmilieu), offering internships and case-study projects that count for up to 10 ECTS of practical credit. M-ENVIE students benefit from field-lab internships at Université Libre de Bruxelles Campus du Solbosch (soil-analysis facility, hydrology lab) and the ULB Ecotron, exposing them directly to industrial workflows in contamination assessment and bioreactor testing. M-ENVIG works closely with ULB’s Career Center and IGEAT’s Tech Transfer Office, enabling students to co-design environmental management plans with real companies (e.g., ULB spin-off “AquaSense” for water-quality solutions).</p>	<p>1. Both tracks are delivered in French and English, requiring CEFR-level proficiency (B2/C1), and attract a diverse student body (25–30 % international enrolment). All core lectures, case studies, and seminars accommodate English-speaking participants. In 2023–24, ULB hosted over 1,500 incoming exchange students (Erasmus+, bilateral agreements), many of whom enroll in M-ENVIE/M-ENVIG modules taught in English.</p> <p>2. Admission requires a Bachelor’s degree in Sciences, Engineering, or Economics (180 ECTS), plus proof of French B2 (DELFB2) and/or English B2 (TOEFL iBT 80 or IELTS 6.5). Applications include a 2-page research proposal and two academic recommendations. Both tracks may require up to 30 ECTS of bridging courses (e.g., “Fundamentals of Geochemistry” or “Intro to Environmental Policy”) if prior training is insufficient, ensuring a leveled classroom at year 1, term 1.</p> <p>3. The “End of studies dissertation” is a 20 ECTS supervised research project (5 months), preceded by a 5 ECTS “Apprentissage du mémoire” workshop. Students submit a 10–12 page exposé by December 15 in their 3rd semester; upon approval, fieldwork/lab/modeling begins under a co-supervisor from IGEAT or ULB faculty. Final thesis (≤ 75 pages, Times New Roman 11 pt) is uploaded to Antares for plagiarism check, and students</p>	-	<p>Both M-ENVIE and M-ENVIG are fully accredited by the French-speaking Community of Belgium (Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles) and comply with EHEA (Bologna) standards, ensuring recognition across Europe. The programmes undergo regular internal quality reviews by AEQES (Agency for the Evaluation of the Quality of Higher Education), which confirmed ULB’s thematic “blocs” approach as exemplary in 2021.</p>

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
				publicly defend before a jury in May/June of their 4th semester. The public defense is 5 ECTS, distinct from the thesis credit, and is open to external stakeholders.		
Czech Republic	University of Chemistry and Technology	-	<p>1. Sustainable Wastewater Treatment & Pollutant Management - Inspired by the NEUTEN project, this research targets the development of energy-efficient wastewater treatment methods that reduce micropollutants and nutrient discharge into aquatic systems. Supported by recent EU and national grants.</p> <p>2. Excursions for Applied Research - Students and researchers participate in field visits to key infrastructure sites such as the Podolí and Plzeň wastewater treatment plants, gaining practical exposure to advanced treatment technologies and environmental monitoring systems.</p> <p>3. Technopark Kralupy - A strategic innovation platform that enables pilot-scale testing, technology transfer, and industrial partnerships in sustainable chemistry and materials engineering. It supports commercialization of research outputs and hosts start-up incubators.</p> <p>4. Research and Technology Transfer Office (RTTO) - The RTTO provides project management support, seed funding for innovation, and administrative assistance for patent applications, licensing, and cooperation with industry. It plays a key role in promoting entrepreneurship and technology deployment at UCT Prague.</p>	<p>1. Teaching in English</p> <p>2. Environmental Engineering laboratories (over 15% ECTS)</p> <p>3. Elective Modules and Specialization Options (≥15% ECTS)</p>	<p>Laboratories: IECE – Institute of Environmental and Chemical Engineering https://fchi.vscht.cz/research/iece; DPEE – Department of Power Engineering and Ecology https://uve.vscht.cz; DWTEE – Department of Water Technology and Environmental Engineering https://tvp.vscht.cz; DEMCh – Department of Environmental Microbiology and Chemistry https://uch.vscht.cz; DOT – Department of Organic Technology https://ftop.vscht.cz; CLIA – Central Laboratories for Instrumental Analysis https://www.vscht.cz/homepage/research/clia; TKTTSL – Technopark Kralupy – Technology Transfer & Scale Lab https://www.vscht.cz/research/technology-transfer;</p>	-

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Denmark	Technical university of Denmark	-	The researchers and students at DTU work across disciplines on groundbreaking projects for the benefit of society. We collaborate with leading academic, private and public partners to create innovative solutions for sustainable change. Research areas include a broad spectrum of science and engineering disciplines, such as energy technology, climate technology, health technology and artificial intelligence.	1. This study programme is also available as an Industry study programme where you can combine work and study over a 4-year period. 2. This study programme gives you the opportunity to enrol in a joint international master's programmes and gain a unique specialization. 3. DTU's Blue Dot projects are student-driven undertakings that cross boundaries between study programmes, semesters and departments. Blue Dot projects are to produce sustainable solutions, and they make high demands on the participants because they run alongside the ordinary teaching schedule	1. Autonomous Systems Test Arena - DTU ASTA is one of the world's largest indoor infrastructures for testing mobile robot technology in three types of environment: land, air, water. 2. E-MAT - The E-MAT facility provides a cross-disciplinary environment and platform for discovering and synthesizing new functional energy materials and is located at DTU, Lyngby in Greater Copenhagen. 3. Groundbreaking research into sustainable waste utilization - Teaching and researching how we can best recover and utilize the resources we normally consider waste.	In 2014, DTU was granted an institutional accreditation by the Danish Accreditation Institution (member of ENQA). https://www.dtu.dk/english/-/media/dtu-endk/education/accreditation/institutional-accreditation-2014.pdf
Denmark	University of Copenhagen	The University of Copenhagen (UCPH) offers programmes and courses for exchange/international students who want to study at UCPH for one or two semesters.	Recent graduates from the programme are working both in Denmark and abroad e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In R&D departments in the chemical and pharmaceutical industry or in consulting firms, where they, for instance, develop products which are not harmful to the environment. • Within 'clean-tech', with developing air filters, soil remediation, and preventing water contamination. • In ministries and government agencies such as the Danish Environment Protection Agency or European Chemicals Agency with focus on assessing chemicals allowed in, for example, food and toys. • Develop nature and freshwater 	It is possible to study abroad as part of your MSc programme at Faculty of Science. A main objective of studying abroad is to further widen your academic knowledge and network. Students can, for example, work with thesis subjects such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hormone-disrupting substances. • The effect of air pollution on health. • Degradation of oil and pesticides in soil. • Toxicity of heavy metals to humans and organisms in the soil. • Risk assessment of harmful substances. • You may also investigate what the implications are when several substances are present at the same time; the so-called cocktail 	-	-

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			ecosystems, for example, rivers and wetlands, diverse grassland and meadows, and restoration of habitats for endangered species. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling natural hazards and disasters caused by chemical pollution e.g., oil spills and waste. • Within legislation and regulation in, for example, ministries or in municipalities and regions in Denmark or in international authorities and expert organisations e.g., EU, UNFCCC, or FAO • Sino-Danish Center for Education and Research (SDC) is a partnership between eight Danish universities, the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Higher Education, the Chinese university University of Chinese Academy of Sciences (UCAS), and the Chinese research institute Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS). The aim of SDC is to promote and strengthen collaboration between Danish and Chinese research and education environments for the benefit of both countries. 	effect. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students can collaborate with both private and public companies, organisations, NGOs etc. You can ask your lecturers for suggestions or specific ideas on what to write about. It is your responsibility to find a company, organisation, or NGO to collaborate with. Unless you have received specific suggestions or ideas from your professor or lecturer, your master's thesis/project assignment must relate to your courses and comply with the academic rules and regulations • In Denmark, many students choose early on to focus on their job and career opportunities by writing their master's thesis or a project assignment in collaboration with a business or an organisation. This gives students the opportunity to learn about life at a workplace and dig into the company's challenges and potentials. 		
Denmark	Aarhus University	-	-	Around 12 per cent of AU's 36.000 students are international, representing over 100 nationalities.	1. Our understanding of the environment around us is largely dependent on the tools we have available. Like the first microscopes changed our perception of the world and lead to the discovery of microorganisms, current technological developments help us unravel the complexity of living systems. Due to the vast complexity, heterogeneity, and varying scale of biological systems we need a variety of tools and methods.2. Sensor	-

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					Lab: Sensors make chemistry visible/measurable and are essential tools to understand biological processes. We want to understand how the chemical environment effects biological processes and organisms and, in turn, how the chemical environment is effected by the biology.3. UAS4Ecology Lab – Laboratory for Ecological Research with Drones uses 'Unmanned Aerial Systems' (UAS) to collect data and to answer fundamental and applied ecological questions. UAS4Ecology Lab was established in 2016 by Professor Signe Normand, who today is the scientific leader of the laboratory. Urs Treier is the UAS4Ecology Lab manager	
Aalborg University	Aalborg University offers many guest, exchange and joint master programmes.	-	As a student at AAU you acquire knowledge and competences by way of AAU's unique study method "The Aalborg Model for Problem Based Learning (PBL)".	Laboratories: 1. The VSA apparatus is used to generate automatic moisture sorption isotherms. Water vapor sorption isotherms are crucial in determining moisture retention and release in building constructions. It is capable of achieving both static and dynamic isotherms by the Dynamic Vapour Sorption (DVS) and Dynamic Dew Point Isotherm (DDI) methods respectively. The VSA is commonly used in the food-industry and medical field, but is also applicable to building materials, in favour of the time-consuming standard methods. The VSA is able to achieve isotherms in the range of 3% to 95% relative	Aalborg University's quality assurance system ensures that the work relating to quality assurance and to the quality development of the University's study programmes will result in the fulfilment of the objectives described in the University's quality assurance policy within the area of education. https://www.politics-society.aau.dk/study-programmes/quality-assurance	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
				humidity at temperatures ranging from 15 – 60°C.		
University of Southern Denmark		Research Areas •Chemical process engineering • Functional materials and fuel cells • Biomass technology • Processing of vegetable raw materials for food, feed and natural medicine • System analysis and environmentally efficient technology • Biosystems technology	SDU offers around 60 programmes taught in English. You become part of a project based and problem based study environment where you work in project groups. You and your fellow students are responsible for planning and carrying out the project – and for meeting the deadlines. Usually we receive the project outlines from companies and we emphasise that the problems you solve are 'real world' problems. In addition, individual in-company projects are encouraged and facilitated in the third semester. SDU has program for choose from a comprehensive list of courses and gain an experience that will last you a lifetime! from over 40 countries for a two week intensive international Summer School in August	-	As a recognised higher education institution in Denmark, SDU is accredited under the Danish accreditation legislation for higher education. The accreditation results from SDU's ability to ensure a high degree of quality and relevance in its study programmes. SDU's latest accreditation process The evaluation of SDU's quality work was carried out by an accreditation panel (appointed by the Danish Accreditation Institution) consisting of academic experts from universities in Denmark, Sweden and Norway. https://www.sdu.dk/en/om-sdu/strategi-politikker/uddannelseskvalitet/nia20	
Tallinn University of Technology	-	Contributions to Horizon Europe Projects; International Mobility and ERASMUS+ Exchanges; Research on Climate Adaptation Strategies.	The Environmental Engineering and Management (MSc) program at Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) is fully accredited by the Estonian Quality Agency for Education (HAKA), ensuring compliance with the rigorous standards of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA).	GIS and Remote Sensing Laboratory; Sustainable Technologies and Energy Systems Laboratory.	The program integrates with industry through practical training and collaborative projects, fostering hands-on experience in environmental engineering.	International Mobility and ERASMUS+ Exchanges; Research on Climate Adaptation Strategies.
Aalto University	-	Research is an integral part of the curriculum, with opportunities for students to participate in	The Water and Environmental Engineering – Master of Science (Technology) program at Aalto University emphasizes strong	Water Quality Laboratory; Hydrology and Flow Modeling Laboratory; Environmental	-	-

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		multidisciplinary projects, including: Climate Change Impact on Water Resources; Wastewater Treatment and Resource Recovery; Sustainable Urban Water Infrastructure; Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity Conservation; International Water Governance and Policy Analysis.	practical skills alongside theoretical knowledge. Students are actively engaged in laboratory work and research projects that address real-world environmental challenges.	Pollution Analysis Laboratory; GIS and Remote Sensing Laboratory.		
University of Oulu	-	Arctic Water Resources Management; Groundwater Pollution and Remediation; Sustainable Wastewater Treatment; River Restoration Projects; Climate Adaptation Strategies for Water Systems.	-	Water Laboratory; Geophysics and Hydrology Laboratory; Environmental Chemistry Laboratory; Laboratory: Environmental monitoring and management using remote sensing and GIS technologies.	-	-
Tampere University	-	Sustainable Water Management; Climate Change and Hydrological Modeling; Wastewater Treatment and Resource Recovery; Ecosystem and Water Quality Monitoring.	-	Water Quality and Treatment Laboratory; Hydrology and Water Systems Laboratory; Environmental Toxicology Laboratory; GIS and Environmental Modeling Laboratory.	-	-
Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology (LUT)	-	Circular Economy and Waste Management; Sustainable Water Management; Climate Change Mitigation.	-	Environmental Simulation Laboratory; Renewable Energy Laboratory; Water Quality & Waste Management Lab; Sustainability and Materials Lab; Environmental Technology Laboratory; Renewable Energy Systems Laboratory; Air Quality and Climate Change Laboratory.	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
University of Eastern Finland	-	Air Quality and Health; Water Purification Technologies; Radiation Exposure Assessment.	-	Environmental Health Laboratory; Radiation Safety Laboratory; Water Quality Laboratory.	-	-
École Polytechnique de Paris	-	Sustainable Water Management in Urban Areas; Innovations in Renewable Energy Integration; Climate Adaptation Strategies for Cities.	1. Real-world case studies in Environmental Protection 2. Interdisciplinary project modules 3. Cooperation with industrial and public sector partners on environmental issues	Water and Soil Protection Laboratory; Air Quality and Emissions Laboratory; Environmental Chemistry and Analysis Laboratory	-	-
Centrale Méditerranée	-	Urban Water Management and Smart Drainage Systems, Circular Economy and Sustainable Resource Management, Climate-resilient Infrastructure and Environmental Risk Assessment.	1. Multidisciplinary project-based courses integrating civil, chemical, and environmental engineering challenges 2. Close collaboration with industry and municipalities on real-life water and waste treatment projects 3. Use of simulation tools and GIS in environmental modeling and planning	Environmental Engineering Laboratory, Hydraulic Engineering and Water Resources Laboratory, Waste Management and Recycling Laboratory	-	-
Grenoble INP - Ense³	-	Groundwater Contamination Remediation, Microbial Technologies for Wastewater, Life Cycle Assessment of Urban Infrastructure, Environmental Modeling and Simulation.	1. Focusing on fundamentals while remaining adaptable to emerging technologies. 2. Ensuring a balance of theoretical knowledge with practical, hands-on learning. 3. Allowing space for specialization while fostering well-rounded engineers who can collaborate across disciplines.	Basic Electronics Lab; Mathematics for Engineers Lab; Digital Circuits Lab; Programming and Simulation Lab.	-	-
Université de Poitiers - ENSIP	-	Development of low-energy wastewater treatment systems; Innovative technologies for air pollutant reduction; Modeling urban water management systems; Circular economy solutions for plastic waste.	1. Industrial collaboration projects on wastewater treatment. 2. Field excursions to municipal and industrial environmental facilities. 3. Participation in international environmental case study competitions.	Environmental Process Engineering Laboratory; Water Quality and Wastewater Treatment Lab; Air Quality Monitoring Lab; Solid Waste and Recycling Technology Laboratory.	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
INSA Toulouse	-	Sustainable Water Management in Urban Areas; Innovations in Renewable Energy Integration; Climate Adaptation Strategies for Cities	1. Real-world case studies in Environmental Protection 2. Interdisciplinary project modules 3. Cooperation with industrial and public sector partners on environmental issues	Water and Soil Protection Laboratory ; Air Quality and Emissions Laboratory; Environmental Chemistry and Analysis Laboratory.	-	-
Leibniz University Hannover	-	Sustainable Water Management in Urban Areas; Innovations in Renewable Energy Integration; Climate Adaptation Strategies for Cities	1. Real-world case studies in Environmental Protection 2. Interdisciplinary project modules 3. Cooperation with industrial and public sector partners on environmental issues	Water and Soil Protection Laboratory; Air Quality and Emissions Laboratory; Environmental Chemistry and Analysis Laboratory	-	-
Technical University of Munich	-	Urban Water Management and Smart Drainage Systems, Circular Economy and Sustainable Resource Management, Climate-resilient Infrastructure and Environmental Risk Assessment	1. Multidisciplinary project-based courses integrating civil, chemical, and environmental engineering challenges 2. Close collaboration with industry and municipalities on real-life water and waste treatment projects 3. Use of simulation tools and GIS in environmental modeling and planning	Environmental Engineering Laboratory, Hydraulic Engineering and Water Resources Laboratory, Waste Management and Recycling Laboratory	-	-
KIT, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	-	Groundwater Contamination Remediation, Microbial Technologies for Wastewater, Life Cycle Assessment of Urban Infrastructure, Environmental Modeling and Simulation	1. Sustainability-focused Engineering Workshops 2. Cross-disciplinary Design Projects 3. Industrial Cooperation in Environmental Systems	Soil and Groundwater Remediation Lab; Air Quality and Emissions Lab; Environmental Biotechnology Lab; Hydrology and Hydraulic Engineering Lab.	-	-
Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH)	-	Development of low-energy wastewater treatment systems; Innovative technologies for air pollutant reduction; Modeling urban water management systems; Circular economy	1. Industrial collaboration projects on wastewater treatment. 2. Field excursions to municipal and industrial environmental facilities. 3. Participation in international environmental case study competitions.	Environmental Process Engineering Laboratory; Water Quality and Wastewater Treatment Lab; Air Quality Monitoring Lab; Solid Waste and Recycling Technology Laboratory.	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
		solutions for plastic waste.				
Universität Stuttgart	-	Sustainable Water Management in Urban Areas; Innovations in Renewable Energy Integration; Climate Adaptation Strategies for Cities	1. Real-world case studies in Environmental Protection 2. Interdisciplinary project modules 3. Cooperation with industrial and public sector partners on environmental issues	Water and Soil Protection Laboratory ; Air Quality and Emissions Laboratory; Environmental Chemistry and Analysis Laboratory.	-	-
RWTH Aachen University	-	Sustainable Water Management in Urban Areas; Innovations in Renewable Energy Integration; Climate Adaptation Strategies for Cities	1. Real-world case studies in Environmental Protection 2. Interdisciplinary project modules 3. Cooperation with industrial and public sector partners on environmental issues	Water and Soil Protection Laboratory; Air Quality and Emissions Laboratory; Environmental Chemistry and Analysis Laboratory	-	-
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	-	H2TRANS project: developing the first hydrogen fuel station in Greece; NEXOGENESIS project: assess water-energy-food-ecosystem system; CLIMPACT project: scientific research on climate change in Greece	1. Green energy technology pilot projects 2. Environmental monitoring and data analysis 3. Developing sustainable development strategies	Energy and Environment Research Laboratory (E2ReLab); Environmental Research Laboratory (EREL); Laboratory of Climatology and Atmospheric Environment (LACAE)	-	-
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)	-	Sustainable Water Management in Urban Areas; Climate Change Impact on Coastal Environments; Waste to Energy Technologies	1. Field-based learning and real case studies 2. Interdisciplinary collaboration 3. Integration of new technologies (GIS, Remote Sensing)	Environmental Engineering Laboratory; Water Quality Control Laboratory; Soil and Waste Laboratory	-	-
University of Crete	-	Sustainable Urban Water Management; Air Quality Monitoring and Modeling; Waste Valorization Technologies; Climate Change Impact on Coastal Areas	1. Problem-based learning (PBL) 2. Field trips and on-site training 3. Interdisciplinary project development 4. Simulation and Modeling Workshops 5. Participation in International Environmental Competitions	Environmental Chemistry Laboratory; Hydraulics and Environmental Fluid Mechanics Laboratory; Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory; Remote Sensing and GIS Laboratory	-	-

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University of Patras	-	-	1. Industrial collaboration projects 2. Field excursions 3. Participation in competitions	Environmental Process Engineering Laboratory; Water Quality and Wastewater Treatment Laboratory; Air Quality Monitoring Laboratory; Solid Waste and Recycling Technology Laboratory	-	-
University of Ioannina	-	Impact of climate change on water resources; Biological waste processing; Air quality modeling	1. Multimodal education 2. The educational process focused on scientific research 3. Attention to climate change and environmental problems	Environmental Chemistry Laboratory; Microbiology Laboratory; Environmental Processes Laboratory	-	-
Trinity College Dublin, The University of Dublin	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Environmental Science and Climate Research Labs; Urban Ecology and Sustainability Labs; Environmental Engineering and Geoscience Labs	-	-
University College Cork	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Marine and Environmental Science Labs; Sustainable Energy and Climate Innovation Labs; Environmental Geoscience and Engineering Labs	-	-
University College Dublin	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Environmental Science and Renewable Energy Labs; Climate Adaptation and Urban Ecology Labs; Environmental Engineering and Geoscience Labs	-	-
University of Galway	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Environmental Science and Marine Research Labs; Sustainable Energy and Climate Innovation Labs; Geoscience and Environmental Engineering Labs	-	-
Politecnico di Milano	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Cleanroom & Nanotechnology Laboratories; Sustainable Energy and Mobility Labs; Environmental Engineering and Geotechnical Labs	-	-
Politecnico di Torino	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International	Cleanroom & Nanotech Lab Facilities; Sustainable Mobility and Energy Labs; Environmental	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
			Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Innovation Projects	Engineering and Geotechnical Testing Centers		
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies – Pisa	-	-	1. Industry and Applied Research Integration 2. Joint International Master's and PhD Programmes 3. Student-Initiated Research and Innovation Projects	TeCIP Institute; Institute of Life Sciences; Land Lab – Sustainability and Circular Economy	-	-
Sapienza University of Rome	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Environmental Chemistry and Pollution Control Labs; Renewable Energy and Sustainable Infrastructure Labs	-	-
University of Bologna	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Center for Sustainable Development and Climate Change; Environmental Chemistry and Ecology Labs; Circular Economy Research Group	-	-
University of Milan	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Advanced Research Laboratories in Biosciences and Nanotechnology; Environmental and Energy Research Centers; Data Science and Artificial Intelligence Labs	-	-
University of Naples Federico II	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Blue Dot Projects	Autonomous Vehicle Engineering (MOVE); Industrial Chemistry for Circular and Bio Economy labs	-	-
University of Padua	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Innovation Projects	Environmental Engineering Labs; Centre for Climate and Environmental Changes; Renewable Energy and Smart Grids Laboratory; Marine Biology Field Station (Chioggia)	-	-
University of Pisa	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Blue Dot Projects	Environmental Science & Technology Labs; Centre for Climate Change Studies; Bio-Economy and Circular Economy Labs; Marine Ecology Research Station	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
University of Turin	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Blue Dot Projects	Autonomous Systems Test Arena (DTU ASTA); E-MAT; Groundbreaking research into sustainable waste utilization	-	-
Università di Padova	The University of Padua is actively involved in several Erasmus Mundus and joint master's programmes in partnership with top universities worldwide. These programmes offer dual degrees and international specialization in fields such as global forestry, sustainable territorial development, and environmental sustainability, giving students valuable global perspectives and research opportunities.	Students at the University of Padua participate in multidisciplinary, student-led projects that address real-world environmental challenges. These initiatives promote sustainability, innovation, and community engagement, and are designed to run in parallel with formal academic studies, fostering leadership and collaborative skills.	University of Padua offers flexible and innovative study options that integrate academic coursework with professional internships and research placements in collaboration with industry and environmental agencies. This structure enhances students' hands-on skills, bridges theory with practice, and prepares them for dynamic roles in the environmental and sustainability sectors.	Advanced Environmental and Sustainability Labs. Equipped for air, water, and soil analysis, these labs support research in climate change, pollution monitoring, biodiversity conservation, and circular economy practices. Marine and Freshwater Biology Research Centers. Specialized facilities focus on aquatic ecosystems, supporting work in marine biodiversity, water quality assessment, and conservation of freshwater habitats. Renewable Energy and Climate Modeling Labs. These labs enable interdisciplinary research on solar energy, wind systems, and climate simulations, advancing innovation in sustainable energy and environmental forecasting.		
University of Latvia	-	-	1. Industry Study Programme Option 2. Joint International Master's Programmes 3. Student-Driven Sustainability Projects	Biodiversity and Ecology Research Facilities; Climate Change and Renewable Energy Research Labs	-	-
Gdańsk University of Technology	You also have the opportunity to participate in a Double-Degree programme in collaboration with the University of Palermo	-	1. No tuition fee for EU students 2. Thesis Seminar and Thesis Exam Preparation	Department of Geotechnical and Hydraulic Engineering; Laboratory facilities available online	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
Cracow University of Technology	The best students have the opportunity to complete the second and third semesters at Università degli Studi di Cagliari and obtain double diplomas	-	-	Laboratory information available on university website	-	-
Warsaw University of Technology	-	-	1. No tuition fee for EU students 2. BSc and MSc accredited by EURO-ACE® label	-	-	-
Czestochowa University of Technology	-	-	1. You can start this course in February and it lasts for 3 semesters	Specialized equipment available on faculty website	-	-
University of Aveiro	-	AX-COAST; NEUTEN; RemediGrass; RadoNorm; A-AAGORA; RESTORE4Cs; SMARTDEC; BIOPROTECT; TERRASAFE; ABSolEU	1. Teaching in Portuguese and English 2. Environmental Engineering seminar (5%ECTS) 3. Free options (5%ECTS) and conditional options (5%ECTS)	CESAM; CICECO; TEMA; RISCO; BESIDE	-	-
University of Porto	Possibility of having a Specialization in Environmental Engineering without the thesis	RaMP; CYCON; Healthy Waters; HyGreen&LowEmissions; LaNSILOT; VOC Advanced; Power2METHANE; BIOSYSMO; Net4CleanAir; HI_MOV	1. Teaching in English (and also Portuguese) 2. Preliminary Project (8,75%ECTS) 3. Free options (5%ECTS) and several conditional options (36,25%ECTS)	LAMUR; LEPABE; CIIMAR; INESC TEC	-	-
Nova University Lisbon	-	CIRCOMOD; CitySelfy; Blue Bioeconomy Pact; BioAgroFloRes; CHyTec; ks4MAQ; CRESTING; ENTRACK; ENVISION; RELIEF	1. Intercalary period between the 1st and 2nd semester for entrepreneurship (2,5%ECTS) 2. The Environmental Engineering Project (5%) developed with external partner 3. Several conditional options (37,5%ECTS) 4. Two specializations: "Environmental	CENSE; UNIDEMI	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
			Management and Systems" or "Sanitary Engineering"			
University of Lisbon	-	CIDMA; SCORE; GEONETC; SYNAPPS; MooB; CRITERIA; ValorWaste; IProPBio; GREENFUEL; ISIS	1. Possibility of taking a Minor with multidisciplinary optional courses (18 ECTS) 2. Extra-curricular activities may be credited to a maximum of 6 ECTS 3. Part of the curriculum is of fully free choice (22,5%ECTS) 4. Taught by Instituto Superior Técnico and Instituto Superior de Agronomia 5. Authorized to operate in the People's Republic of China	CERIS; CERENA	-	-
University of Cyprus	-	No information	Some Testimonials available online	-	-	-
Cyprus International University	-	No information	No information	-	-	-
Open University of Cyprus	-	No information	No information	-	-	-
University Politehnica of Bucharest	-	-	1. Working visits: Water treatment/purification plants; Soil remediation platforms; Waste sorting/recycling stations	-	-	-
Politehnica University of Timișoara	-	-	-	-	-	-
Babeș-Bolyai University (Cluj-Napoca)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dunărea de Jos University of Galați	-	-	-	-	-	-
Slovak University of	-	Research on water and air purification, circular	1. Laboratory-oriented learning with direct access to modern instruments	Environmental Chemistry Laboratory, Wastewater Treatment	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
Technology in Bratislava (STU)		economy, biowaste valorisation, and climate resilience	2. Student involvement in EU-funded environmental research projects 3. Interdisciplinary cooperation with chemical and biological engineering departments	Lab, Analytical Instrumentation Lab		
University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Trnava (UCM)	-	Applied research in air pollution control, environmental monitoring, and green technologies	1. Integration of risk-based environmental modeling in course projects 2. Use of modern lab equipment for pollution analysis 3. Collaboration with municipal and industrial partners for applied projects	Environmental Chemistry Lab, Pollution Control Lab, GIS Lab	-	-
University of Ljubljana	-	Research in hydrology, flood management, sustainable urban water systems, and EU water directives compliance	1. Strong integration of field work with academic instruction 2. Collaboration with governmental and private sector in water management projects 3. Emphasis on interdisciplinary and international project-based learning	Hydraulics Laboratory, Environmental Engineering Lab, Geodesy and Remote Sensing Lab	-	-
Technical University of Madrid	-	Projects on circular economy, air pollution modeling, industrial waste valorization, advanced water treatment	1. Applied research projects linked to real environmental engineering challenges 2. Laboratory work integrated with professional and academic field visits 3. Participation in European innovation and sustainability networks (LIFE, H2020)	Water Quality Lab, Environmental Engineering Lab, Pilot Plant for Waste Treatment	-	-
University of Santiago de Compostela	-	Participation in European projects (H2020, LIFE), collaboration with research centres such as CIEMAT and CSIC	1. Strong interdisciplinary component with integration of science and engineering 2. Access to specialised laboratories in environmental analysis and microbiology 3. International cooperation in environmental research programmes	Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Microbiology Laboratory, Chemical Engineering Laboratory	-	-
University of Seville	-	Collaboration in European and national environmental sustainability projects,	1. Direct link with the professional sector through curricular internships in companies 2. Technical training complemented with a legal and environmental management vision	Environmental Engineering Laboratory, Applied Chemistry Laboratory, Air Pollution Laboratory	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
		teaching innovation and R&D&I programmes	3. Faculty with experience in applied research and knowledge transfer			
Polytechnic University of Cartagena	-	National and international projects (Horizon Europe, LIFE) in sustainability, energy and environmental management	1. Collaboration with companies in the environmental sector for professional internships 2. International mobility and participation in Erasmus+ programmes 3. Access to R&D&I projects with institutions and technology centres	Environmental Engineering, Water Technologies, Microalgae and Industrial Safety Laboratories	-	-
University of Huelva and International University of Andalucía	-	Collaboration with research centres and companies in projects financed by the LIFE and Horizon Europe programmes	1. External internships in companies in the environmental sector 2. International mobility to complete training in European universities 3. Participation in R&D&I projects in sustainability and the environment	Environmental Pollution, Renewable Energy and Chemical Analysis Laboratories	-	-
University of A Coruña	-	Participation in European and national projects on pollution control, sustainability and environmental assessment	1. Strong integration of multidisciplinary research teams in environmental sciences and technology 2. Close collaboration with public and private environmental institutions 3. Active participation of students in environmental monitoring projects	Environmental Chemistry Lab, Ecology Lab, Soil Analysis Lab	-	-
Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)	-	Participation in international projects on circular economy, renewable energy, and environmental remediation (H2020, Horizon Europe)	1. Project-based learning in collaboration with industry 2. Interdisciplinary research and teaching teams 3. Access to modern laboratories and international mobility opportunities	Environmental Engineering Lab, Energy Efficiency Lab, Analytical Chemistry Lab	The master's degree is accredited with the EUR-ACE international quality seal of the European Network for Accreditation of Engineering Education (ENAE)	-
University of Cantabria (in collaboration with University of the Basque Country - UPV/EHU)	-	Projects related to climate change adaptation, sustainable waste and water systems (funded by national and EU programmes)	1. Joint delivery with the University of the Basque Country offering multidisciplinary exposure 2. Close collaboration with public institutions and environmental consulting firms 3. Integration of real environmental projects into the curriculum	Hydraulics Lab, Environmental Chemistry Lab, Waste Management and Water Treatment Lab	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
European University of the Atlantic	-	Applied projects in collaboration with UNEATLANTICO research centers in water, soil, air quality and energy systems	1. Flexibility through asynchronous online learning format 2. Integration of real case studies and professional context in course content 3. Emphasis on sustainability, renewable energy and circular economy in all modules	Virtual labs for simulation of environmental analysis, pollution control, and energy systems	The Ibero-American University Foundation (FUNIBER) grants financial aid scholarships for these master's degrees	-
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)	Double degree opportunities with international partner institutions	Research linked to national and international projects on water reuse, climate change adaptation, and circular economy	1. Participation in industry-driven projects as part of coursework 2. Access to high-level laboratories for water treatment, air pollution, and waste technologies	Environmental Engineering Lab, Hydraulics Lab, Waste Management Lab	-	-
KTH Royal Institute of Technology	-	Research centres in Digitalisation, Energy, Industrial transformation, Life Science, Materials, Transport, Sustainable development	Teaching in English	KTH Environmental Humanities Laboratory (EHL)	-	-
Lund University	-	Our research contributes to a better understanding of the problems around us, but also to solving current and future environmental and climate crises. Research environments: Aerosols, Agrifood economics, Biodiversity data, Carbon cycle research, Circular biobased economy, Climate-neutral cities 2030, Energy transition, Environmental and climate science, Industrial environmental economics, Innovation research, Narrating climate futures, Polar research, Public transport, Sustainability	1. Possibility of having a Specialization in Environmental Engineering without the thesis 2. Teaching in English 3. Preliminary Project (8,75%ECTS) 4. Free options (5%ECTS) and several conditional options (36,25%ECTS)	LAMUR; LEPABE; CIIMAR; INESC TEC	-	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
		studies, Sustainable enterprise development, Sustainable finance and biodiversity, Sustainable land use, Sustainable societies, Sustainable water use				
Chalmers University of technology	-	CIRCOMOD; CitySelfy; Blue Bioeconomy Pact; BioAgroFloRes; CHyTec; ks4MAQ; CRESTING; ENTRACK; ENVISION; RELIEF	1. Intercalary period between the 1st and 2nd semester for entrepreneurship (2,5%ECTS) 2. The Environmental Engineering Project (5%) developed with external partner 3. Several conditional options (37,5%ECTS) 4. Two specializations: "Environmental Management and Systems" or "Sanitary Engineering"	CENSE; UNIDEMI	-	-
Middle East Technical University	-	Several research projects listed in WoS Research Areas: Environmental Sciences, Environment/Ecology. Research groups: Waste Valorization and Environmental Materials Research Group; Advanced Technologies (SITE) Platform for Sustainable Cities	-	Environmental Engineering; Air Pollution Laboratory; Chemistry Laboratory; Microbiology Laboratory; Basic Operations Laboratory	ABET Accreditation	-
Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	-	Sustainable Land Use Management and Reconstruction of Destructed Ecosystem in the Arctic Region; Developing A Biological And Ecological Remediation Method Model For Oil-Polluted Soil; R&D Project on Production of Economically Valued	-	ITU Environmental Engineering Center Laboratory	Quality Management System; ITU Environmental Engineering Undergraduate Program: Accredited by the Engineering Accreditation Commission (EAC) of ABET	-

EU university	Double degree	Research	Educational	Laboratory	Quality assurance	Erasmus projects
		Carboxylic Acid from Chicken Waste Using Anaerobic Digestion Technology; Comparison of Single and Two Phase Anaerobic Digestion of Lignosellulosic Waste				
Boğaziçi University	-	No information	No information	SEWAGE SLUDGE (BIOSOLIDS) LABORATORY; ENVIRONMENTAL MICROBIOLOGY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY LABORATORY; ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSES LABORATORY; ANAEROBIC BIOLOGICAL TREATMENT LABORATORY; ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESSES LABORATORY; SOLID WASTE LABORATORY; MOLECULAR ECOLOGY AND PHILOGENETICS LABORATORY; SOIL POLLUTION LABORATORY; ECOTOXICOLOGY AND CHEMOMETRIC LABORATORY; SOLAR PHOTOCATALYTIC OXIDATION LABORATORY; BIOMASS AND MICROBIAL ECOLOGY LABORATORY; MOLECULAR EVOLUTION AND DNA BARCODING LABORATORY	-	-